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Understanding the role of endothelial cells in cerebral amyloid angiopathy in Down syndrome and *APP* microduplication

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Introduction

Introduction

I Down Syndrome (DS)

Down syndrome (DS), originally described in 1866 by John Langdon Down from whom its name derives[1], is associated with a wide range of physical and cognitive characteristics. It is the most common chromosomal abnormality linked to intellectual disability resulting from a complete (95% of cases), or partial duplication of the 21st chromosome[2,3]. It affects 3.3 to 6.7 per 10,000 individuals worldwide[3].

The most common physical phenotypes include flat facial profile, almond shape eyes, epicanthal fold, small nose and flat nasal bridge, small mouth with macroglossia, small low set ears, short neck with excess skin at the nape, hypotonia, short stature, presence of brachycephaly, single palmar crease, clinodactyly, sandal gap deformity and atlantoaxial instability (loose neck joints).[4–7] It is also considered the most common condition associated with intellectual disability, ranging from mild to moderate, delayed speech and language development, delayed motor milestones, increased risk of autism spectrum disorder and general behavioral issues.[8–10]

Beside intellectual disability, individuals with DS have increased risk for several pathologies such as cardiac malformations[11], diabetes[12,13], hypothyroidism[14], gastro intestinal defects[15], hematologic defect (increased risk of leukemia)[16], hearing[17] and vision defects[18], increased susceptibility to infections[19], obstructive sleep apnea[20], and obesity[21]. In addition, individuals with DS are at high risk for developing Alzheimer disease (AD) (77% in their 60s)[22]. They exhibit the same neuropathological hallmarks as those observed in individuals with AD in the general population, but at a much younger age. By their fourth decade, all individuals with DS show full-blown AD pathology, regardless of the presence of symptoms[23].

Clinical features associated with DS also occur in the general population but at different rates, severity or age of onset. Interestingly, individuals with DS have significant lower risk of developing solid tumors [24], arteriosclerosis[25] and arterial hypertension [21,26,27] suggesting protective mechanisms associated with the overexpression of genes from chromosome 21. They are also less prone to smoking [28]. The risk of vascular fibrosis and calcification was found to be lower in the hippocampus[29], but higher in the basal ganglia[30].

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II Cerebrovascular diseases in DS

Individuals with DS are at high risk for moyamoya disease (MMD, ORPHA:2573), a rare blood vessel condition affecting most commonly children, in which the carotid artery in the skull becomes blocked or narrowed. Its incidence is 0.086 to 0.94 per 100,000 individuals in the general population[31] while 9.5% of all MMD cases under 15 are DS[32]. This suggests shared developmental dysfunctions that contribute to the occlusion of the internal carotid artery and its proximal branches. Combined with the numerous case reports of vascular abnormalities in young individuals with DS[33–39], these findings indicate an increased vulnerability of the neurovascular unit (NVU) in DS from a very young age.

Cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) is characterized by an accumulation of amyloid β ($A\beta$) peptides in the walls of the cerebral blood vessels (Fig.1-1), resulting in vascular fragility, microbleeds and impaired blood flow. Sporadic CAA is most often present in the occipital cortex and other neocortical area while medial temporal structures and the hippocampus are less affected[40]. The first description of “plaques like incrustation” in the cerebral blood vessel of an individual with DS was reported in 1948[41]. Since then, numerous *post-mortem* studies have confirmed a significantly higher risk of CAA in individuals with DS, increasing their susceptibility to stroke and microbleed with aging[42–47]. While individuals with DS also face a high risk of developing AD, the interplay between CAA and AD remains to be fully elucidated.

Figure 1-1: Patterns of $A\beta$ immunostaining showing cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) and plaque deposition in the occipital cortex of an *APPdup* patient in arteries, arterioles (A) and capillaries (B). Adapted from Mann et al (2018)[44].

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III Alzheimer disease (AD) and cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) in DS

1. Molecular mechanisms: A β deposition and vascular dysfunction, which comes first?

AD is a progressive neurodegenerative disease characterized clinically by memory loss and cognitive decline, disorientation, and impaired praxis[48,49]. At the pathological level, it is defined by the deposition of extracellular A β peptides in the parenchyma and intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles composed of hyperphosphorylated tau[50,51] (Fig.1-2). AD is classified based on its pathology and underlying causes. Sporadic late onset AD (sLOAD) and sporadic early onset AD (sEOAD) are distinguished by their age of onset, clinical symptoms, pathology topography, and a greater genetic component often associated with sEOAD. They represent more than 95% of all AD cases[44,52,53].

Figure 1-2: *A: A β immunolabeling (Dako antibody) reveals a cored plaque with a dense focal center (arrowhead), surrounded by a halo and a diffuse corona of lightly labeled A β . B: A flame-shaped neurofibrillary tangle (arrow) labeled with AT8 antibody, with tau also accumulating in the dendritic shaft (arrowheads). Extracellular ghost tangles (small arrows) are also visible. Adapted from Duyckaerts et al. (2009)[54].*

Autosomal dominant AD (ADAD) results from point mutations in the Amyloid precursor protein gene (*APP*), Presenilin genes (*PSEN1* or *PSEN2*) [52], or microduplications of the *APP* locus (*APPdup*), with a total of three copies of that locus, as in DS[55]. DS, with three copies of chromosome 21, including the *APP* locus, is now considered as ADAD[56]. In ADAD cases with point mutations, alteration of APP processing leads to changes in A β production and deposition[57,58]. In contrast, DS and *APPdup* cases exhibit increased A β production due to overexpression of the *APP* gene[44,55]. CAA is present to varying degrees in both sAD and different forms of ADAD, highlighting its complex role in AD pathology[44].

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APP is a transmembrane glycoprotein[59] widely expressed in cells across various organs[60], including the vascular unit and the central nervous system. APP undergoes two major proteolytic processing pathways: the non-amyloidogenic pathway[61–63] (Fig.1-3B), which is the predominant route, and the amyloidogenic pathway (Fig.1-3C), which leads to A β production[61,64]. The balance between these pathways is crucial for APP metabolism and A β generation. A β is produced through the sequential cleavage of APP by two key enzymes. β -Secretase (Beta-Site APP-Cleaving Enzyme 1, BACE1) first cleaves APP in the extracellular domain, generating membrane-bound C-terminal fragments (CTF) [65]. γ -Secretase then processes CTF within the membrane, producing A β peptides[66]. BACE2, a homolog of BACE1, can also cleave APP but at alternative sites, including the β' -site (Fig.1-3A), resulting in shorter fragments. While BACE2 typical activity favors non-amyloidogenic processing[67], under certain pathological conditions BACE2 can act as a conditional β -secretase[68]. A β peptides range in length up to 49 amino acids[46,69]. A β 42 is prone to aggregation and primarily accumulates in amyloid plaques within the brain parenchyma, a hallmark of AD[70]. In addition, A β 40 and truncated A β peptides at both the amino and carboxi termini accumulate in blood vessels, where they are closely linked to CAA [46,71].

The origin of A β peptides deposited in the NVU is subject to multiple non-exclusive hypothesis. A β peptides could be (1) produced locally by cells from the NVU, the cells proven to produce A β are the endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells[72] and glial cells[73–75]; (2) imported from the parenchyma for clearance through peri-vascular drainage[76], or (3) coming from the periphery, produced in other organs[60,77] and seeding in the NVU (Fig.1-4). Moreover, positive correlation between glymphatic system dysfunction and CAA severity has been found in sporadic CAA[78]. Despite extensive research, the precise mechanisms underlying A β production and aggregation in blood vessels, the specific cell types, and the distinct roles of different A β species in CAA and AD remain unclear. In fact, diagnosis of CAA *in vivo* remained a challenge for a long time.

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Figure 1-3: representation of APP processing pathways. **(A)** The A β peptide sequence spans part of the ectodomain and the transmembrane region (red). **(B)** In the non-amyloidogenic pathway, APP is cleaved by α -secretase, followed by γ -secretase, preventing A β formation. **(C)** In the amyloidogenic pathway, APP is first cleaved by BACE1 (β -secretase), then by γ -secretase, generating A β peptides. Both pathways produce soluble ectodomains (sAPP α or sAPP β) and a shared intracellular domain (AICD). Adapted from O'Brien and Wong (2011)[79]. **D:** The γ -secretase complex sequentially cleaves the APP in two pathways generating A β peptides of various length. Adapted from Potier et al. (2024)[80].

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Figure 1-4: Hypothesis of the origin of Aβ peptides in CAA. Aβ peptides could be (1) produced locally by cells from the NVU, (2) imported from the parenchyma for clearance, or (3) coming from the periphery, produced in other organs. Reproduced from Valay and Potier (2025)[81]

2. Identification of CAA in DS: *post-mortem* studies

Until the late 1990s, CAA was primarily studied in *post-mortem* samples from individuals with sporadic AD, including few individuals with DS[77,82–94]. This limited number of DS samples was likely due to the challenges in obtaining them, as well as the discovery that in AD and DS, Aβ deposits were very similar[95]. Early studies focusing on Aβ, considered DS similar to AD and did not differentiate them in their analyses[70,96–102] (Supplementary Table 1). The first large comparative study was published by David M. A. Mann's group in 1989[103]. This study examined 44 *post-mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS and highlighted the progression of Aβ deposition throughout the lifespan of individuals with DS, showing the vast predominance of vascular deposition after 40 years old, and paving the way for a series of

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influential papers with large cohorts and key discoveries[104–106,44]. A few other studies also utilized a large number of *post-mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS but did not identify any significant difference between DS and AD [107,108]. As *post-mortem* brains from individual with DS became more accessible and new research and diagnostic tools emerged, the number of studies on the molecular mechanisms and link between AD, CAA in DS increased[43,45].

In a paper published in 2018 by Mann's team[44], 152 *post-mortem* brain samples were used to study the pattern and severity of vascular A β in ADAD, DS, sAD and controls. The samples were divided into six categories: 4 patients from two families with *APP*dup (three from the same family), 34 individuals with DS, 16 patients with missense mutation in the *APP* gene, 34 patients diagnosed with sEOAD, 34 diagnosed with sLOAD, and finally, 30 elderly controls. In the paper, they separated CAA into different types including: type 1 CAA involving abundant diffuse and cored A β plaques across the cerebral cortex, with amyloid deposition restricted to leptomeningeal vessels; type 2 CAA also featuring numerous plaques, with CAA extending into both leptomeningeal and penetrating cortical arteries, particularly in the occipital cortex and type 3 with CAA in both capillaries and arteries, especially in the primary visual cortex, but accompanied by relatively few A β plaques. This major study led to numerous results. First, amyloid plaques were more abundant both in DS and missense *APP* mutations compared to sEOAD and sLOAD cases, while there was no significant difference between sEOAD and sLOAD (Fig.1-5A). Second, the severity of CAA was significantly higher in *APP*dup and missense *APP* mutations, as well as in DS, compared to sAD (Fig.1-5B). Third, in DS, sLOAD, and controls, type 1 CAA was significantly more predominant compared to types 2 and 3. However, in *APP*dup, type 3 was the principal CAA phenotype (Fig.1-5C). In summary, their study suggested that missense *APP* mutation, *APP*dup and DS are associated with the most severe CAA compared to sAD and controls. Additionally, the study highlighted differences between *APP*dup and DS with higher frequency of the more severe type3 CAA in *APP*dup, despite their shared characteristic of having three copies of the *APP* gene, indicating that other genes on chromosome 21 may influence CAA. However, one crucial limit to this study was the low number of *APP*dup cases due to the rare occurrence of such genetic disease.

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Figure 1-5: **A:** Box plots of scores for severity of plaques. **B:** Box plots of scores for severity of CAA. **C:** Percentage frequency of the four CAA phenotypes within each of six different pathological AD groups. Adapted from Mann et al. (2018)[44].

In a more recent study from the team[46], 51 *post-mortem* brain samples analyzed, with 15 samples from aged-matched controls, 11 with sAD, 6 with *APP* point mutations, 7 with *APPdup* from 6 families (Fig.1-6B), 8 from individuals with DS and AD neuropathology (DSAD) and 7 from individuals with DS but no AD. By performing immunostaining of A β on cortical sections, they found that A β deposits were present in small quantity in the parenchyma but absent from the blood vessels in the four cases with DS without AD, while deposits were present in the parenchyma and in blood vessels of DSAD cases (Fig.1-6B). This suggested that a threshold of A β in the parenchyma might be required to develop CAA. However, in samples with *APPdup*, despite the massive amyloid deposits in the blood vessels, parenchymal A β levels were similar to those observed in DS without AD (Fig.1-6B). Overall, these results suggest that individuals with DS are protected against CAA compared to those with *APPdup*, which could imply the presence of protective mechanisms due to the overexpression of genes from chromosome 21.

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Figure 1-6: See next page for legend

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Figure 1-6: **A:** Quantification of $A\beta$ and Tau pathologies in post-mortem human cortex from controls, *sAD*, *DS*, *DS-AD*, *APPdup* and *APP* mutations. Heatmap showing mean scores over multiple samples. **B:** Parenchymal and vascular $A\beta$ deposit differences between cases with *APPdup*, *DS* and *DS-AD*. Heatmap of scores across cases revealed striking differences between *APPdup* and *DS-AD*. Lightest blue corresponds to score 0, and darkest blue to score 3. **C:** Overlap of the duplicated segment from *Chr21* in various cases with *APPdup* includes two genes: *APP* and *GABPA*. Adapted from Kasri et al. (2024)[46].

3. Imaging CAA in DS *in vivo*

The diagnosis of CAA has evolved significantly with advancements in biomarkers and imaging techniques. Historically, CAA could only be confirmed *post-mortem* through histopathological examination of amyloid deposits in cerebral vessels[109]. The introduction of the Boston criteria in the 1990s allowed for the diagnosis of probable CAA in living patients using brain imaging, moving the diagnostic process from *post-mortem* examination to clinical settings.[109] Furthermore, imaging modalities such as susceptibility-weighted MRI and amyloid-PET now enable *in vivo* detection of characteristic hemorrhagic and amyloid deposition patterns[110–112]. MRI, particularly using T2*-weighted GRE or SWI, reveals microbleeds which are key radiological markers supporting the Boston criteria for probable CAA[47,113].

A meta-analysis on case reports suggested that in individuals with DS, the occurrence of intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) may be greatly reduced compared to *APPdup* by nearly 10 times [114]. However, a later study found that while a reduction is present, it is less significant than initially estimated but remains 2 fold[42]. Interestingly two individuals with DS and ICH detected on MRI showed no clinical symptoms of ICH[42]. Furthermore, individuals with DS appeared to have significantly more lobar microbleeds than EOAD patients, as in other forms of ADAD. In a later study, individuals with DS were also found to have significantly more microbleeds than controls without impacting cognitive performance[47].

IV Biomarkers of CAA

CAA exhibits a unique cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarker profile compared to healthy controls (HC) and AD patients. Specifically, CSF $A\beta_{40}$ levels are reduced in CAA relative to both HC and AD, whereas tau and phosphorylated tau (p-tau) levels are elevated in CAA compared to HC but remain lower than those observed in AD. These biomarkers offer potential non-invasive diagnostic alternatives, especially in at-risk populations such as individuals with DS[115–117]. In a recent study investigating the $A\beta$ peptides signature associated with CAA

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in *post-mortem* brain samples[46], we observed that in the insoluble fraction derived from the cortex and hippocampus of patients, N-terminally truncated peptides terminating at positions 37, 38, 39, and 40 exhibited the strongest positive correlations with CAA. Conversely, peptides ending at amino acids 42 and 43, along with their pyroglutamylated forms, were found to exhibit significant negative correlations with CAA severity. A recent study involving patients with sporadic and hereditary CAA indicated that the level of Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein (GFAP) in the CSF might serve as an early marker for CAA[118]. However, another study found similar GFAP levels between patient with sporadic CAA and controls subjects[117] indicating that additional investigation is needed to establish GFAP as reliable biomarker for CAA.

Another direction to find plasma biomarkers was tested in a recent study using machine learning algorithms to develop and assess the performance of plasma biomarker identified using proteomic analyses[119]. A panel of 146 individuals with probable CAA and 128 controls were prospectively enrolled and a total of 166 differentially expressed proteins were identified in patients with CAA. Six hub proteins were selected to construct a circulating panel, which demonstrated strong performance in distinguishing patients from controls across all cohorts: Pro-CTSH, the inactive precursor of cathepsin H, emerged as the most influential across three independent cohorts; USP15, a deubiquitinating enzyme implicated in the regulation of type I interferon signaling and neuroinflammation; ApoA-IV plays a key role in lipoprotein metabolism and plasma lipid transport; PREP, serine peptidase that hydrolyzes proline-containing peptides; Fibulin-5, an extracellular matrix protein essential for elastic fiber assembly and cell adhesion; and RNase 4, a member of the RNase A superfamily, with undefined biological role. Although no direct protein-protein interactions have been identified among these candidates, they are suggested to converge on shared pathogenic pathways including A β production and clearance, vascular remodeling, neuroinflammation, and oxidative stress, all central to CAA pathophysiology. Furthermore, the risk stratification system based on the hub protein panel effectively identified individuals at high risk for new-onset lobar ICH. Altogether, the study uncovered distinct circulating protein profiles associated with CAA and developed a validated hub protein panel to support CAA screening and risk stratification. The integration of these tools should improve early detection, risk stratification, and potential therapeutic monitoring of CAA[120].

Introduction

V. The Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB): Structure and Function

The blood brain barrier (BBB) is a microscopic fortress that not only protects neural circuits but also functions as a selective filter, regulating communication and exchange between the brain and the rest of the body via the bloodstream.[121,122]. It is not a uniform structure, but rather a dynamic and highly specialized interface formed by the coordinated interplay of multiple cell types across distinct vascular segments. In the brain, arteries, arterioles, capillaries, venules, and veins each possess unique structural and cellular features that influence their contribution to BBB function and cerebral homeostasis[123] (Fig.1-7).

At the core of the BBB lies a monolayer of endothelial cells lining the inner surface of all cerebral blood vessels, serving as the primary barrier and selective filter between the bloodstream and the brain[121]. In capillaries, which represent the main functional site of the BBB, these endothelial cells are interconnected by complex tight and adherens junctions that restrict paracellular diffusion and tightly regulate selective permeability[124] (Fig1-8). Tight junction proteins such as claudins, occludin, and junctional adhesion molecules (JAMs) interact with a cytoplasmic plaque of scaffolding proteins, including the Zonula occludens (ZO) proteins, to anchor the junctions firmly to the actin cytoskeleton, ensuring structural integrity and selective permeability. Adherens junctions, primarily mediated by vascular endothelial (VE)-cadherin and CD31, provide mechanical stability and facilitate intracellular signaling that maintains barrier homeostasis. Surrounding the endothelium, pericytes are embedded within the basement membrane and are particularly abundant in capillaries, precapillary arterioles, and post-capillary venules. They play critical roles in maintaining endothelial stability, modulating vessel diameter, and preserving BBB integrity[123]. Enveloping the vessel wall, astrocytic end-feet provide essential metabolic support and influence barrier properties through dynamic signaling interactions with endothelial cells and interactions[125] (Fig.1-7).

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Figure1-7: See next page for legend

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Figure1-7: A: Structure of brain vasculature and mural cell distribution. Pial arterioles branch from surface arteries and penetrate the brain parenchyma, transitioning into capillaries and eventually venules. Mural cells include vascular smooth muscle cells (SMCs), found in larger vessels, and pericytes, found in capillaries and post-capillary venules. Pericytes vary by location and are classified into subtypes such as ensheathing, transitional, capillary, and post-capillary pericytes. Adapted from Uemura et al.(2020)[123] **B:** Structural organization and cellular composition of arteries, capillaries, and veins.

In arteries and arterioles, the vessel wall is reinforced by multiple layers of vascular smooth muscle cells (SMCs), which play key roles in regulating cerebral blood flow and vascular tone[126]. Although SMCs are less directly involved in the restrictive properties of the BBB, they are essential for maintaining vessel integrity and responding to injury or pathological stimuli[127]. Fibroblasts located in the adventitia of larger vessels provide structural support and contribute to the composition of the extracellular matrix, thereby influencing vessel stability and repair processes[128]. The number of smooth muscle layers progressively decreases as arteries branch into smaller arterioles and eventually into capillaries, at which point astrocytic end-feet begin to ensheath the vessel walls (Fig.1-7B). Emerging evidence indicates that arteries and arterioles contribute to BBB function in a manner distinct from capillaries[129]. Unlike the classical endothelial barrier observed in capillaries, the arterial BBB permits certain substances to traverse both the endothelial and smooth muscle layers, while passage beyond the astrocyte end-feet remains restricted. This selective permeability is mediated by caveolae vesicles in endothelial and smooth muscle cells, which facilitate transcytosis[129]. Initially characterized in murine models, similar mechanisms seem to be present in the human brain, highlighting vascular heterogeneity as a promising frontier for uncovering novel BBB functions[130].

In contrast, veins and venules possess thinner vessel walls with fewer SMCs and pericytes, and their endothelial junctions are generally less restrictive, resulting in lower barrier properties compared to capillaries[123,131]. Despite this, these vascular segments play critical roles in fluid drainage and immune cell trafficking[132]. The presence of a perivascular space around venules is especially important for the clearance of interstitial solutes, including amyloid β , via CSF flow and the activity of perivascular macrophages (PVMs)[133,134]. This clearance function is particularly prominent in post-capillary venules, although PVMs are also found around arterioles[135].

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Figure 1-8: Tight and adherens junctions in brain endothelial cells. The figure illustrates key components of the blood-brain barrier, highlighting the organization of tight junctions and adherens junctions. Adapted from Kadry et al. (2020)[124].

Together, these diverse cell types (endothelial cells, pericytes, SMCs, fibroblasts, and astrocytes) constitute the neurovascular unit (NVU), whose coordinated interactions are crucial for the development, maintenance, and regulation of the BBB. Disruption to any component of this multicellular ensemble, or to the specialized architecture of arteries, capillaries, or veins, can compromise barrier function and contribute to the pathogenesis of neurological diseases. The NVU also serves as a crucial immunological interface, protecting the brain from injury and infection. Beyond structural support, the NVU incorporates a diverse set of immune-related cells, including PVMs, microglia, and other border-associated macrophages (BAMs), which play key roles in immune surveillance and response[136–138]. Microglia, the primary resident immune cells of the brain parenchyma, closely interact with endothelial cells, pericytes, and astrocytes, modulating neuroinflammation, and contributing to the maintenance or disruption of BBB integrity, particularly in pathological contexts such as Alzheimer's disease[139,140]. In the presence of A β , microglia become activated and can exacerbate BBB dysfunction[139] through the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species, while also attempting to clear A β deposits through phagocytosis[140]. BAMs, comprising meningeal macrophages, choroid plexus macrophages, and PVMs, reside along the CNS borders and are essential for immunological homeostasis at the brain's interfaces[137]. Finally, under

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pathological conditions, including A β accumulation, circulating monocytes can be recruited across the compromised BBB, where they differentiate into macrophages within the brain parenchyma or perivascular space. These infiltrating macrophages may contribute to A β clearance and tissue repair[141] but can also propagate neuroinflammation and further disrupt NVU function[142], potentially in ways distinct from resident immune populations.

To conclude, the BBB function is not static. It is modulated throughout development, adapts to physiological demands, and is particularly sensitive to pathological changes. Disruption of BBB integrity is increasingly recognized as both a marker and a driver of neurological diseases, including neuroinflammation, stroke, and neurodegeneration.

VI. Role of the blood brain barrier in CAA

The BBB is known to play a crucial role in the clearance of A β in AD, and emerging evidence suggests that BBB dysfunction may occur early in the disease, impairing A β clearance and promoting its accumulation[143]. This may create a vicious cycle contributing to both AD and CAA[144]. However, the precise relationship between BBB dysfunction and CAA remains poorly understood, particularly in DSAD, where ICH and microbleeds appear to be less frequent than expected when compared to *APP*dup, despite the common genetic factor of an additional *APP* copy[81]. Similarly, CAA in DS is below the expected level due to *APP* overexpression, further challenging our understanding of the role of the BBB in DSAD and CAA. It suggests that there may be protective mechanisms, potentially linked to genes or regulatory elements on chromosome 21, that influence A β deposition in the NVU. Our current knowledge is that under normal condition, A β is cleared through enzymatic degradation, perivascular drainage, and transport across the BBB via low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 1 (LRP1)[145,146].

Research on CAA and the BBB dysfunction in DS still faces several limitations. *Post-mortem* studies provide valuable insights into vascular pathology but fail to capture dynamic changes in BBB integrity over time, limiting their applicability to disease progression. In addition, intense lipofuscin and rapid RNA degradation in *post-mortem* samples limit their use for immunofluorescence staining and RNAseq analysis respectively. *In vivo* imaging techniques, such as dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI and PET, offer real-time assessment of BBB permeability but often lack the resolution to detect subtle molecular alterations[147,148]. Nevertheless, intra-arterial injection, and the long acquisition time could be difficult to apply to individuals with DS. Additionally, CSF biomarker studies are constrained by the invasive

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nature of lumbar punctures, reducing their feasibility for large-scale studies[149], especially in individuals with DS. Blood biomarkers could represent a more feasible alternative to CSF biomarkers in DS.

VII BBB integrity in DS

To the best of our knowledge, the sole cross-sectional peer-reviewed study investigating BBB permeability in DS is the one conducted by Mann's team in 1992, in which they used lectin histochemistry to investigate brain microvessels in *post-mortem* samples. The study included control brains from individuals aged 20 (n=4), 40 (n=5), 60 (n=6), and 80 (n=5) years, as well as brains from patients with AD (n=23), and individuals with DS under 50 years of age (n=8) and over 50 years old (n=9)[104]. They found that in AD and in individuals with DS older than 50 years, the binding of lectins e-PHA, L-PHA, and PAA was elevated beyond what would be expected due to normal aging. Additionally, lectins UEA-1 and BSA-I_{B4} binding were increased in AD but not in DS. Individuals with DS under 50 years old showed no binding changes beyond those associated with normal aging. These specific increases observed in AD and DS may reflect disease-related alterations in the basement membrane (BM) and could suggest impaired BBB function or integrity. If so, it would suggest that young individuals with DS have no BBB integrity issues but develop them with aging probably due the deposition of A β . Furthermore, the lack of increase of UEA-1 and BSA-I_{B4} in DS compared to AD may indicate some relatively less integrity issues in DS compared to AD. Most of the current understanding of BBB integrity in DS is based on indirect evidence, including signs of vascular abnormalities and an increased vulnerability to neurodegenerative conditions such as CAA and AD. By assuming a direct link between CAA, ICH and BBB integrity, one could hypothesize that the observed lower incidence of ICH[42,114] and reduced CAA[46,106] burden in DS compared to individuals with *APPdup* could suggest that the BBB in DS may be relatively more resilient than in *APPdup* cases.

A recent cross-sectional proteomic analysis of CSF from individuals with DS revealed an increase in plasma proteins over a decade before estimated year of onset (EYO), suggesting potential BBB leakage[150]. Interestingly, lactadherin, known as the precursor of medin which co-aggregates with vascular A β [151] and a marker associated with CAA in the CSF[152], was found to be decreased more than 20 years before EYO[150]. This suggests that BBB leakage could potentially be a secondary effect of CAA.

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While some *post-mortem* analyses and *in vivo* imaging studies suggest BBB dysfunction in DS, there is a significant gap in research, particularly regarding in-depth mechanistic studies and longitudinal analyses in living individuals. More studies using advanced imaging techniques, CSF biomarker analysis, and *in vitro* BBB models derived from cells of individuals with DS are needed to fully characterize the extent and consequences of BBB alterations in DS.

VIII. iPSCs origin and use in research

The advent of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) has revolutionized biomedical research, enabling unprecedented access to patient-specific cell types otherwise inaccessible, such as various cerebral cell types, for disease modeling and therapeutic development. iPSCs were first described in 2006 by Shinya Yamanaka and colleagues, who demonstrated that the introduction of four transcription factors (OCT4, SOX2, KLF4, and c-MYC) could reprogram adult somatic cells into a pluripotent state, functionally similar to embryonic stem cells[153]. This discovery, awarded the Nobel Prize in 2012, provided a powerful alternative to the use of embryonic stem cells, bypassing associated ethical concerns and allowing the generation of pluripotent cells from virtually any individual, provided informed consent is obtained[154].

iPSCs possess the capacity for near unlimited self-renewal and can theoretically differentiate into all cell types of the three germ layers; ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm[155] (Fig.1-9). This pluripotency, combined with the ability to capture the unique genetic background of the donor, makes iPSCs an invaluable tool for modeling human development, studying disease mechanisms, and screening potential therapeutics in a patient-specific context[156]. The use of iPSCs has rapidly expanded across diverse fields of biomedical research. By reprogramming somatic cells from patients with genetic or sporadic diseases, researchers can generate disease-relevant cell types that recapitulate key pathological features *in vitro*. This approach enables the study of disease mechanisms in a controlled environment, the identification of disease-specific phenotypes, and the testing of pharmacological interventions[156].

iPSC-derived models have been particularly transformative for studying neurological and neurodegenerative diseases, where access to primary human brain tissue is limited. Neurons, astrocytes, microglia, and oligodendrocytes can all be generated from iPSCs, allowing for the investigation of cell-type-specific contributions to disease pathogenesis. Furthermore, iPSCs can be genetically engineered to introduce or correct mutations, facilitating the creation

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of isogenic control lines that differ only at the locus of interest acting as an essential feature for dissecting the effects of specific genetic variants[157,158].

Figure 1-9: Overview of the reprogramming of somatic blood cells into induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) and their differentiation into organ-specific cell types. iPSCs, derived from patient blood samples, can generate all three germ layers (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm) which give rise to various specialized cells, including neural, vascular, cardiac, hepatic, and pancreatic lineages. Abbreviations: iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cell; miRNA, microRNA. Reproduced from Adegunsoye et al. (2023)[156].

One of the significant advances in iPSC technology has been the development of protocols to generate brain microvascular endothelial cells (iPSC-bmECs), which can replicate BBB hallmarks such as tight junctions, nutrient transporters, active efflux pumps, and high transendothelial electrical resistance (TEER, $\sim 1,450 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)[159]. These iPSC-bmECs can be cultured alone or co-cultured with pericytes and astrocytes, also derived from iPSCs, to reconstitute the neurovascular unit *in vitro*. Such models faithfully recapitulate many features of the human BBB, including the formation of tight and adherens junctions, polarized transporter expression, and selective permeability[160]. Other protocol also exist for robust and rapid general ECs differentiation[161].

iPSC-derived BBB models offer several key advantages:

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- **Human Relevance:** They capture the genetic and epigenetic background of individual donors, enabling the study of patient-specific or disease-specific BBB properties.
- **Isogenic Controls:** Using gene editing, isogenic pairs can be created to isolate the effects of single mutations or copy number variations, such as *APP* microduplication.
- **Functional Assays:** These models allow for the assessment of barrier integrity, transporter activity, and responses to pathological stimuli or therapeutic agents in a controlled setting.
- **Mechanistic Insights:** By integrating transcriptomic, proteomic, and various other OMICS with functional analyses, iPSC-BBB models can elucidate molecular pathways underlying BBB dysfunction in neurological diseases.

IX New research tools for studying CAA and the BBB

Cellular models, such as those developed from iPSCs, offer valuable mechanistic insights. However, they might not completely mimic the intricate relationship between the various cell types within the NVU. Despite this limitation, they remain essential to the investigation of brain cell types that are typically inaccessible. Mono- and co-cultures of iPSC-derived cells can serve as *in vitro* BBB models. Besides evaluating the functionality of the BBB under specific conditions, through methods such as Transwell assays[162] or TEER measurements[163], these techniques can also play a crucial role investigating drug delivery mechanism to the brain.[164] The Transwell model serves as an *in vitro* method to study the permeability and transport of molecules through biological membranes. It typically comprises two compartments separated by a semi-permeable membrane that supports cell culture. TEER is a quantitative measure of the resistance to current flow across a cell monolayer, providing insights into tight junctions' integrity.

Developing organoids from individuals with DS derived cells can resolve some of the 2D culture limitations by integrating cell type interactions and 3D configuration. Cerebral organoids are now widely studied and protocols to generate specific brain regions have been developed[165] which can even recapitulate AD phenotype[166,167]. In addition, the recent development of vascular organoids[168] allowed the generation of cerebrovascular organoids that potentially recreate the interaction between specific brains regions and the NVU[169–174].

Mouse models have been developed to better reflect *in vivo* pathophysiology, for investigating the mechanisms of DS[175] but with several limitations. Human chromosome 21q

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genes are orthologous to segments from three mouse chromosomes, the 16th, 17th and 10th. Most mouse models have only a portion of the orthologous chromosome 21 duplicated genes, potentially not representing all complex genetic interactions. In addition, mice modelling DS do not produce A β plaques even with a humanized *APP* gene[176], unless the *APP* gene carries specific mutations present in familial form of AD [177,178]. Nevertheless, as every model has its own strengths and limitations, mouse models remain crucial in DS research due to their ability to mimic key genetic features, provide controlled environments for studying disease progression, and facilitate long-term, longitudinal studies. In the context of CAA, mouse models can be used to study BBB permeability and A β clearance[179–183]. While mice remain the most common model for DS research, a variety of animal models including rats[175], zebrafish[184] and primates[185], offer complementary insights into the genetic, developmental, and cognitive aspects of DS.

Model	Mutations/Design	CAA Onset	Key Features
APPDutch[186]	APP mutation Dutch (E693Q)	22-25 months	Severe CAA with hemorrhages
Tg-SwDI[187]	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), Dutch (E693Q), Iowa (D694N)	3 months	Early microvascular A β , dual pathology vascular/parenchymal
5xFAD[188]	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), Florida (I716V), London (V717I) and PSEN1 mutations M146L and L286V	3 months	Parenchymal plaques dominate
APP23[189,190]	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), London (V717I)	8-10 months	Microhemorrhages and vascular remodeling
APP/Ld[191]	APP mutation London (V717I)	15-24 months	Late-onset CAA with no hemorrhages

Table 1: Overview of commonly used mouse model of CAA, including associated mutations, CAA onset, and key features (Note: This is not an exhaustive list)

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) is now an established technique for investigating biological mechanisms at both the cellular and molecular levels. When combined with vessel enrichment protocols, it has enabled the creation of a detailed atlas of the human NVU[192–194]. While this approach has not yet been applied to individuals with DS, it has already been used in sAD to identify genes positively and negatively associated with CAA[195]. Moreover, advances in spatial transcriptomic technologies have allowed for even higher-resolution analyses, enabling researchers to assess how proximity to A β deposits affects the transcriptomes of different cell types[196]. These emerging techniques will be essential for

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investigating CAA in individuals with DS and for understanding its impact on the various cell types that make up the BBB.

X Current therapeutic strategies for CAA

Individuals with DS represent the largest population group with EOAD but they have been largely under-studied and were initially excluded from clinical trials. This exclusion can be attributed to various factors including enrollment challenges, broad exclusion criteria, regulation concerning informed consent for individuals with intellectual disabilities, and overly cautious institutional review boards[197]. In the last decades, the inclusion of individuals with DS in trials has greatly improved. The review of Alldred *et al.* (2021) [197] summed up many trials with DS persons to prevent or reduce cognitive impairment and decline[198]. Several trials are now focusing on AD in DS[199] such as the Amyloid Lowering for Alzheimer's in Down syndrome with Donanemab Investigation (ALADDIN NCT06911944) presented during AAIC in 2024, the A β ATE study (NCT05462106), a recent phase 1 clinical trial for a vaccine against A β , and the HERO study (NCT06673069), to evaluate the safety and tolerability of ION269, an antisense oligonucleotide designed to reduce the expression of the *APP* gene. In the A β ATE study, the vaccine effectively induced an immune response, promoting the production of A β antibodies without any adverse effect, which is promising for its potential therapeutic applications. Further optimization and trials will be necessary to fully explore the therapeutic potential to treat neurological disorders associated with A β [200].

There is currently no effective treatment for CAA in the general population, as well as in the context of DS. Current potential treatments are focused on targeting the formation and deposition of A β at various stages[201–203]. A study conducted by Head's team revealed that lecanemab, a monoclonal antibody targeting soluble A β protofibrils, binds to vascular A β in *post-mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS. This finding suggests that lecanemab may have potential therapeutic effect on both parenchymal and vascular A β deposits[204]. However, removing A β from already deteriorating vessels could lead to complication such as Amyloid Related Imaging Abnormalities-Hemorrhages (ARIA-H) and ARIA-Edema (ARIA-E)[149,205] and in some are cases being fatal[206].

Alternative stroke recovery therapies can be implemented, with participation in a physical exercise program, a safe and effective approach to regain pre-stroke levels of cardiorespiratory fitness and functional mobility[207]. Botulinum toxin (BoNT) may help visual rehabilitation for patients with cerebral damages due to cerebrovascular stroke in DS[208]. By temporarily

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inhibiting acetylcholine release at the neuromuscular junction, BoNT can reduce overactivity in extraocular muscles, thereby correcting strabismus and improving ocular alignment. This can enhance binocular vision, support visual relearning, and facilitate engagement with rehabilitation strategies that rely on intact visual processing. Additionally, by alleviating abnormal muscle tone or facial dystonia, BoNT can improve visual field utilization and facial symmetry, both of which are relevant in post-stroke recovery. Given that individuals with DS are predisposed to both cerebrovascular events and pre-existing visual impairments, BoNT could be a valuable therapy in neurorehabilitation strategies.

A recent study found a link between pulse pressure and dementia in DS[209]. Higher pulse pressure was found to be associated with increased white matter hyperintensity (WMH) volumes, particularly in the global, parietal, and occipital regions. However, no significant association was observed between pulse pressure and enlarged perivascular spaces, cerebral microbleeds, or infarcts. However, a larger volume of WMH is linked to increased neurodegeneration and dementia. Therefore, a potential preventive therapy could focus on reducing pulse pressure in individuals with elevated levels.

A novel therapeutic approach involves the transient opening of the BBB to improve drug delivery to the brain [210]. The BBB serves as a selective filter, protecting the brain from harmful substances while permitting essential nutrients to pass through. This selectivity, however, complicates the delivery of drugs intended to treat neurological disorders. In the review from 2023, Niazi discusses emerging non-invasive strategies to enhance drug delivery to the brain, such as focused ultrasound with microbubbles, transcranial magnetic stimulation, nanoparticles, and intranasal methods. These techniques aim to overcome the challenges posed by the BBB and improve the treatment of AD, Parkinson disease and DS.

XI Research gap and emerging topics

There is a clear gap in our understanding of BBB permeability and integrity in DS, both in the context of CAA and AD, but also in younger healthier individuals. While evidence suggests a potential link between CAA and BBB dysfunction with potential protective factors limiting this dysfunction in DS, the exact mechanisms remain elusive. Historically, this research gap may have stemmed from limited access to appropriate tools for mechanistic and *in vivo* investigations of the BBB. However, recent advancements in neuroimaging techniques, such as high-resolution MRI, and molecular approaches like single-cell RNA sequencing, have brought us closer to answering these critical questions.

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To bridge this gap, future research should leverage longitudinal, multimodal imaging combined with advanced CSF and blood-based biomarkers to monitor BBB alterations over time. The development of non-invasive BBB permeability assays, including blood-based markers of endothelial dysfunction and novel MRI contrast agents, holds promise for earlier detection of BBB impairment. Additionally, emerging models and techniques now enable the study of previously underexplored aspects, such as the distinct roles of endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells, pericytes, and perivascular macrophages, among others, in BBB regulation. Furthermore, key molecular pathways, including inflammation[211], oxidative stress[212], vascular remodeling[213], and amyloid clearance, warrant deeper investigation to understand their contributions to BBB dysfunction in DS. Addressing these research gaps will be essential for developing targeted therapeutic strategies aimed at preserving BBB integrity and mitigating cerebrovascular pathology in DS while potentially finding protective factors against CAA on chromosome 21.

VI Rational and hypothesis

Individuals with DS exhibit a heightened vulnerability to cerebrovascular pathologies across their lifespan, from early-life MMD to late-onset CAA and AD. The overlap between these conditions underscores a complex interplay of genetic, molecular, and vascular factors, many of which remain poorly understood. While significant progress has been made in understanding A β metabolism and deposition in DS, questions persist regarding the role of the BBB in CAA pathogenesis, particularly in DSAD, where ICH and microbleeds appears less frequent than expected, especially compared to *APP*dup (Fig.1-10). Emerging research suggests that additional genetic factors on chromosome 21 may confer a degree of protection, necessitating further investigation.

The development of advanced imaging modalities, biomarkers, and experimental models, ranging from transgenic mice to iPSC-derived vascular models, has provided unprecedented opportunities to study the mechanisms of CAA in DS and AD. However, despite these advances, major questions remain regarding the interplay between CAA and BBB integrity in the context of DS at the cellular and molecular levels. As highlighted previously, individuals with DS and those with *APP* microduplication both exhibit increased *APP* gene A β overproduction yet display notable differences in CAA severity and distribution[44,46,81]. This paradox suggests that factors beyond *APP* overexpression, potentially involving other genes located on chromosome 21, may contribute to the observed cerebrovascular phenotypes.

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Among the cellular components of the BBB, endothelial cells are uniquely positioned as both regulator of barrier integrity and potential source of A β . However, direct evidence for endothelial-intrinsic mechanisms underlying CAA in genetic forms of AD remains limited. In particular, the contribution of endothelial cells to local A β production, junctional integrity, and overall BBB permeability in DS and *APPdup* has not been systematically investigated.

Our initial hypothesis was that endothelial cells may play a major role in the formation of vascular A β deposits in the CAA and that their morphology and function could be altered in DS and *APPdup*.

To address this hypothesis, my PhD project aimed to:

- **Establish a robust *in vitro* model** of human brain endothelial cells by differentiating induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) from individuals with Down syndrome (DS), *APP* microduplication (*APPdup*), their respective isogenic controls, and independent controls.
- **Compare the secretion profiles of amyloid- β (A β) peptides** across all these iPSC-derived endothelial cells (iPSC-ECs) genotypes to assess the relevancy in a CAA context.
- **Characterize the molecular profiles** of the iPSC-ECs using bulk RNA sequencing, in order to identify genotype-specific pathways and gene networks that may explain the difference in CAA severity of observed between DS and *APPdup*.
- **Perform immunostaining for key junctional and adhesion proteins** to evaluate morphological changes and to validate, at the protein level, the transcriptomic alterations observed.
- **Develop and implement a functional Transwell assay** to assess how each genetic condition affects the permeability of iPSC-EC monolayers, relative to their isogenic controls.

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Figure 1-10: Comparative overview of CAA-related features across different conditions. The schematic summarizes key vascular pathologies in elderly control individuals (Ctrl), individuals with Down syndrome (DS), sporadic Alzheimer's disease (sAD), DS with Alzheimer's disease (DSAD), and APP microduplication (APPdup). **CAA frequency** progressively increases from Ctrl and DS to sAD, DSAD, and APPdup[43–46,214], with severity following a similar trend, from controls exhibiting milder CAA, to APPdup presenting severe CAA. **Frequencies of Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH)**[28,42,114,215] **and microbleeds**[42,47,214,215] parallel CAA patterns. **Blood–brain barrier (BBB) integrity** is poorly characterized, but available data suggest a general decline in sAD relative to controls, with substantial interindividual variability likely influenced by age, genetic background and other factors[143] and very limited information on DS individuals [150]. Adapted from Valay and Potier (2025)[81]

Abbreviations

A β : Amyloid β

AD: Alzheimer Disease

ADAD: Autosomal Dominant Alzheimer Disease

APP: Amyloid Precursor Protein

APPdup: *APP* microduplication

ARIA-E: Amyloid Related Imaging Abnormalities- Edema

ARIA-H: Amyloid Related Imaging Abnormalities-Hemorrhages

BACE: Beta-Site APP-Cleaving Enzyme

BM: Basal Membrane

BoNT: Botulinum toxin

CAA: Cerebral Amyloid Angiopathy

CLDN5: Claudin-5

CSF: Cerebrospinal fluid

CTF: C-Terminal Fragment

DS: Down Syndrome

DSAD: Down Syndrome with Alzheimer Disease

DYRK1A: Dual Specificity Tyrosine-Phosphorylation-Regulated Kinase 1A

EC: Endothelial Cell

EGM2: Endothelial Growth Medium

ERG: ETS-Related Genes

EYO: Estimated Year of Onset

GABPA: GA Binding Protein Transcription Factor Alpha Subunit

GFAP: Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein

HC: Healthy Control

hiPSC : human induced Pluripotent Stem Cell

ICH: Intracerebral Hemorrhage

iPSC: induced Pluripotent Stem Cell

iPSC-EC: Endothelial cell differentiated from hiPSCs

JAM: Junctional Adhesion Molecules

MMD: Moyamoya Disease

NVU: Neurovascular Unit

OCN: Occludin
POFUT2: Protein O-Fucosyltransferase 2
p-tau: Phosphorylated tau
PVM: Perivascular Macrophages
RUNX1: Runt-Related Transcription Factor 1
sEOAD: sporadic Early Onset Alzheimer Disease
sLOAD: sporadic Late Onset Alzheimer Disease
SMC: Smooth Muscle Cell
TEER: Transendothelial Electrical Resistance
VE-cadherin: Vascular Endothelial Cadherin
VEGF: Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor
WMH: White Matter Hyperintensity
ZO: Zonula Occludens

Material and Methods

Materials and Methods

Methods for the introduction review

We conducted a comprehensive search on PubMed for publications up to December 2024, using "Down Syndrome" as the primary keyword in combination with 12 additional keywords: "(brain) AND (vascular)", "(cerebral amyloid angiopathy)", "(cerebral endothelial cell)", "(cerebral smooth muscle cell)", "(perivascular macrophage)", "(pericyte)", "(blood-brain barrier)", "(blood-brain barrier permeability)", "(cerebral atherosclerosis)", "(cerebral arteriosclerosis)", "(microbleed)", and "(cerebral hemorrhage)". The number of records found for each keyword combination is detailed in the workflow (supplementary Fig.1) and supplementary Table 2. The selection of these keywords was the result of discussions among the authors to ensure all relevant research on CAA in Down syndrome was included. In total, 711 records were identified.

The screening process consisted of three steps. First, abstracts were reviewed to exclude irrelevant records that did not mention Down syndrome or vascular content (e.g., articles using "down" in the context of "downregulated" in other syndromes). The second step involved removing duplicate publications from overlapping keyword searches. Finally, in the third step, we excluded articles deemed irrelevant after full-text review or those for which full-text access was unavailable. After all screening processes, 24 cases reports, 86 research articles and 46 reviews were included for a total of 156 records.

It is important to note that due to the evolving nomenclature of Down syndrome, earlier articles using outdated terms (e.g., "mongoloid") may have been missed. Additionally, some articles that were not directly related to CAA or vascular issues (such as those on A β metabolism or general Down syndrome pathology) were also included. Relevant articles were identified through general reviews and PubMed research. Ongoing clinical trials mentioned in the review were identified from congresses attended by the authors.

To confirm the research gap on BBB permeability, AI tools ChatGPT, Consensus, and Perplexity were employed to identify all studies on the topic, ensuring no relevant research was overlooked. These tools were also used during the writing process to help rephrase and improve the clarity of the text.

The work was published as a peer-reviewed review article (Valay and Potier, 2025, *Alzheimers Dement.* [81], Supplementary Annex 2).

Materials and Methods

Cell lines

Human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC) lines carrying the amyloid precursor protein (*APP*) duplication were obtained from the Coriell Institute (GM24675, Finnish, hereafter *APPdup*, Fig.2-1A) and from the laboratory of Pr. Dean Nižetić (hereafter *APPdup2*, French, Fig.1-6C, #3 ROU037004). The *APPdup* hiPSCs from the Coriell institute were generated from fibroblast[216] while the *APPdup2* hiPSCs were generated from blood mononuclear cells[217]. hiPSC lines exhibiting trisomy 21 and their corresponding isogenic euploid controls (designated DS1 and DS1 isogenic, respectively) were obtained from the WiCell Research Institute (UWWC1-DS1 and UWWC1-DS2U) and were generated from fibroblasts[218]. Furthermore, an independent control hiPSC line (referred to as WTS60) was acquired from the Sanger Institute (HPSI0114i-zapk_3) and was generated from fibroblast[219].

Generation of APPdup isogenic hiPSCs

The *APPdup* isogenic control hiPSC line was created using CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing by the iPS facility (ICV-iPS) of the Paris Brain Institut, by Dr. Amal Kasri under the supervision of Stéphanie Bigou. A total of 10^6 iPSCs from the *APPdup* hiPSC clone were nucleofected (Lonza, 4D nucleofector System) with a ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex, which included 225pmol each of crRNA and tracrRNA-ATTO, along with 120pmol of Cas9 protein (IDT, Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 crRNA, Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 tracrRNA, ATTO 550, and Alt-R® S.p. HiFi Cas9 Nuclease 3NLS). The crRNA was designed using CRISPOR tool (<https://crispor.gi.ucsc.edu/crispor.py>) to target the sequence 5'-GCGGAATTGACAAGTTCCGA-3', situated immediately upstream of the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequence 5'-GGG-3' in exon 5 of *APP* gene.

Twenty-four hours after nucleofection, ATTO-positive cells were isolated using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) and plated at a low density (10–50 cells/cm²) on Laminin-521-coated plates supplemented with CloneR2 for clonal selection (StemCell, 77003 and 100-0691 respectively). After one-week, 192 individual iPSC clones were manually selected under a stereomicroscope and expanded in 96-well plates coated with Laminin-521. Upon reaching confluency, the clones were further expanded for cryopreservation and genomic DNA extraction.

Genomic DNA from each clone was analysed through PCR amplification followed by Sanger sequencing (primer Fwd = ACCAAAGTGTAACCCATGCT, primer Rev = GCAGACTCTGATGGGAGTGG). Sanger sequence files were then analysed using ICE

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CRISPR Analysis Tool (<https://ice.editco.bio/#/>). Three knockout (3KO) clones were identified. One clone, initially named CE2 but later referred to as *APPdup* isogenic, containing a 1 bp deletion at codon 180 in exon 5 220C on one of the three alleles, was selected for all subsequent analyses (Fig.2-1B).

The same protocol was applied to generate the *APPdup2* isogenic control line. Three knockout (3KO) clones were also identified. One clone, initially named CF1 but later referred to as *APPdup2* isogenic, containing a 1 bp insertion (G) at codon 180 in exon 5 220C on one of the three alleles, was selected for all subsequent analyses.

Differentiation of hiPSC into Endothelial Cells (iPSC-EC)

The differentiation of hiPSC clones into endothelial cells was carried out similarly as previously described[161] (Fig.2-1D), by Dr. Vincent Fontaine at ICAN. In summary, hiPSCs were dissociated with 0.5 mM EDTA and plated on hESC-grade Matrigel (Corning #354277) at a density of 37,000 to 47,000 cells per cm² (depending on the cell line) in mTeSR1 (STEMCELL Technologies, Catalog #85850) medium supplemented with 10 μM Y-27632 (Biotechne #1254). Upon reaching 90% confluency, the medium was replaced with a priming mesoderm medium. This medium consisted of N2B27, a 1:1 mixture of DMEM:F12 with Glutamax (Gibco #31331028) and Neurobasal media, supplemented with N2 and B27 (Life Technologies # 17502048 and #17504044), 6 μM CHIR99021 (Stemcell #72054), and 25 ng/mL BMP4 (R&D Systems # 314-BP). After three days, the priming medium was switched to EC Induction Medium, which comprised StemPro-34 SFM medium (Life Technologies #10639011) supplemented with 200 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ (PeproTech #100-20-50UG) and 2 μM forskolin (Sigma-Aldrich #50-165-7104). This induction medium was refreshed after one day. On the sixth day of differentiation, EC were dissociated using Accutase and separated via Magnetic-Activated Cell Sorting using CD144 (also called CDH5 or VE-cadherin) MicroBeads (Miltenyi Biotec # 130-097-857). The CD144-positive sorted cells were then replated on hESC-grade Matrigel-coated dishes at a density of 35,000 cells per cm² in StemPro-34 SFM supplemented with 100 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ for one day. On day seven, the medium was replaced with EGM2 medium (Lonza #CC-3162) supplemented with 50 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ (endothelial cell expansion medium). This expansion medium was replaced every other day. Confluent cells were cryopreserved at 1 million cells per vial in a freezing medium consisting of 50% EGM2, 40% FCS, and 10% DMSO before being used for assays. Quality controls, using VE-cadherin and CD31 immunostaining, were performed on hiPSC-derived endothelial cells at passage 3, and these cells maintained their endothelial phenotype at least up to passage 4.

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Endothelial Cells culture

For all experiments involving hiPSC-derived endothelial cells (iPSC-EC), the cells were cultured on 60 mm petri dishes (TPP™ #93060) coated with Matrigel. The culture medium used was EGM2, supplemented with an additional 50 µg/mL of VEGF₁₆₅. The medium was completely replaced every 2-3 days, and the cells were utilized for experiments once they reached at least 80% confluence.

MSD assay for Aβ measurements

Aβ peptides quantification was performed using the Meso Scale Discovery (MSD) electrochemiluminescence immunoassay platform with the Aβ Peptide Panel 1 (6E10) Kit (K15200E-2), following the manufacturer's instructions. Cell culture supernatants were collected, centrifuged to remove debris, and stored at -80 °C until analysis. MSD 96-well multi-spot plates pre-coated with capture antibodies against Aβ₃₈, Aβ₄₀ and Aβ₄₂ were blocked with MSD Blocker A, followed by incubation with standards and samples in duplicate for 2 hours at room temperature. After washing, SULFO-TAG-labeled detection antibodies were added and incubated for 1h. Plates were washed again, and MSD Read Buffer T was added immediately before reading on a MESO QuickPlex SQ 120 instrument. Electrochemiluminescence signals were quantified using MSD Discovery Workbench software, and analyte concentrations were calculated based on a standard curve. Data below the lower limit of detection were excluded, and statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism on the average between the sample duplicates.

Mass spectrometry of Aβ species

After 48 hours of culture, the EGM2 media was collected and centrifuged at 300 × g for 15 minutes at 4°C to remove cellular debris. The clarified supernatants were then pulled together by genotypes, stored at -80°C, and shipped to our collaborators in Gothenburg, Sweden, within Professor Henrik Zetterberg's research team, where analyses were conducted by Elena Camporesi and Gunnar Brinkmalm.

Briefly, Aβ peptides were enriched from ECs supernatants by immunoprecipitation using two monoclonal antibodies, 6E10 and 4G8, each covalently linked to magnetic beads. The antibodies target distinct epitopes within the Aβ sequence (residues 3–8 for 6E10 and residues 18–22 for 4G8) allowing broad capture of various Aβ isoforms. EC supernatants were incubated with the antibody-conjugated beads under gentle agitation to facilitate specific

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binding of A β species. Following incubation, beads were subjected to multiple wash steps to remove non-specifically bound proteins and other contaminants. The bound A β peptides were then eluted from the beads. The eluted peptides were analyzed by LC-MS without enzymatic digestion, preserving the native peptide forms. This approach enabled the detection of intact full-length and truncated A β species, providing a detailed profile of A β isoforms secreted by ECs.

RNAseq

RNA extraction and sequencing were conducted in three batches, with alignment and analysis performed uniformly across batches. Detailed information on each batch's samples is provided in Supplementary Table 3.

For the first two batches, frozen cell pellets were prepared and sent by Dr. Amal Kasri to our collaborator Dr. Martin Irmeler at Helmholtz Zentrum München, where RNA extraction and sequencing were performed. The resulting FASTQ files were then returned to us for alignment and downstream analysis. Total RNA was isolated using the RNeasy Mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), which included a Trizol treatment step. The quality of the RNA was evaluated using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer, and only RNA samples with a RIN greater than 7 were used for RNAseq. Sequencing was carried out at the Helmholtz Zentrum Munich core facility on an Illumina NovaSeq sequencer. Illumina library kits, specifically TruSeq Stranded mRNA or Stranded mRNA Prep, Ligation, were used along with a PE150 stranded protocol to generate paired-end data. This data was then processed through an RNA-seq pipeline that included quality control checks using FastQC and MultiQC, followed by read trimming with trim_galore version 0.6.6 and cutadapt version 3.4.

For the third batch, RNA extraction was performed by us, and library preparation and sequencing were carried out by the iGenSeq platform at ICM. Total RNA isolation was performed using the RNeasy Plus Mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), which included a DTT treatment. The mRNA library preparation followed the manufacturer's recommendations using the Illumina Stranded mRNA Prep, Ligation kit from Illumina. The pooled library preparations were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus platform at Paris Brain Institute, yielding 2 x 50 million 100-base reads per sample after demultiplexing.

Dragen

The initial bioinformatics analyses were conducted by the Data Analysis Core facility at ICM (RRID:SCR_026138). FastQC was used to assess the quality of the raw sequencing data. Poor-

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quality sequences were filtered out, and adapters were trimmed using fastp with default parameters. The Illumina DRAGEN bio-IT Platform (version 4.2.9, project PB25_LVA_RSQ) was employed to map the reads to the reference genome hg38 and to quantify the reads based on GENCODE version 47. Picard tools were utilized to evaluate library orientation, library composition, and coverage along transcripts. Normalized counts per million (CPM) were calculated using EdgeR (version 3.38.0)[220]. Supplementary Table 11 gives the level of expression for all sequenced samples.

Projection of Bulk RNA-seq Data onto a Single-Nuclei Reference Using Seurat

Bulk RNA-seq data were projected onto a vascular single-nuclei RNA-seq reference using Seurat (v4) in R (Supplementary Annex 1). Bulk and single-nuclei expression matrices were imported and subset to genes that were commonly mapped in both datasets, regardless of expression levels. Both datasets were converted into Seurat objects, normalized, and scaled. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) were performed on the single-nuclei data using the top 15 principal components (number explaining more than 80% of the variance). Anchors between the datasets were identified with FindTransferAnchors(), and bulk samples were mapped onto the UMAP space using MapQuery(). Cell subtype annotations from the single-nuclei reference were used for visualization, and bulk samples were overlaid using ggplot2 to assess transcriptional similarity and alignment within the vascular cell landscape.

Differential expression analysis - Quby

Downstream analyses and data visualizations were performed using Quby, an R Shiny software developed by the Data Analysis Core of the Paris Brain Institute (<https://dac.institutducleveau.org/>). The raw data were filtered using a CPM threshold greater than 1 in at least half of the samples. Differential expression analysis was carried out using the GLM framework likelihood ratio test from DESeq2 (version 1.34) with the design formula \sim Batch + SampleGroup for the DS1 and isogenic samples, and \sim Passage + SampleGroup for the APPdup and isogenic samples. The resulting p-values were adjusted using the Benjamini and Hochberg procedure to control the False Discovery Rate (FDR). Genes with an FDR less than 0.05 were considered significantly differentially expressed, either upregulated or downregulated.

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Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA)

Enrichment analysis was performed using clusterProfiler (version 3.14.3) with Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) utilizing the Gene Ontology database C5: GO gene sets (April 2025). To compile a comprehensive list of protein-coding genes on human chromosome 21, we queried the Ensembl genome database using the BioMart data mining tool (Ensembl Genes 114, Human genes, GRCh38.p14).

Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA)

The Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) was conducted using a custom R program within the RStudio environment, specifically utilizing R version 4.4.3 (released on 2025-02-28 ucrt) and RStudio 2024.12.1 Build 563. Gene expression count data (in CPM) samples were imported and batch-corrected using the ComBat function to remove batch effects. Negative values resulting from correction were set to zero. Genes expressed above 1 CPM in at least half of the samples were retained and log₂-transformed (log₂(CPM + 1)).

Samples and genes with excessive missing data were excluded using the goodSamplesGenes function. The top 3000 most variable genes were selected for further analysis. We selected the 3,000 genes with highest variance across samples for WGCNA to enhance computational efficiency and reduce noise from low-variance genes. A soft-thresholding power was determined using the pickSoftThreshold function to approximate scale-free topology, and a power of 15 was chosen for both DS1 and *APP*dup analysis.

Weighted gene co-expression networks were constructed using the WGCNA package. Adjacency and topological overlap matrices (TOM) were computed, followed by hierarchical clustering of genes based on TOM dissimilarity. Modules were identified using dynamic tree cutting with a minimum module size of 30 genes, then merged based on eigengene similarity at a cut height of 0.25.

Module eigengenes were correlated with clinical traits (Trisomy 21 and *APP*dup status). Module membership (MM) and gene significance (GS) measures were calculated to identify key genes within modules associated with traits. Module networks with an absolute module trait relationship superior to 0.5 and a MM GS correlation superior to 0.4 were exported for visualization in Cytoscape (V3.10.3) where gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) was performed on all modules. Representative networks reflecting result diversity were selected.

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Fold change values from differential gene expression analysis were used as border color coding for gene nodes, while edge weights were displayed inside gene names.

Permeability assay

Cells were washed once with sterile PBS, detached using 1 mL pre-warmed TrypLE Express (Thermo Fisher Scientific #12604013) at 37°C for 6 minutes, and collected in EGM 2 medium. Cell concentration was determined using a hemocytometer, centrifuged at $200 \times g$ for 5 minutes, and resuspended to 5×10^5 cells/mL. Cells (5×10^4 in 100 μ L) were seeded onto fibronectin-coated (5 μ g/cm², Merck F1141) Corning 6.5 mm Transwell inserts (Corning #3413) and cultured at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Medium was refreshed after 24 hours and then every 2–3 days. For permeability assays, 70 kDa FITC-Dextran in EGM2 (0.07 mg/mL, Sigma-Aldrich #FD250S) was applied to the apical side, with thrombin (10 U/mL, Sigma-Aldrich #T6884) only in positive controls Transwells. Samples from the well compartment were collected every 30 minutes over 2 hours, and fluorescence was measured using a SpectraMax® i3X microplate reader (Molecular Devices) with excitation and emission wavelengths set at 485 nm and 535 nm, respectively.

ImmunoCyto Chemistry (ICC)

Cells were seeded between 7.5 to 10×10^4 cells per well onto glass coverslips placed in 24-well plates (Costar 3527), pre-coated with fibronectin (Merck #F1141) at 5 μ g/cm² in PBS for 1 hour at room temperature (RT). Cells were cultured in EGM2 medium at 37 °C with 5% CO₂, with medium changes every 2–3 days. After 7 days, cells were rinsed with PBS and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA, Electron Microscopy Science #15714) diluted in PBS for 20 minutes at RT, followed by three PBS washes. Samples were stored at 4 °C in PBS until immunofluorescence staining.

For staining, cells were permeabilized for 20 minutes at RT with PBS containing 2% BSA and 0.05% saponin, then incubated with primary antibodies (Abcam antibodies VE-cadherin #ab33168, CD31 #ab24590, Occludin #ab242202, Claudin-5 #ab131259, KDR # ab2349, VWF #ab11713, Invitrogen antibody ZO1 #40-2200 and Biolegend antibody 6E10 #803001) for 1 hour at RT, followed by secondary antibodies for 1 hour, both diluted in PBS-BSA-saponin. Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI (1 μ g/mL) for 10 minutes at RT. Coverslips were mounted with Vectashield Antifade Mounting Medium (Vectashield #H-1700-10) and stored at 4 °C until imaging.

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All images were captured in a single session with identical settings. Z-stacks were acquired for each field of view to capture the full thickness of the endothelial monolayer, ensuring complete coverage of cellular signal throughout the apical–basal axis. For each image, a summed Z-projection (sum of slices) was generated in Fiji (ImageJ, version 1.54f) to integrate total signal intensity across the entire cell volume for quantification.

Each immunostaining batch consisted of parallel seeding, fixation, staining, and imaging performed under identical conditions to ensure reproducibility and allow accurate comparison across cell lines.

To estimate average cell size, the total surface area of the field of view (acquired using identical confocal parameters across all samples) was divided by the number of DAPI-positive nuclei in that image. For consistency across experiments, each value was normalized to the average cell area of the corresponding isogenic control within the same immunostaining batch.

Protein expression was quantified by measuring the mean fluorescence intensity on summed Z-projection of the entire area of acquisition (not limited to the membrane) to include both junctional and cytoplasmic pools of each protein. Expression values were then normalized both on a per-cell basis and to the corresponding isogenic control average within each staining batch to account for differences in cell size and inter-batch variability.

Statistical Analyses

All statistical analyses and figure generation were performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.2. Details regarding the specific statistical tests used and the number of replicates are provided in the corresponding figures legends.

Figure and writing

Figure layouts and illustrations were created using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.2. and BioRender. Assistance from AI tools ChatGPT, Consensus, and Perplexity were employed for support with writing by reformulating sections of this article for clarity, but also as search engine for bibliography.

All data and supplementary materials generated in this study have been deposited on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18259653) and can be accessed using the thesis title and author details.

Chapter 1

Chapter 1 : Characterization of endothelial cells differentiated from human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC-EC) as a model to study CAA

I Cell lines selection and differentiation

Human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC, derived from fibroblasts) lines used in this study included cells derived from an individual with mosaic Down syndrome (DS), obtained from the WiCell Institute. This line gave rise to both trisomic hiPSCs (DS1) and an isogenic euploid control line (DS1 isogenic)[218]. In addition, hiPSCs from a patient carrying a 763 134 bp microduplication around the *APP* locus[216] (*APPdup*, Fig.2-1A) were included, along with an unrelated control hiPSC line derived from a healthy 60-year-old individual with no known pathology[219] (Fig.2-1C). To create an isogenic control for the *APPdup* line, three independent clones were generated using CRISPR/Cas9 mediated genome editing, by Stéphanie Bigou et Dr. Amal Kasri. One clone, designated CE2, containing a 1 bp deletion at codon 180 in exon 5 220C on one of the three *APP* alleles (Fig. 2-1B), was selected for all subsequent experiments.

Differentiation of hiPSCs into endothelial cells (hiPSC-ECs) was carried out at ICAN by Dr. Vincent Fontaine using a stepwise protocol adapted from a Patsch *et al.* (2015)[161] (Fig.2-1D). During the first phase, cells were exposed to CHIR99021, a GSK3 β inhibitor that activates Wnt signaling, and BMP4, a morphogen that promotes mesoderm specification, to induce mesodermal commitment. In the second phase, cells were treated with VEGF₁₆₅, a key angiogenic factor that drives endothelial lineage specification, and forskolin, a cAMP activator that enhances endothelial differentiation efficiency, in endothelial growth medium (EGM2). To obtain a purified population of endothelial cells, magnetic-activated cell sorting (MACS) was performed using anti-CD144 (VE-cadherin) microbeads, selecting CD144-positive cells.

In summary, this study utilized five hiPSC lines: one carrying the *APP* microduplication (*APPdup*), one carrying Down syndrome (DS1), their respective isogenic controls (*APPdup* isogenic and DS1 isogenic), and one independent control from a healthy individual (WTS60).

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Figure 2-1: hiPSC-ECs lines selection and differentiation. *A*: Site of the microduplication carried by the APPdup patient. The microduplication includes the genes GABPA, ATP5J, JAM2 and APP. *B*: Location of the CRISPR/Cas9 mediated deletion introduced in one of the three APP copies of the APPdup hiPSCs to generate an isogenic hiPSC control line. *C*: Names of the five cell lines with associated pathologies, expected CAA, and number of active APP copies. *D*: Summary of the differentiation protocol based on a previously published method from Patsch et al. (2015)[161].

II hiPSC-ECs express key tight and adherens junctions proteins

Following differentiation, immunofluorescence staining was used to assess the expression of key endothelial markers. All hiPSC-ECs lines displayed robust expression of adherens and tight junction proteins, including VE-cadherin and ZO-1 (Fig.2-2A). Additional endothelial markers such as adherens junction protein CD31, tight junction protein Claudin-5 (CLDN5), and Occludin (OCLN), von Willebrand factor (VWF) and the VEGF receptor type 2 also known as Kinase insert Domain Receptor (KDR), were robustly expressed thus confirming endothelial identity and BBB-relevant protein expression.

For all downstream experiments, hiPSC-ECs were cultured in EGM2 medium supplemented with 50 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ to preserve their endothelial phenotype. Although VEGF is known to modulate endothelial cell morphology and barrier permeability[221,222], initial attempts to culture *APP*dup and its isogenic control hiPSC-ECs without VEGF₁₆₅ supplementation resulted in rapid dedifferentiation and substantial cell loss within a few days (Fig.2-2B). These initial optimization experiments were conducted using the *APP*dup line and its isogenic control. Due to the pronounced negative effects observed, we did not repeat the VEGF₁₆₅ withdrawal in the subsequently generated DS1 and its isogenic iPSC-ECs. Thus, VEGF₁₆₅ supplementation was deemed essential to maintain both cell identity and viability throughout the study. Importantly, all experimental conditions were treated with the same concentration of VEGF₁₆₅, ensuring consistency and comparability across groups. Notably, no VEGF₁₆₅ was added during the permeability assays (only on the day of the assay), in an effort to limit its effect on hiPSC-ECs permeability properties.

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Figure 2-2: Validation of the iPSC-ECs by immunostaining. *A:* The iPSC-ECs express tight junction ZO1 and adherens junction VE-cadherin. *B:* If not supplemented with additional VEGF₁₆₅, the ECs appear more cobblestone shaped but lose their identity and die.

III hiPSC-ECs exhibit gene expression profiles similar to those of brain ECs

To further confirm the endothelial identity of our hiPSC-derived endothelial cells and to perform molecular analysis detailed in a later chapter, bulk RNA sequencing was performed on all hiPSC-ECs lines. We compared the transcriptomic profile of our hiPSC-ECs with a dataset of single-nuclei RNA sequencing (snRNA-seq) published in *Nature Neuroscience* in 2023[194]. This snRNA-seq provided comprehensive transcriptional profiles of human brain vascular cells from various brain regions and includes cell-type-specific gene signatures for arterial, venous, and capillary endothelial cells, as well as pericytes, smooth muscle cells, and fibroblasts.

The comparison revealed that over 95% of endothelial identity genes were shared between our hiPSC-ECs and the human brain endothelial profiles, demonstrating strong transcriptional similarity (Fig.2-3A). Comparatively, the expression overlap with non-endothelial vascular cell types was markedly lower. Among the vascular endothelial subtypes, hiPSC-ECs showed slightly greater transcriptional similarity to arterial ECs signatures than to capillary and venous ECs but still expressed genes specific to each of the three subtypes gene list.

In an effort to not only take into account which genes were commonly expressed but also their individual expression levels, we projected our bulk RNA-seq data onto the published snRNA-seq reference using the Seurat package's integration workflow (Supplementary Annex 1). To do so, bulk RNA-seq expression data were imported from a CSV file containing genes expression matrix (normalized counts in cpm), and snRNA-seq data from human vascular brain cells were loaded as a Seurat object with accompanying cell-level metadata from the publicly accessible data. Bulk and single-nuclei expression matrices were imported and subset to genes that were commonly mapped in both datasets, regardless of expression levels. Both the bulk and snRNA-seq datasets were converted into Seurat objects. Normalization was performed using the `NormalizeData()` function. Variable features were identified using `FindVariableFeatures()`, followed by scaling with `ScaleData()`. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed on the single-nuclei reference using 50 components. The proportion of variance explained by each component was used to guide dimensionality reduction. Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) was computed using the first fifteen principal components (`RunUMAP(dims = 1:15)`). The number of dimensions was determined by the minimum number explaining more than 80% of the cumulative variance (Fig. 2-3B). To project the bulk RNA-seq samples onto the single-nuclei reference UMAP space, anchor-based

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integration was performed using `FindTransferAnchors()` with the single-nuclei dataset as reference and the bulk data as query. The resulting anchors were used in `MapQuery()` to generate UMAP coordinates for the bulk samples using the reference UMAP model. UMAP projections of the reference single- clusters were visualized with cell subtype annotations using `DimPlot()`. The projected bulk samples were overlaid on the same UMAP space. Overlay plots were customized using `ggplot2` to assign colors to cell types and the query samples. Our analysis showed that all hiPSC-ECs samples mapped predominantly onto the arterial endothelial cluster (Fig.2-3C). This approach allowed a high-resolution comparison and validation of the endothelial identity of our hiPSC-ECs. Over the hiPSC-ECs generated have a transcriptomic profile closer to endothelial cells compared to any other vascular celltype and seem to be slightly more similar to arterial ECs than capillaries and venous ECs.

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Figure 2-3: hiPSC-EC exhibit gene expression profiles similar to those of brain ECs. A: Table showing the number of expressed genes shared between hiPSC-ECs and transcriptomic signatures of various human brain vascular cell types, as defined by snRNA-seq from Sun et al. (2023)[194] showing more than 95% similarities between brain endothelial cells and hiPSC-ECs gene expression. Values in parentheses indicate the total number of genes in each reference signature (column headers) and the number of shared genes (table entries). **B:** Cumulative variance explained by principal components in single-nuclei RNA-seq data. The 0.8 threshold is crossed at PC15. **C:** UMAP projection of bulk hiPSC-EC RNA-seq data onto a reference single-nuclei vascular cell atlas using Seurat. hiPSC-EC samples are shown in red and superpose with brain endothelial cells.

III A β secretion is significantly but differently altered in DS and APPdup

Having validated that our hiPSC-ECs exhibit key BBB protein and similar transcriptomic signature to brain endothelial cells, we next examined their functional capacity to contribute to CAA pathology. One hallmark feature of CAA is the accumulation of A β peptides along the walls of cerebral blood vessels, a process in which endothelial cells may play an active role, either by producing, transporting, or clearing A β . To explore this, we analyzed the A β production profile of our hiPSC-ECs. Understanding which A β isoforms are produced, and in what relative proportions, can shed light on whether brain-like endothelial cells derived from hiPSCs possess intrinsic amyloidogenic activity and potentially contribute to vascular amyloid deposition. This step is critical for assessing the relevance of this *in vitro* model for studying endothelial contributions to CAA pathogenesis.

Figure 2-4: *A: Relative higher A β ₄₀ levels compared to the respective isogenic control in DS1 (left) and APPdup (right). B: Relative higher A β ₄₂ levels compared to the respective isogenic control in DS1 (left) and APPdup (right). C: A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio measured by MSD assay for each peptide alighting and significant increase in DS1 compared to DS1 isogenic whereas there is a more modest tendency to its decrease in APPdup compared to APPdup isogenic. Unpaired *t*-tests were performed between each condition and its respective isogenic control for all the sections. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.*

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We first measured A β peptide secretion from EC culture supernatants using MSD assays targeting A β ₃₈, A β ₄₀, and A β ₄₂. To account for potential technical variability (e.g., culture timing, cell number, surface area), all values were normalized to the average of the respective isogenic controls processed in parallel, after which batch replicates were pooled. Normalization was not applied to the A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio, as it is inherently self-normalizing. A β ₃₈ was undetectable across all lines, suggesting either absence or levels below the assay's detection threshold (most likely the latter). In contrast, both A β ₄₀ (Fig. 2–4A) and A β ₄₂ (Fig. 2–4B) were consistently detected and secreted in higher amounts by DS1 and *APPdup* ECs compared to their respective controls. DS1 cells secreted approximately 1.9-fold more A β ₄₀ and 2.5-fold more A β ₄₂, while *APPdup* cells showed a 1.5-fold and 1.25-fold increase, respectively. The A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio (Fig. 2–4C) confirmed that ECs predominantly secrete A β ₄₀, with levels 10–14 times higher than A β ₄₂. While the ratio was slightly decreased in *APPdup* ECs, it was significantly elevated in DS1 cells, indicating altered processing or secretion dynamics in this line.

To further assess the spectrum of A β species secreted by ECs, we analyzed ECs supernatant by mass spectrometry (Fig.2-5A). A β peptides were first enriched using immunoprecipitation with monoclonal antibodies 6E10 and 4G8, which were covalently coupled to magnetic beads. These antibodies target distinct regions of the A β peptide (residues 3–8 for 6E10 and 18–22 for 4G8), enabling broad capture of A β isoforms. The supernatant was incubated with the antibody-conjugated beads, allowing A β species to bind specifically. After extensive washing to remove non-specifically bound material, the captured A β peptides were eluted and subjected to liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC/MS) analysis without enzymatic digestion. This no-digestion approach preserves the intact peptide structure, allowing the detection of full-length and truncated A β . A total of 16 distinct A β peptides were identified, originating from cleavage sites at positions 1, 5, and 17, and terminating at various downstream positions (Fig.2-5B). The most abundant peptides detected were A β ₁₋₁₉ and A β ₁₋₁₅. Notably, DS1 cells exhibited a unique peptide signature characterized by a high abundance of A β ₁₋₁₇, distinct from all other samples. Furthermore, only DS1 and *APPdup* cells secreted detectable amounts of the longer peptides A β ₄₀ and A β ₃₄. The DS1 isogenic control also showed a distinct profile, with several peptides absent compared to other conditions. Overall, the total A β peptide content was highest in DS1 and *APPdup* cells relative to their respective controls, consistent with the quantitative measurements obtained via MSD assay (Fig.2-5C).

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Figure 2-5: A β species identification by mass spectrometry. **A:** A β peptides were immunoprecipitated using 6E10- and 4G8-conjugated magnetic beads and analyzed by LC/MS. **B:** Different A β peptides detected in hiPSC-EC supernatants by mass spectrometry. Both bar height and color scale indicate signal intensity for each peptide. **C:** Total abundance (sum) of all A β peptides identified in G confirming the MSD results. Numbers above bars indicate the number of distinct A β peptides detected per group.

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IV Conclusion

In this chapter, we systematically established and validated a relevant *in vitro* cellular model to investigate endothelial contributions to CAA. We employed a panel of five hiPSC lines, including lines carrying Down syndrome (DS1) and an *APP* microduplication (*APPdup*), along with their respective isogenic controls and a healthy donor line. These hiPSCs were successfully differentiated into endothelial cells using a stepwise protocol, yielding cells with robust expression of key BBB and endothelial markers.

Comprehensive molecular validation confirmed the endothelial identity of derived cells. Specifically, immunostaining demonstrated the presence of tight and adherens junction proteins essential for BBB function, while transcriptomic comparisons with published human brain vascular single-nuclei datasets revealed strong molecular similarity to brain endothelial cells compared to other vasculature cell-type. Functional analyses further established the model's relevance by showing increased production and secretion of A β peptides, especially A β ₄₀ and A β ₄₂, in DS1 and *APPdup* endothelial cells compared to isogenic controls. Mass spectrometry profiling confirmed the secretion of diverse A β isoforms in disease-associated lines, including longer and truncated species associated with amyloid pathology but also revealed distinct A β isoforms secretion signature in each of the different lines.

Altogether, Chapter 1 demonstrates the successful generation of a highly characterized hiPSC-EC model suited for exploring the vascular mechanisms contributing to CAA. This foundational work ensures that the model possesses both molecular fidelity to brain endothelial cells and functional relevance to amyloid-related processes, thereby laying the groundwork for further molecular and mechanistic studies in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 2

Chapter 2 : Biological pathways altered in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-EC

Transcriptomic technologies have significantly expanded our ability to interrogate cellular identity and function at a genome-wide scale, enabling detailed characterization of gene expression changes in both physiological and disease contexts. In this chapter, we apply a multi-layered transcriptomic framework to investigate gene expression alterations in our hiPSC-derived endothelial cell models. Three complementary analytical strategies were employed:

- **Differential Gene Expression (DGE) Analysis:** This quantitative comparison of gene expression levels between experimental groups enable to identify individual genes with statistically significant changes in expression, providing a foundation for molecular interpretation of disease-associated phenotypes[223].
- **Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA):** Moving beyond single-gene changes, GSEA assesses whether predefined gene sets, representing biological pathways or functional categories, are overrepresented among differentially expressed genes, providing a pathway-level view of molecular perturbations[224].
- **Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA):** It is a systems-level approach that identifies modules of genes with highly correlated expression patterns across samples. Unlike DGE, which focuses on changes in individual genes, and GSEA, which tests predefined gene groups for enrichment, WGCNA is entirely data-driven and reveals emergent patterns of co-regulation without relying on prior knowledge. This allows for the discovery of possible novel gene networks associated with experimental traits and the identification of potential central “hub” genes within these networks[225].

By integrating these distinct analytical approaches, we aim to capture both targeted and global aspects of transcriptional regulation within our models. While each method has its limitations, such as sensitivity to noise in DGE or the dependency of GSEA and WGCNA on curated gene sets or correlation structure, their combined use provides a more robust and interpretable picture of transcriptomic alterations relevant to ECs function and their link to *APP* or chromosome 21 duplication.

I Gene expression changes in hiPSC-ECs from individual with DS and patient carrying *APPdup*

To explore the transcriptomic landscape of our hiPSC-EC models, we began by examining global expression variation using principal component analysis (PCA), which revealed clear segregation between both DS1 and *APPdup* samples and their respective isogenic controls (Fig. 3-1), indicating consistent and condition-specific transcriptional profiles. For the DS1 and DS1 isogenic lines, two independent differentiations were performed and sequenced across two separate batches; batch was therefore included as a covariate to account for variability introduced by this experimental design. This batch covariate coincidentally happens to also match the differentiation and passage number, as such by correcting the batch effect we also correct for the passage and differentiation effect (Supplementary Table 3). For the *APPdup* and *APPdup* isogenic lines, three and two independent differentiations, respectively, were used, but all samples were sequenced in a single batch and only *APPdup* samples were sequenced for the first differentiation, not allowing for a proper differentiation correction. In this case, cell passage numbers were included as a covariate to control for technical variation.

Differential gene expression analysis reveals more drastic dysregulation in DS

Differential gene expression (DGE) analysis was performed using DESeq2, following pre-filtering to exclude genes with low expression (defined as <1 cpm in at least half the samples of one of the compared groups). No additional fold change threshold was applied in order to retain a comprehensive gene set for downstream enrichment and network-level analyses (GSEA). In DS1 ECs, we identified 6,566 differentially expressed genes (DEGs; adjusted $p < 0.05$), including 3,175 upregulated and 3,391 downregulated genes (Fig. 3-2A). MA and volcano plots visualized the scale and statistical significance of gene expression changes, without revealing any signs of technical artifacts or global biases (Fig. 3-2B, C). A heatmap of the DEGs further demonstrated consistent and robust segregation between DS1 and isogenic control samples (Fig. 3-2D).

In *APPdup* ECs, we identified 2,952 DEGs (adjusted $p < 0.05$), comprising 1,569 upregulated and 1,383 downregulated genes (Fig. 3-3A). Although the extent of transcriptomic dysregulation was less pronounced than in DS1, the MA and volcano plots again showed well-distributed changes (Fig. 3-3B, C). Hierarchical clustering of the DEGs confirmed clear separation between *APPdup* and isogenic controls (Fig. 3-3D).

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Figure 3-1: Principal component analysis of DS1, APPdup and their respective controls. A: PCA of DS1 and its isogenic control, corrected for batch effects, reveals clear segregation by genotype and differentiation. **B:** PCA of APPdup and its isogenic control, corrected for passage number, reveals segregation by genotype and differentiation.

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Figure 3-2: Results of the DGE performed on DS1 vs DS1 isogenic with a batch covariate. A: Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the DS1 hiPSC-ECs. **B:** Volcano plot showing massive dysregulations. **C:** MA plot showing no abnormal global trends. **D:** Heatmap associated with DS1 DGE analysis.

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Figure 3-3: Results of the DGE performed on *APPdup* vs *APPdup* isogenic with a passage covariate. **A: Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs. **B:** Volcano plot showing more modest dysregulations compared to DSI. **C:** MA plot showing no abnormal global trends. **D:** Heatmap associated with *APPdup* DGE analysis.**

Chapter 2

Identification of chromosome 21 genes involved in hiPSC-ECs phenotypes in DS and *APPdup*

To further investigate the transcriptional impact of trisomy 21 and *APP* microduplication, we specifically examined protein encoding genes mapping to human chromosome 21 (Chr21). We extracted the fold change (FC) values for all dysregulated Chr21 genes and analyzed their distribution (Fig.3-4A) in DS and *APPdup* ECs. In DS, the distribution displayed a prominent peak around a 1.5-fold change, consistent with the expected gene dosage effect of trisomy 21. In contrast, *APPdup* cells showed only a modest symmetrical peak around -1.5 and 1.5 FC, reflecting the duplication of the *APP* locus only. We then assessed the overlap between the Chr21 genes and the DEGs in DS and *APPdup* (Fig.3-4B). In DS, of the 122 Chr21 genes expressed, 80 were upregulated and 10 were downregulated compared to isogenic control. In *APPdup*, among the 119 expressed Chr21 genes, 13 were upregulated and 10 were downregulated.

To characterize more thoroughly the shared dysregulation pattern, we performed an intersection analysis of Chr21 DEGs between DS and *APPdup* (Fig.3-4C). Of the 13 upregulated Chr21 genes in *APPdup*, 9 were also upregulated in DS, including key genes such as *APP*, *DYRK1A* (a kinase implicated in Down syndrome and neurovascular dysfunction[226]), *GABPA* (a transcription factor that regulates mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative metabolism[227]), and *ERG* (an ETS-family transcription factor controlling the expression of key genes involved in vascular development, barrier integrity, and anti-inflammatory responses[228–231]), all of which could be implicated in endothelial function and vascular biology. Interestingly, among the 10 downregulated Chr21 genes in *APPdup*, 7 were found to be upregulated in DS, including *BACE2*, a gene involved in A β peptide processing[67,68]. As a side note, among the tight junction components, three claudin genes (*CLDN8*, *CLDN14*, and *CLDN17*) are located on Chr21, and one might expect these genes to be upregulated in ECs derived from individuals with DS and alter ECs functions. However, none of these claudins were found to be expressed in accordance with the literature. *CLDN8* is mainly found in epithelia of kidney, colon, and other absorptive tissues[232], *CLDN14* is strongly linked to the inner ear (mutations cause hereditary deafness)[233], and *CLDN17* is described as an anion-selective claudin expressed in kidney and liver epithelia[234].

Altogether, these results suggest both shared and distinct mechanisms involving Chr21 genes in DS and *APPdup* ECs, with potential implication for their respective cellular phenotypes and general function.

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Figure 3-4: Chromosome 21 Gene expression changes in hiPSC-ECs from individual with DS and patient carrying APPdup. **A:** Histogram showing the number of differentially expressed genes (y-axis) on chromosome 21 across fold change intervals (x-axis, bin width = 0.5) from the differential gene expression analysis on DS1 and APPdup and their respective isogenic controls and confirming the trisomy in DS1 with a high spike at FC 1.5. **B:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes expressed in DS1 (up) and APPdup (down) and the differentially expressed genes from their respective DGE analysis. **C:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes dysregulated in DS1 and APPdup respective DGE analysis showing similarities but also distinct expressions changes. The list of the 64 Chr21 genes upregulated in DS1 only can be found in Supplementary Table 4.

II Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) reveals distinct pathway alteration in DS and *APP*dup hiPSC-ECs

To gain further insight into the biological pathways affected in DS and *APP*dup hiPSC-ECs, we performed Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) using the DEGs and Gene Ontology (GO) gene sets. In the DS condition, a total of 327 gene sets reached significance with a false discovery rate (FDR) below 0.05. The most prominent positively enriched pathways were related to apoptosis, immune response and inflammation, endosomal and lysosomal compartments, and in a lesser way, cellular metabolism with fucose metabolism. Conversely, negatively enriched pathways were predominantly associated with cell cycle regulation and chromosome organization, suggesting impaired proliferative capacity and altered cellular architecture (Supplementary Table 5).

In contrast, in *APP*dup hiPSC-ECs no gene sets met FDR < 0.05 threshold. However, when considering gene sets with an FDR below 0.1 to explore potential trends, we observed negatively enriched pathways related to ribosomal function and translation, immune system regulation, and protein processing (Supplementary Table 6). Interestingly, in both DS and *APP*dup ECs, the gene set "GOBP_protein_targeting_to_membrane" displayed a notable downregulation (Fig.3-5A and B). Although this gene set did not meet the FDR significance threshold, the low nominal p-values suggest a biological trend worth considering, particularly given its potential relevance to the brain ECs tight and adherens junction proteins location at the plasma membrane. Additionally, in DS, the "GOBP_maintenance_of_blood_brain_barrier" gene set showed upregulation of numerous tight and adherens junction-related genes (Fig.3-5C, Table 2). While this enrichment did not reach FDR significance, the individual upregulation of the genes in that geneset may be sufficient to impact endothelial barrier properties. This pattern was not observed in *APP*dup cells (Fig.3-5D), suggesting that distinct mechanisms may underlie endothelial dysfunction in DS and *APP*dup.

Collectively, these results suggest widespread transcriptional alterations in DS ECs, with specific enrichment of pathways related to blood barrier integrity, inflammation, and cellular metabolism, while *APP*dup ECs showed more subtle tendencies.

In a recent study published in *The Journal of Neuroscience*[195], the authors performed snRNA-seq on endothelial cells isolated from various human brain regions, including samples with sporadic CAA (determined from histological assessment on the 32 human brain from donor diagnosed with sAD). Their analysis revealed 684 genes associated with CAA,

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comprising 350 genes negatively correlated, and 334 genes positively correlated with the presence of CAA.

To investigate potential changes of CAA-related ECs changes in DS and *APPdup*, we performed GSEA using the positively and negatively correlated CAA-associated gene sets alongside the list of endothelial genes from Fig.2-3A deduced from the other published snRNA-seq study[194]. We found that DEGs in DS were significantly enriched among genes negatively associated with CAA, while DEGs in *APPdup* were significantly enriched among genes positively associated with CAA (Table 3). Additionally, both the DS and *APPdup* DEGs showed significant enrichment within the broader set of endothelial genes, suggesting that both DS and *APPdup* alter the global ECs function.

Figure 3-5: Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) reveals distinct pathway alteration in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs. A, B: Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "protein targeting to the membrane." Showing global down regulation of genes in both DS1 (A) and *APPdup* (B). C, D: Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "Maintenance of blood-brain barrier" Showing global up regulation of genes in DS1 (C) but not in *APPdup* (D).

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Junction type	FeatureID	Line	FC	FDR	Status	average expression (cpm)
Adherens junctions	PECAM1 (CD31)	DS1	2.74	1.94E-18	Up in DS1	1558
		APPdup	-1.16	0.39	Not regulated	2239
	CDH5 (VE-cadherin)	DS1	1.75	1.10E-08	Up in DS1	971
		APPdup	-1.01	0.96	Not regulated	1007
Tight junctions	CLDN5 (Claudin 5)	DS1	2.35	7.52E-04	Up in DS1	481
		APPdup	1.23	0.62	Not regulated	453
	OCLN (Occludin)	DS1	1.90	8.31E-06	Up in DS1	13
		APPdup	-1.02	0.97	Not regulated	5.94
	TJP1 (ZO1)	DS1	1.09	0.61	Not regulated	103
		APPdup	1.31	3.19E-03	Up in APPdup	102
	TJP2 (ZO2)	DS1	1.80	1.28E-20	Up in DS1	83
		APPdup	1.01	0.97	Not regulated	90
	TJP3 (ZO3)	DS1	not expressed			
		APPdup	not expressed			
	F11R (JAM1)	DS1	1.84	2.40E-13	Up in DS1	142
		APPdup	1.01	0.96	Not regulated	126
	JAM2	DS1	1.45	0.45	Not regulated	1.67
		APPdup	-1.63	0.29	Not regulated	0.93
JAM3	DS1	2.12	1.20E-15	Up in DS1	239	
	APPdup	1.33	0.02	Up in APPdup	219	
ESAM	DS1	1.82	1.03E-07	Up in DS1	581	
	APPdup	1.07	0.58	Not regulated	650	

Table 2: Dysregulation status of keys endothelial tight and adherens junctions genes.

Description	setSize	Condition	setSize expressed	Enrichment Score	NES	pvalue	p.adjust	qvalues
Endothelial gene list	935	DS1	899	0.48	1.67	1.68E-4	8.38E-4	5.29E-4
		APPdup	908	0.39	1.41	5.98E-4	1.77E-3	1.12E-3
Positive correlation with CAA	334	DS1	308	0.26	0.83	0.92	0.92	0.58
		APPdup	310	0.49	1.67	7.09E-4	1.77E-3	1.12E-3
Negative correlation with CAA	350	DS1	326	0.48	1.55	1.27E-3	3.18E-3	2.01E-3
		APPdup	325	0.33	1.13	0.19	0.31	0.20

Table 3: GSEA results using a custom gene list: endothelial genes from Bryant et al. 2023[195] and genes positively or negatively correlated with CAA from Sun et al. 2023[194].

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III Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) identifies transcriptional modules similar to the GSEA

To complement the DGE analysis and its associated GSEA, which focuses on individual genes or predefined gene sets, we applied a Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) to gain a broader, systems-level understanding of transcriptional organization in DS and *APPdup*. While DGE and GSEA are effective for identifying gene-level changes and coordinated shifts in known pathways, they do not explicitly account for correlation structure across the transcriptome. In contrast, WGCNA identifies data-driven modules of co-expressed genes, which may reflect shared regulatory control or biological function. This allows us to assess whether entire co-expression networks, rather than isolated genes, are dysregulated in DS and *APPdup*. Moreover, enrichment analyses performed within each module can reveal coordinated functional changes, including those not captured by traditional pathway-based approaches.

Due to the limited combined number of samples in the DS and its isogenic control group ($n = 10$), the analysis was extended to include independent control samples. This brought the total number of samples to 15, aligning with the recommendation that WGCNA be performed on at least 15 samples to ensure reliable network construction and module detection. In contrast, the *APPdup* dataset included 15 samples consisting solely of *APPdup* and its isogenic control samples. Independent controls were not added to this group, as the subtler transcriptomic effects expected from a microduplication, as opposed to a full trisomy, might be obscured by inter-individual variation introduced by unrelated controls.

For both datasets, the analysis was performed on the top 3000 most variable genes, and the appropriate soft-thresholding power (β) was determined by evaluating scale-free topology fit indices. In each case, the network approximated a scale-free topology with an R^2 value above the standard 0.80 threshold when the power exceeded 15 (Fig.3-6). Network construction was then performed resulting in the construction of 31 modules for the DS dataset and 36 modules for the *APPdup* dataset (Fig.3-7A and C). Modules with eigengenes showing greater than 0.75 similarity (Pearson correlation) were subsequently merged, yielding 13 merged modules in the DS network and 15 in the *APPdup* network (Fig.3-7A and C, Supplementary Figures 2A, B and 3A, B). To focus on biologically meaningful modules, we applied thresholds based on both module-trait correlation (how strongly a module is related to an external trait, DS and *APPdup* in our case) and within-module gene significance (how closely a gene's importance for a trait matches how central it is within a module), helping highlight the most relevant genes for that

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trait. Only modules with an absolute module-trait correlation > 0.5 and a correlation between gene significance (GS) and module membership (MM) > 0.4 (with associated p-values < 0.05) were retained for further analysis (Fig.3-7B and D, Supplementary Figures 2 and 3). These modules were exported to Cytoscape for network visualization, and GSEA was performed on each of them to better understand what biological function could be associated with each modules.

Figure 3-6: The scale independence plot shows that a scale-free topology fit ($R^2 > 0.8$) is achieved at soft-thresholding power $\beta = 15$ in both the DS data set (A) and the APPdup dataset (B).

In DS, the grey60 module exhibited an exceptionally strong positive correlation with DS (0.96) and a high GS–MM correlation (0.87). This module was significantly enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery, cell adhesion, and blood vessel morphogenesis, with most genes within these sets being upregulated. (Fig.3-8A, Supplementary Table 7). Similarly, the white module, which was also positively correlated with DS, was enriched for gene sets associated with immune response. The salmon and darkorange modules, both positively correlated with DS, were enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery and cell surface, consistent with the biological functions identified in the grey60 module. Notably two geneset related to apoptosis where also significant, “extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway” in the grey60 module and “regulation of apoptotic process” in the salmon module, consistent with the positive link to apoptosis revealed in the previous GSEA. In contrast, the blue module, which was the only module negatively correlated with DS (-0.86), was enriched for gene sets linked to cell cycle regulation, cell division, and chromosome organization, with most genes either downregulated or not differentially expressed (Fig.3-8A, Supplementary Table 7).

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A similar WGCNA approach in *APPdup* samples revealed the brown module as the strongest positive correlation with *APP* duplication (0.94). This module was enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery and in a lesser proportion, cell adhesion, although to a lesser extent than in DS, as reflected by a smaller number of genes per gene set and a lower proportion of upregulated genes (Fig.3-8B, Supplementary Table 8). The darkgrey module showed minimal enrichment for any gene sets, and none of the enriched sets were relevant to endothelial cell biology (Supplementary Table 8). Among the negatively correlated modules, the blue module displayed the strongest negative correlation with *APPdup* and was enriched for gene sets associated with cell periphery, cell adhesion, cell junctions, and blood vessel morphogenesis, with most genes either downregulated or not differentially expressed. The midnightblue module, which was also negatively correlated with *APPdup* but to a lesser extent, showed similar enrichment for gene sets involved in cell junction organization, cell periphery, motility, and differentiation (Fig.3-8B, Supplementary Table 8).

WGCNA results were largely consistent with GSEA findings for both DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs, reinforcing prior observations. In DS hiPSC-ECs, gene expression showed a strong positive correlation with pathways related to cell adhesion, angiogenesis, apoptosis, and immune response, alongside a pronounced negative correlation with cell cycle and division. In contrast, *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs exhibited a more ambiguous profile, with generally negative correlations involving membrane proteins, cell adhesion, and junction-related pathways.

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A Gene dendrogram and module colors for original and merged modules

B

Module	Module Trait Correlation	pvalue Module Trait Cor	Correlation GS.MM	pvalue cor GS.MM
grey60	0.95743462	2.18E-08	0.87019844	6.24E-102
white	0.63764886	0.01054775	0.45415198	4.19E-09
salmon	0.57386869	0.02528913	0.56493533	1.19E-16
darkorange	0.55721083	0.03093626	0.75663818	1.53E-11
blue	-0.85597218	4.67E-05	0.66100849	2.40E-57

C Gene dendrogram and module colors for original and merged modules

D

Module	Module Trait Correlation	pvalue Module Trait Cor	Correlation GS.MM	pvalue cor GS.MM
brown	0.93760024	2.49E-07	0.82071759	5.65E-30
darkgrey	0.72502136	0.00222604	0.4910309	1.58E-36
midnightblue	-0.55853913	0.03045398	0.44454537	6.38E-10
blue	-0.62915181	0.01197672	0.53713819	4.96E-34

Figure 3-7: WGCNA identifies various merged modules significantly correlated with DS and APPdup. **A, C:** Gene dendrograms and corresponding module color assignments before and after module merging for the DSI (A), APPdup (C) and their respective controls datasets. **B, D:** Summary tables showing the selected merged modules in DSI (B) and APPdup (D), based on module–trait correlation and correlation between gene significance (GS) and module membership (MM), with associated *p*-values.

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IV Analysis of a second *APP* microduplication hiPSC-EC line by bulk

RNA-seq

A second iPSC line was generated from another patient *APPdup* (referred as *APPdup2*, Fig. Fig.1-6C, #3 ROU037004, generated from blood mononuclear cells[217]) from which an isogenic control was created by CRISPR/Cas9 similarly to the first *APPdup* line. After differentiation using the same method as described in chapter 1, hiPSC-ECs were subjected to bulk RNA sequencing to validate and compare findings from the first line. The sequencing was performed in two separate batches and included three *APPdup2* differentiation samples and two *APPdup2* isogenic control differentiations. Correction for both batch and passage number was applied in the design matrix; however, correction for differentiation batch was not feasible, as differentiation 2 only included *APPdup2* samples without isogenic counterpart (Supplementary Table 3). After covariate correction, PCA revealed no clear segregation by genotype, suggesting a weak global transcriptional signature or a higher variability between differentiations as compared to between genotypes (Fig.3-9A). DGE analysis using the same covariates (batch and passage) showed an asymmetric dysregulation profile, with a bias toward upregulated genes and much lower FDR compared to the first *APPdup* line (Fig3-9B). The total number of significantly dysregulated genes was approximately three times lower than in the first *APPdup* dataset (Fig.3-9C). The MA plot revealed an abnormal global trend, with many genes showing large FC but non-significant FDRs, suggesting potential issues with sample heterogeneity (Fig.3-9D). Similarly, the heatmap showed poor segregation between *APPdup2* and its isogenic samples and instead indicated greater variability between differentiations than between genotypes (Fig.3-9E). Notably, the second differentiation samples (*APPdup2* diff2) clustered closely with isogenic samples, and one isogenic sample (diff3-1) appeared to be a strong outlier.

To address these issues, we repeated the DGE analysis excluding the *APPdup2* diff2 samples and the outlier isogenic sample (diff3-1). Following this exclusion, PCA revealed improved genotype segregation (Fig.3-10A), though a residual differentiation effect was still present. The volcano plot showed a more symmetrical distribution of up- and downregulated genes (Fig.3-10B), and while FDR values remained lower than in the first *APPdup* line, the overall number of significantly dysregulated genes was now comparable (Fig.3-10C). The MA plot also showed a more typical trend, although a few genes still exhibited high FC without statistical significance (Fig.3-10D). Importantly, the heatmap now demonstrated clear segregation by genotype, though variability between differentiation batches remained visible (Fig.3-10E).

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Figure 3-9: Transcriptomic profiling of *APPdup2* reveals high inter differentiation variability. *A:* PCA after correction for batch and passage shows no clear segregation between *APPdup2* and isogenic samples. *B:* Volcano plot of DGE results using batch and passage as covariates reveals asymmetric dysregulation, with a bias toward upregulated genes and generally lower FDR compared to the first *APPdup2* line. *C:* Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the *APPdup2* hiPSC-ECs. *D:* MA plot highlights an abnormal trend, with many genes exhibiting high fold changes but non-significant FDRs, suggesting possible sample heterogeneity. *E:* Heatmap of the differentially expressed genes shows poor segregation by genotype and greater variability across differentiations. Notably, the *APPdup2* diff2 samples cluster with isogenic controls, and one isogenic sample (diff3-1) appears as a strong outlier.

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Figure 3-10: Transcriptomic profiling of APPdup2 improves by removing outliers. **A:** PCA after correction for batch and passage without outliers shows better segregation between APPdup2 and isogenic samples. **B:** Volcano plot of DGE results without outliers reveals symmetric dysregulations and improved FDR. **C:** Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the APPdup2 hiPSC-ECs. **D:** MA plot without outliers shows less abnormal trend, but still with genes exhibiting high fold changes but non-significant FDRs. **E:** Heatmap of the differentially expressed genes shows perfect segregation but variability across differentiations, especially in APPdup2 (less in the isogenic controls).

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To explore whether similar biological pathways were affected in *APPdup2*, we performed GSEA on the differentially expressed genes identified after removing the outlier samples. A total of 333 gene sets showed significant enrichment ($FDR < 0.05$, Supplementary Table 9). The negatively enriched gene sets were associated with blood vessel morphogenesis, extracellular matrix organization, protein synthesis, membrane targeting, and apoptosis, as partially illustrated on the ridge plot of the 15 top geneset (Fig.3-11A). In contrast, gene sets with positive normalized enrichment scores (NES) included pathways related to the cell cycle, cytoskeleton and microtubule organization, as well as the immune response. Overall, these results partially mirror the transcriptional trends observed in the first *APPdup* line, from the combined GSEA and WGCNA. This reinforces the notion that *APP* microduplication negatively affects blood vessel development and protein synthesis and targeting to the membrane, while also implicating extracellular matrix remodeling, which may in turn influence cell adhesion. The observed upregulation of immune-related pathways supports a potential pro-inflammatory effect of *APP* duplication varying between patients as it was negatively correlated in the first *APPdup*. Interestingly, the positive enrichment of cell cycle and cytoskeleton-related pathways stands in contrast to what was found in the DS samples, where these processes were strongly negatively regulated both in the GSEA and WGCNA, suggesting possible opposite effect on cell cycle between *APP* microduplication and DS. Nevertheless, when visualizing the expression patterns of representative gene sets in heatmaps, it became apparent that although the FDR was significant, sample clustering was far less robust compared to the first *APPdup* line and the DS samples, once again reflecting high variability between differentiation batches (Fig3-11B, C and D).

Taken together, the GSEA results from this *APPdup2* line provide partial validation of the transcriptional results observed in the initial *APPdup*, suggesting a degree of biological consistency across individuals. Nonetheless, the marked variability between differentiations, which could not be accounted for by technical or biological covariates, limits the interpretability and robustness of these findings. For this reason, and to maintain clarity and reproducibility in downstream analyses, we chose to exclude this second line from further analysis. Despite this, it remains noteworthy that several transcriptional signatures appear reproducible in a second *APPdup* background, pointing to potentially robust disease-associated pathways.

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Figure 3-11: GSEA in APPdup2 reveals dysregulation consistent with the first APPdup hiPSC-ECs results. **A:** Ridge plot showing the top 15 significantly enriched gene sets (FDR < 0.05) identified by GSEA after removal of outlier samples. **B-D:** Heatmaps of selected representative gene sets highlight variability in expression patterns across samples “GO: protein targeting to membrane” (**B**), “GO: extracellular matrix organization” (**C**) and “GO: blood vessel morphogenesis” (**D**).

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Conclusion

In this chapter, transcriptomic profiling of endothelial cells revealed a coordinated set of molecular alterations across multiple analytical layers, highlighting distinct patterns between DS and *APPdup*. Transcriptomic profiling of endothelial cells revealed distinct molecular signatures in DS and *APPdup*. DS showed twice as many dysregulated genes as *APPdup*, including key chromosome 21 genes such as *DYRK1A*, *GABPA*, and *ERG*. While some genes were commonly upregulated, GSEA revealed divergent pathway enrichment: DS was enriched in apoptosis, immune response, lysosomal function, and fucose metabolism, and showed repression of cell cycle and chromosomal organization. In contrast, *APPdup* showed weaker trends, with only gene sets below $FDR < 0.1$, pointing to downregulation of ribosomal function, immune regulation, and protein processing. Both conditions showed downregulation of protein targeting to the membrane, but only DS exhibited upregulation of tight and adherens junction genes, supporting a stronger effect on blood–brain barrier maintenance. WGCNA confirmed these patterns, with DS modules showing negative associations to cell cycle and cytoskeleton but positive link to cell adhesion and junction pathways while *APPdup* indicated mixed correlation to cell adhesion with an overall stronger negative trend. Analysis of a second *APPdup* hiPSC-EC line revealed similar tendencies, particularly in negative correlation towards vascular development and matrix organization, but results were confounded by high inter-differentiation variability. Although the underlying cause remains unclear, this hiPSC line consistently displayed greater differentiation variability compared to the others, suggesting an inherent instability. Notably, it is the only hiPSC line derived from blood mononuclear cells, whereas all other lines were generated from fibroblasts, raising the possibility that the source cell type may influence differentiation potential. This may reflect intrinsic properties of the line, such as epigenetic dysregulation, genetic variation, or heightened sensitivity to environmental conditions, that compromise its reproducibility under the differentiation protocol we used.

Altogether, DS displays a robust endothelial signature with enhanced adhesion and suppressed proliferation, while *APPdup* has milder, yet potentially disruptive, effects on cell adhesion and membrane protein targeting

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Chapter 3 : Consequences on ECs functionality

I Quantification of junction proteins in DS and *APPdup* using immunolabelling of hiPSC-ECs

To investigate whether the transcriptional changes observed in junctional proteins at the transcriptomic level were reflected at the protein level, we performed immunostaining on monolayers of hiPSC-ECs grown on a fibronectin coating and focusing on tight and adherens junction proteins, as well as the endothelial markers VWF, KDR, and APP/A β (Figs. 4-1 and 4-2A).

Relative cell area was calculated by dividing the acquisition surface by the number of nuclei in each image, then normalized to the average value of the respective isogenic control within each batch, allowing for integration of data across multiple experimental batches. Each immunostaining batch consisted of hiPSC-ECs seeded, cultured, fixed, stained, and imaged in parallel under identical conditions, including confocal acquisition parameters, to ensure comparability. Quantification of protein expression was performed across the entire cell area, rather than limited to the membrane, to capture both membrane-associated and cytoplasmic signal. Results were normalized per cell and relative to the respective isogenic control, accounting for differences in cell size and facilitating cross-batch comparison (Fig. 4-2).

Quantification of cell area revealed that DS1-derived ECs were significantly larger than both their isogenic control (1.7-fold increase) and the independent control line (1.2-fold increase). *APPdup* ECs also showed a moderate increase in cell size (1.25-fold compared to their isogenic controls). At the protein level, DS ECs showed a significant increase in the expression of tight junction proteins CLDN5, OCLN, and ZO-1, as well as adherens junction proteins VE-cadherin and CD31, consistent with transcriptomic evidence of upregulated genes involved in cell adhesion and endothelial structure (Fig. 4-2B–H). In contrast, *APPdup* ECs did not show significant changes in tight junction protein levels relative to their isogenic control but did exhibit a modest yet significant increase in adherens junction proteins. Interestingly, Occludin often appeared localized in vesicle-like structures, likely due to internalization triggered by VEGF₁₆₅, which was included in the medium to support hiPSC-EC viability and stability (Fig.2-2B). Nonetheless, Occludin expression remained significantly elevated in DS ECs. Both KDR (VEGFR2) and APP/A β (detected with the 6E10 antibody) were significantly increased in DS and *APPdup* ECs compared to their respective controls, consistent with the

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presence of an additional *APP* copy in both lines. VWF was notably and significantly elevated in DS1, though with high variability.

Overall, these results support our earlier findings: DS ECs exhibit broadly increased expression of both tight and adherens junction proteins compared to their isogenic controls, while *APPdup* ECs display milder changes, limited to adherens junction proteins, and no significant alterations in tight junctions. However, since measurements were performed on whole cells, the data may not fully reflect the functional status of these proteins. Moreover, not all relevant junctional proteins were assessed, such as JAMs, ZO-2, or regulators of junctional integrity. Therefore, the functional impact on endothelial permeability remained to be determined.

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Figure 4-1: Immunostaining of endothelial markers and APP/A β in hiPSC-ECs. Immunofluorescence staining of (from top to bottom) adherens junction marker CD31, tight junction proteins Claudin-5 and Occludin, endothelial markers VWF and KDR, and APP/A β (6E10 antibody), with nuclei counterstained using DAPI, in hiPSC-ECs from individuals with DS, APPdup, their respective isogenic controls, and the independent control line WTS60. Scale bars: 50 μ m.

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Figure 4-2: Quantification of immunostaining for endothelial markers and APP/A β in hiPSC-ECs. **A:** Relative cell area in each hiPSC-EC line. **B-I:** Quantification of adherens junctions VE-cadherin (**B**) and CD31 (**C**), tight junctions Claudin-5 (**D**), Occludin (**E**) and ZO1 (**F**), endothelial markers VWF (**G**) and KDR (**H**) and APP/A β (6E10, **I**). All measurements represent relative signal per cell, normalized to the respective isogenic control line, including cell area (**A**). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA for each comparison. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

II Measure of permeability of monolayers of hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APPdup*

To assess whether the transcriptional and protein-level alterations observed in tight and adherens junction proteins translated into functional changes in endothelial barrier integrity, we established a quantitative permeability assay for hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APPdup* and their corresponding isogenic controls as well as the independent control WTS60. The hiPSC-ECs were grown as a confluent monolayer on Transwell microporous membranes (0.4 μm pore size) made of polycarbonate and coated with fibronectin. As the polycarbonate membrane is opaque, direct visualization of monolayer formation during live culture was not feasible. Consequently, we assessed confluency post-fixation via immunostaining, although this approach resulted in higher background signal compared to standard glass coverslips. To address this limitation, all immunostainings intended for quantification were performed on fibronectin-coated glass coverslips, which allowed for clearer imaging.

The optimal seeding density required to achieve a confluent monolayer on the Transwell inserts was determined empirically through trial and error. We established that seeding 50,000 cells per insert and culturing them for one week reliably produced uniform monolayers and allowed sufficient time for the formation of mature intercellular junctions (Figs. 4-3, 4-4A). Paracellular permeability was assessed by introducing FITC-labeled dextran (70 kDa) into the upper chamber of the Transwell system and quantifying fluorescence in the lower chamber over time (Figs. 4-3A, B and C). Thrombin, which is known to transiently disrupt endothelial junctions [235,236], was used as a positive control (Figs. 4-4D, E). In cases where the measured permeability of untreated monolayers approached that of thrombin-treated samples, indicating incomplete barrier formation, the experiment was excluded from further analysis. To facilitate comparison across multiple independent experiments, permeability values for each cell line were normalized to the average permeability of the independent control within the same experiment. Using this approach, we found that *APPdup* ECs exhibited a 1.3-fold increase in permeability relative to their isogenic controls (Fig. 4-4F), consistent with impaired barrier function. In contrast, DS ECs showed a significant 2.8-fold decrease in permeability compared to both their isogenic and independent controls (Fig. 4-4G), suggesting enhanced barrier integrity. Altogether, these functional findings corroborate the transcriptomic evidence, supporting a link between gene expression changes and altered endothelial barrier properties.

Figure 4-3: Visualization of endothelial monolayers on Transwell membranes. Representative immunofluorescence images showing homogenous endothelial monolayers derived from different hi-PSC-EC lines cultured on Transwell inserts coated with fibronectin. Cells were stained for VE-cadherin (green), CD31 (red), and nuclei (DAPI, blue). All cell lines formed continuous monolayers exhibiting well-defined adherens junctions. Color variations between images are due to differences in acquisition settings; however, all cell lines formed continuous monolayers with well-defined adherens junctions.

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Figure 4-4: See next page for legend

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Figure 4-4: Measure of permeability of monolayers of hiPSC-ECs from DS and APPdup. A: Schematic of the experimental setup used to measure permeability: a 70KDa FITC-dextran passage through a hiPSC-EC monolayer cultured on Transwell inserts was monitored over time, and permeability was calculated using the formula adapted from Czupalla et al. (2014)[237]. **B, C:** Time-course of FITC fluorescence accumulation in the lower well compartment, showing reduced tracer passage in the presence of hiPSC-EC monolayers from DS1 (**B**) and APPdup (**C**) compared to cell-free controls. **D, E:** Permeability values over time for DS1-associated (**D**) and APPdup-associated (**E**) hiPSC-EC, including controls. Thrombin treatment was used as a positive control to disrupt adherens junctions and increase permeability. **F:** Normalized permeability at 120 minutes in DS1, its isogenic control, and the independent control WTS60, showing a significantly reduced permeability in DS1 compared to both controls. **G:** Normalized permeability at 120 minutes in APPdup, its isogenic control, and WTS60, showing a significantly increased permeability in APPdup relative to both controls. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with multiple comparisons. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Discussion

Discussion

General conclusion

During this project, we developed a relevant *in vitro* cellular model to investigate endothelial cells contributions to CAA in Down Syndrome but also in patients carrying a microduplication of the *APP* locus, both leading to ADAD. We employed a panel of five hiPSC lines, including lines carrying Down syndrome (DS1) and an *APP* microduplication (*APPdup*), along with their respective isogenic controls and a healthy donor hiPSC line. These hiPSCs were successfully differentiated into endothelial cells using a stepwise protocol, yielding cells with robust expression of key BBB and endothelial markers among which are tight and adherens junction proteins. We further analyzed and confirmed the endothelial identity through comprehensive transcriptomic comparison with published human brain vascular single-nuclei datasets revealing strong transcriptomic similarity to brain endothelial cells compared to other vasculature cell-types.

A β peptides secretion quantifications not only further established the model's relevance to CAA by showing increased production and secretion of A β peptides, especially A β ₄₀ and A β ₄₂, in both DS1 and *APPdup* endothelial cells compared to isogenic controls, but also revealed distinct A β peptide signature through mass spectrometry study in both conditions compared to each other and to their isogenic controls, including longer and truncated species associated with amyloid pathology. This suggested distinct alteration of the *APP* processing in DS and *APPdup* that could alter their contribution or the role they are playing on the formation of amyloid deposits in CAA.

Transcriptomic profiling of endothelial cells revealed a coordinated set of molecular alterations across multiple analytical layers, highlighting distinct patterns between DS and *APPdup*. Differential gene expression analysis in DS identified approximately twice as many dysregulated genes compared to *APPdup*, including several chromosome 21 genes that could impact endothelial cell function. While some of these genes were upregulated in both DS and *APPdup*, GSEA revealed important differences in the biological processes associated with these changes.

In DS, dysregulated genes were significantly enriched (FDR < 0.05) in pathways related to apoptosis, immune response and inflammation, and endosomal/lysosomal function, with additional enrichment in fucose metabolism. Conversely, DS showed negative enrichment in

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gene sets associated with cell cycle regulation and chromosome organization, suggesting reduced proliferative capacity. In contrast, GSEA of *APPdup*-associated dysregulation revealed more modest trends, with no gene sets reaching an FDR < 0.05. However, gene sets with FDR < 0.1 indicated potential negative regulation of ribosomal function and translation, immune system pathways, and protein processing.

A notable shared feature between DS and *APPdup* was the downregulation of genes involved in protein targeting to the membrane, a process most likely to be essential for endothelial cell junction integrity and function. However, only DS exhibited a significant upregulation of genes involved in blood–brain barrier maintenance, including many tight and adherens junction components.

These findings were further supported by WGCNA. In DS, modules enriched in genes related to cell cycle, chromosome segregation, and cytoskeleton organization were negatively correlated with the condition, whereas modules enriched in cell adhesion and immune response were positively associated. In contrast, *APPdup* showed a negative correlation with modules enriched for cell adhesion and junction, while positively correlated modules showed modest enrichment for similar pathways, indicating a weaker and potentially similar transcriptional pattern compared to DS. Furthermore, GSEA performed on a published list of genes positively or negatively correlated to CAA associated with sAD revealed significant enrichment in genes negatively correlated with CAA in DS while *APPdup* dysregulation were enriched in genes positively correlated with CAA.

To assess the reproducibility of these findings, we performed DGE and GSEA on a second hiPSC-derived EC line from another *APPdup* patient. Despite some variability, the results showed consistent enrichment of gene sets negatively associated with blood vessel morphogenesis, extracellular matrix organization, and protein targeting to the membrane. However, due to the high variability between differentiations in this second *APPdup* line and the presence of outlier samples, these findings should be interpreted with caution.

Overall, our results point to a clear and robust transcriptional signature in DS, characterized by enhanced cell adhesion, immune activation, and tight junction expression, alongside suppressed cell cycle and proliferative pathways. In contrast, *APPdup* appears to exert a more subtle effect, with modest downregulation of cell adhesion and junction-related genes and impaired protein targeting to the membrane, which may contribute to endothelial dysfunction by affecting the synthesis or localization of tight and adherens junction proteins.

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Finally, immunostaining confirmed the observation made at the transcriptomic level to the protein level. DS hiPSC-ECs had significantly higher levels of tight and adherens junction protein while *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs present a much smaller changes, only in adherens junction proteins. Permeability assay using Transwell and a 70kDa FITC dextran revealed significantly high reduction of the permeability in DS hiPSC-ECs while a more modest, yet still significant increase was observed in *APPdup* compared to their respective controls and independent control, confirming once and for all the previous transcriptomic observations on the endothelial functionality.

Roles of A β and *APP* on hiPSC-ECs phenotypes in DS and *APPdup*

To the best of our knowledge, no prior study has examined A β secretion specifically from iPSC-ECs from individuals with DS and *APPdup*. Our findings indicate that ECs secrete A β in a pattern similar to neurons, with levels of A β_{40} approximately 10–15 times higher than those of A β_{42} . This observation aligns with previous reports suggesting that vascular amyloid is predominantly composed of A β_{40} [238].

Our findings indicate a significant increase in the secretion of both A β_{40} and A β_{42} in ECs derived from iPSC from individuals with DS or *APPdup* compared to their respective isogenic controls. This elevated secretion was associated with alterations in the A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio, showing a marked increase in DS and a trend to decrease in *APPdup*. Several studies have reported that the A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio in plasma of individuals with DS decreases with age due to the deposition of A β_{42} [239,240] and generally exhibits a lower A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio compared to controls[241–243]. Conversely, studies using cultured neurons have documented an increased A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio in DS relative to isogenic controls and DS cells with one *APP* copy KO[244,245]. Interestingly, the relatively higher proportion of A β_{40} in plasma compared to culture media may indicate increased deposition of A β_{42} in the brain or reduced transport of A β_{42} across the BBB in individuals with DS. Despite these variations, all the aforementioned studies concur that both A β_{40} and A β_{42} levels are elevated in DS compared to controls. This aligns with our findings and is consistent with the overexpression of the *APP* gene due to the presence of an extra Chr21.

Furthermore, mass spectrometry analysis revealed distinct A β peptide profiles between *APPdup* and DS. The most abundant secreted peptides were A β_{17} and A β_{19} , the later only in DS, both products of APP processing via the amyloidogenic pathway. A β_{19} has been observed in cells expressing APP with the Iowa and Swedish mutations, while A β_{17} was found to be

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increased only with the Swedish mutation[246]. Notably, A β ₁₇ is the second most abundant peptide in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), elevated in Alzheimer's disease, whereas A β ₁₉ is also present but at lower concentrations[247]. Both A β ₁₇ and A β ₁₉ levels decreased following γ -secretase inhibition[248,249], which is known to regulate vascular permeability and angiogenesis in endothelial cells through its role in the Notch signalling pathway, affecting cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival[250]. Indeed, γ -secretase inhibitors have been shown to induce the formation of immature vessel networks[250].

Additionally, A β ₁₉ can be produced following BACE2 cleavage[251], which is increased in DS. While BACE2 favours non-amyloidogenic processing[67], in AD, it can act as a β -secretase[68]. Other studies using DS organoids have suggested that BACE2 acts as an AD-suppressor gene[217]. Here, DS ECs carrying three genomic copies of BACE2 produced very high levels of A β ₁₉ compared to DS isogenic ECs with only two copies of BACE2. Levels of BACE2 transcripts in DS ECs were 7.7fold higher compared to isogenic ECs (Table 4). *APP*dup ECs and their isogenic counterparts produced similar levels of A β ₁₉, albeit lower than those observed in DS. Of note, the previously mentioned study[217] did not include *APP*dup isogenic organoids. Our recent work on *post-mortem* brains[46] showed that A β ₁₇ was absent in control and DS brains but high in DS with AD (DSAD) and *APP*dup. A β ₁₉ levels were high across all cases. Collectively, these findings suggest differential APP processing in DS and *APP*dup.

It is widely accepted that A β disrupts endothelial junctional integrity and impairs BBB function by modulating VE-cadherin phosphorylation[252], reducing the expression and altering the distribution of tight junction proteins[253–255], and promoting cytoskeletal rearrangements such as stress fiber formation and actin filament disorganization[256]. These changes create intercellular gaps and ultimately increase endothelial permeability. However, the intrinsic role of APP in ECs, independent of its cleavage into A β , remains less well characterized. Nonetheless, it is among the most highly expressed genes across all our iPSC-EC lines (average cpm of 2864 across all samples, and 20th most highly express gene, Supplementary Table 11), clearly indicating an important biological role.

Emerging evidence suggests that *APP* expression in the vascular endothelium is important for maintaining endothelial homeostasis. APP has been implicated in the regulation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) expression and the maintenance of nitric oxide (NO)-mediated endothelial function[257]. Given that eNOS-derived NO contributes to the structural and functional integrity of endothelial junctions[258], preserving barrier properties and coordinating intercellular signaling, APP overexpression may enhance endothelial cell

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junctional stability to some extent by increasing NO production and promoting the formation of adherens junctions.

Conversely, APP has also been shown to mediate tyrosine kinase-dependent signaling cascades in endothelial cells[259]. Kinases such as Src and Yes are known to regulate the dynamic remodeling of adherens junctions through the phosphorylation of VE-cadherin, a key adhesion molecule[260,261]. Dysregulation of this pathway by *APP* overexpression could impair junctional plasticity, leading to increased vascular permeability or impaired endothelial repair[260,261]. In this light, *APP* overexpression may exert a dual effect: while promoting some aspects of endothelial stability, it may also destabilize junctions through aberrant kinase signaling. This duality could potentially explain our WGCNA results in *APPdup*, which revealed a balance between a modest pro-cell adherens and a stronger anti-angiogenic, and negative effect on both cell adhesion and junction. These findings highlight the complex, context-dependent role of APP in endothelial biology, suggesting that both its expression level and processing may critically shape vascular function.

Differences in gene expression between DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs and their effects on CAA

First, gene expression changes were found to be more than twice as extensive in DS compared to *APPdup*, with 6,566 and 2,952 differentially expressed genes (DEGs), respectively. This broader impact in DS is due to the overexpression of the entire Chr21, compared to only the *APP* locus in *APPdup*.

Second, GSEA showed that upregulated genes in DS were involved in apoptosis, immune response and inflammation, the endo-lysosomal compartment and fucose metabolism while in *APPdup* downregulated genes belonged to categories such as the immune system and protein synthesis. Only in DS did downregulated genes belong to the cell cycle and proliferation categories. Interestingly “protein targeting to the membrane” gene category was decreased both in DS and *APPdup* while genes involved in maintenance of the BBB were increased in DS but not in *APPdup*. A published study in hiPSC-ECs from DS found similar increase of apoptosis but also mitochondrial reactive oxygen species, angiogenesis and oxygen consumption rate as well as a decrease in EGR1[262]. Consistent with the GSEA findings, our WGCNA also revealed a positive link with angiogenesis (module grey60, Fig.3-8 and Supplementary Table 7) in DS. Furthermore, we observed reduced EGR1 expression in our samples with foldchange

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of -2.75 (Supplementary Table 10). Overall, our results support and partially replicate the previously reported DS endothelial phenotype.

DEGs in DS ECs were enriched in genes negatively correlated with CAA while in *APPdup* DEGs positively correlated with CAA, a difference that could explain the higher CAA severity in *APPdup* compared to DS, suggesting gene expression profile in ECs that could protect against CAA. These findings also support the hypothesis that ECs are intrinsically involved in CAA pathology and support the use of ECs as a relevant model to study early CAA mechanisms. Nevertheless, whether the observed ECs functional alterations (junction organization and permeability changes) are directly driven by genes identified in the CAA correlation analysis remains uncertain. The link is biologically plausible but requires further validation through perturbation studies.

Finally the WGCNA showed that in DS, gene modules positively correlated with the condition were enriched for processes related to cell adhesion, blood vessel morphogenesis, and the immune response, with most genes being upregulated. In contrast, negatively correlated modules were associated with cell cycle regulation and chromosome organization, with genes largely downregulated. In *APPdup*, similar but weaker enrichments for cell adhesion and cell periphery were observed among positively correlated modules, while negatively correlated modules were enriched for cell junction organization, morphogenesis, and motility, with most genes either downregulated or unchanged. Overall GSEA and WGNA analyses pointed to negative changes in cell cycle only in DS, with opposite effects on immune response and membrane proteins involved in cell adhesion and junction between DS and *APPdup*. In *post-mortem* brains from individuals with DS, co-expression modules related to ECs, microglia and astrocytes were positively correlated with immune response and vascular development[263]. The largest number of hub genes were involved in extracellular signalling and cell-cell interaction, consistent with our WGCNA results.

Overexpression of Chr21 genes in DS on ECs phenotypes

Our data shows upregulation of *APP*, *DYRK1A*, *ERG*, and *GABPA* transcripts in both *APPdup* and DS, with *RUNX1* (a transcription factor essential for hematopoiesis) downregulated in both conditions. Conversely, *IL10RB*, *BACE2*, and *POFUT2* (an enzyme that adds O-fucose sugars to proteins, aiding their proper folding and function) were upregulated in DS but downregulated in *APPdup* while *RCAN1* was upregulated in DS ECs alone (Table 4, Fig.3-4C).

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ERG is known to directly regulate the expression of *CLDN5* gene by binding to its promoter region; knockdown or loss of *ERG* leads to reduced *CLDN5* levels and increased endothelial permeability[228,229]. In addition, it positively regulates adherens junctions through Wnt/ β -Catenin but also affects VE-cadherin[230,231]. Overall, the overexpression of ERG is expected to stabilize not only tight junctions but also adherens junctions and therefore decrease ECs permeability.

Although less studied in ECs, *DYRK1A* loss-of-function disrupts tight junctions, increases vascular permeability, and causes cerebral haemorrhage, indicating its role in maintaining junctional stability[184]. Mechanistically, *DYRK1A* regulates calcium homeostasis, essential for assembling and maintaining tight and adherens junctions. Disruption leads to altered calcium-binding protein and adhesion molecule expression, compromising junction integrity[184]. Thus, *DYRK1A* upregulation could enhance junction stability and barrier function, consistent with its positive regulation of angiogenesis and ECs proliferation[226]. It was also demonstrated that *DYRK1A* increases EGFR1 via PPARG suppression and that the involvement of EGFR1 on ECs phenotypes in DS (apoptosis, mitochondrial reactive oxygen species production, angiogenesis, and oxygen consumption rate) can be restored either by EGFR1 suppression by treatment with pioglitazone or inhibition of *DYRK1A*[262]. It will be interesting to know whether *DYRK1A* inhibition can modify the decrease of permeability of a monolayer of ECs with DS.

Downregulation of *IL10RB* in *APPdup* may impair endothelial junction integrity, as *IL10RB* mediates IL-10 signaling that reduces endothelial inflammation, apoptosis, and permeability, while preserving VE-cadherin expression[264–266]. Similarly, *POFUT2*, an enzyme responsible for O-fucosylation of thrombospondin type 1 repeat (TSR)-containing proteins, is critical for post-translational modification of extracellular matrix (ECM) and adhesion proteins, which are vital for ECs junctions[267–269]. Its downregulation in *APPdup* could impair ECM protein maturation and junction function.

RUNX1 induces VE-cadherin expression and promotes angiogenesis in embryonic endothelial precursors. Loss of *RUNX1* results in defective vascular formation, increased permeability, and hemorrhage, underscoring its role in maintaining barrier integrity[270]. Its downregulation in both *APPdup* and DS likely contributes to junctional defects, particularly in adherens junctions. We were quite surprised to find *RUNX1* downregulated in DS-derived endothelial cells, despite its well-documented upregulation in other DS contexts. Overexpression of *RUNX1* in DS modulates the extracellular matrix (ECM) in various cell types and tissues such as heart and fibroblasts, increasing cell migration while those effects are

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reduced by silencing RUNX1[271]. This unexpected result may be explained by the cell type and differentiation state: in mature endothelial cells, RUNX1 is typically expressed at very low basal levels[272] crucial for proper endothelium function[273], and its overexpression, due to trisomy, may have triggered a compensatory epigenetic silencing mechanism, such as promoter hypermethylation, to maintain cellular homeostasis. A couple studies already documented the hypermethylation of the *RUNX1* gene in DS blood[274,275]. This suggests that the response to gene dosage imbalance may differ depending on the cellular context and developmental stage, highlighting the complexity of transcriptional regulation in DS.

FeatureID	Line	FC	FDR	Status	Average expression (cpm)
APP	DS1	1.87	4.25E-16	Up in DS1	1658.91
	APPdup	1.47	7.95E-05	Up in APPdup	1920.15
DYRK1A	DS1	1.67	6.04E-10	Up in DS1	33.50
	APPdup	1.37	2.56E-03	Up in APPdup	25.30
ERG	DS1	1.94	6.44E-06	Up in DS1	213.90
	APPdup	1.29	2.12E-03	Up in APPdup	213.28
GABPA	DS1	1.42	6.83E-04	Up in DS1	16.64
	APPdup	1.30	1.27E-02	Up in APPdup	19.38
RUNX1	DS1	-10.18	4.39E-77	Down in DS1	4.60
	APPdup	-2.26	1.32E-02	Down in APPdup	2.65
IL10RB	DS1	2.41	3.15E-19	Up in DS1	43.91
	APPdup	-1.38	6.03E-04	Down in APPdup	32.74
BACE2	DS1	7.70	1.34E-70	Up in DS1	240.19
	APPdup	-1.54	2.51E-02	Down in APPdup	84.58
POFUT2	DS1	1.57	1.19E-22	Up in DS1	60.85
	APPdup	-1.35	9.86E-05	Down in APPdup	51.18
RCAN1	DS1	2.72	5.61E-6	Up in DS1	58.15
	APPdup	-1.37	0.29	Not regulated	36.51

Table 4: Expression changes of key Chr21 genes in hiPSC-ECs from DS and APPdup and their isogenic controls.

GABPA regulates genes essential for endothelial morphogenesis and cell structure[276]. A conserved GABP-binding motif was found in *Robo4* promoter, validated by mutagenesis and *in vivo* reporter assays, and critical for Robo4 endothelial expression[277]. Robo4 itself plays a key role in barrier stabilization and angiogenesis[278–280]. Moreover, GABP α/γ complexes repress *VEGF* transcription by promoter binding. In cerebral ischemia

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models, reduced BAI2 lowers GABP levels, resulting in VEGF upregulation[281]. Therefore, *GABPA* upregulation may slow the cell cycle by repressing VEGF[282], consistent with our WGCNA results. Collectively, *GABPA* overexpression in DS and *APPdup* likely impacts endothelial function at multiple levels.

RCAN1 (also known as DSCR1) is a key regulator of calcineurin signaling in endothelial cells, with RCAN1.4 being the most relevant isoform in this setting. RCAN1.4 is robustly induced by vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and is required for processes such as VEGFR-2 internalization, endothelial cell migration, and the establishment of cell polarity during angiogenesis. By orchestrating cytoskeletal remodeling and directional movement, RCAN1.4 also supports endothelial sprouting and the formation of new vessels[283]. Beyond its role in angiogenesis, RCAN1 contributes to the preservation and restoration of endothelial barrier integrity after inflammatory or permeability-inducing challenges, such as histamine exposure[284]. Its overexpression strengthens barrier function through mechanisms such as maintaining tight junctions and inhibiting endothelial nitric oxide synthase (NOS3)[285]. In addition, increased RCAN1 expression in 5xFAD mice has been shown to enhance the coverage and function of dorsal meningeal lymphatic vessels, leading to improved clearance of waste products (including A β) from the brain[286].

Although several of these genes are upregulated in both *APPdup* and DS, the greater fold changes observed in DS, combined with differences in gene dysregulation patterns, may underline the compensatory effects seen exclusively in DS (Table 4).

BBB Functionality and Aging in DS and *APPdup*

While the opposing effect on ECs permeability in DS and *APPdup* are in accordance with molecular analysis, the decrease in ECs permeability observed in DS ECs does not equate to preserved or improved BBB function during aging compared to the general population. Both *APPdup* and DS share a common pathogenic driver: *APP* overexpression leading to increased A β production. This A β burden is a major contributor to age-related endothelial dysfunction, impaired A β clearance, and ultimately a self-reinforcing cycle of endothelial injury, A β accumulation, CAA, and associated microbleeds and ICH[81]. Although the reduced permeability observed in DS ECs may confer a comparatively more resilient BBB than in *APPdup*, *APP* overexpression alone is still expected to greatly compromise BBB integrity relative to euploid controls. Thus, in DS, overexpression of other chromosome 21 genes could partially delay endothelial impairment (therefore maintaining transcellular clearance) and

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mitigate, though not prevent, the severity of CAA and cerebrovascular pathology compared to *APPdup*, while both conditions remain substantially more vulnerable than typical aging due to *APP* gene dosage.

Furthermore, ECs from DS exhibit a slower cell cycle and increased size, features that may limit regenerative capacity during aging and thereby contribute to BBB dysfunction later in life. The initially enhanced junctional organization could confer early-stage resilience, especially when compared to *APPdup* ECs. This might suggest a window of relative vascular stability in DS, followed by a decline associated with reduced renewal capacity and cumulative stress. Moreover, the positive correlation with angiogenesis observed in the WGCNA could actually compromised the equilibrium of different cell type interactions in the BBB. Recent work from Dr. Elizabeth Head's group from University of California was presented at AAIC 2025 (ID: 106199, unpublished) where they focused on assessing vascular integrity in *post-mortem* DSAD brain tissues compared to neurotypical controls, using histological markers to probe BBB disruption. They found increased basement membrane coverage, vascular density and length, pericyte number, string vessels, and fibrin deposition in the occipital cortex. They concluded that DSAD was associated with significant vascular remodeling and that the fibrin leakage was evidence of blood–brain barrier breakdown. Parts of these results are in accordance with our WGCNA results that found a positive correlation between DS and angiogenesis, but the effect on a complete vascular system is not predictable from our results and model. We await the full publication of this work, as it may provide additional insight into the *in vivo* relevance of the endothelial alterations we observed in our hiPSC-derived models.

It was also found that DS ECs exhibit decreased proliferation, reduced migration, less responsive to VEGF with an increase in VEGF receptors (FLT1, KDR and FLT4) and a weak TNF- α inflammatory response[287]. The decrease of response to VEGF could be due to the increase of formation of A β -VEGF-derived peptides complexes in DS and *APPdup*. Indeed it was shown that those VEGF-derived peptides can prevent A β aggregation and toxicity[288]. In our study FLT4 and KDR were increased with FC of 1.9 and 1.8 respectively (Supplementary Table 10), suggesting reproducibility across various DS lines.

Limitations

While our hiPSC-EC model provides valuable insights into cell-intrinsic changes, it cannot fully recapitulate the complexity of the NVU and the brain microenvironment. Factors such as aging, multicellular interactions, and systemic inflammation likely play crucial roles in

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modulating the BBB integrity and CAA progression. The interplay between endothelial, glial, pericytes, smooth muscle cells and immune cells at the NVU suggests that the transcriptomic and functional changes observed in hiPSC-ECs represent only a subset of the broader *in vivo* effects. Importantly, chronic disturbances in homeostasis, particularly those related to A β accumulation and impaired clearance, are expected to further compromise BBB function over time. Furthermore, while transcriptomic comparisons confirmed that our hiPSC-ECs share key features with brain ECs, we were unable to compare them directly with ECs from other organs. Moreover, the differentiation protocol employed was primarily inspired by one designed to generate general ECs rather than brain-specific ECs, raising the possibility that certain brain-specific endothelial characteristics were not fully captured. Despite this, the results remain robust and interpretable, as all comparisons were made to isogenic controls differentiated and processed under identical conditions.

On the same subject, several studies have highlighted the variability in endothelial cell morphology *in vitro*, which can be influenced by donor origin[289], differentiation protocols[159,161,290], and culture conditions such as medium composition and substrate[159]. The elongated morphology observed in our iPSC-ECs likely reflects the high concentration of VEGF₁₆₅ used, which is known to stimulate endothelial proliferation, and is consistent with previous reports of brain EC morphology *in vitro*[159,289,291]. Although VEGF is known to modulate endothelial cell morphology and barrier permeability[221,222], as mentioned in chapter 1, VEGF complementation was deemed necessary, however, no VEGF₁₆₅ was added during the permeability assays, in an effort to limit its effect on iPSC-ECs permeability properties.

As the hiPSC-EC model continues to evolve, and protocols tailored specifically to brain ECs become more refined and available, future studies will be better positioned to address these limitations and further enhance the physiological relevance of the model.

We acknowledge that the findings presented in this study are based on hiPSC-ECs derived from a single individual with Down syndrome and one with *APP* microduplication. While this represents an inherent limitation, efforts are ongoing to replicate these results, particularly regarding endothelial permeability, using three additional hiPSC-EC lines from three individuals with DS from the GO-DS21 European project (<https://go-ds21.eu>). A first differentiation was attempted but abnormal morphology was observed from thawing at P2, and RNAseq confirmed a redifferentiation toward fibroblast identity. A second differentiation has already been performed, and preliminary results show proper endothelial identity and no

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abnormal morphology. In the case of *APP* microduplication, this pathology being extremely rare, finding new hiPSC lines will probably be challenging; however, the partial replication of key transcriptional trends in a second *APPdup* line provides encouraging evidence that the observed effects are not restricted to a single individual and may reflect broader disease-associated mechanisms.

Future directions

In addition to the Transwell-based dextran permeability assay, measuring transendothelial electrical resistance (TEER) represents a valuable complementary approach to assess endothelial barrier integrity. While the permeability assay provides a direct measure of paracellular diffusion of macromolecules, TEER offers real-time, non-invasive quantification of ionic conductance across the endothelial monolayer, reflecting the integrity and tightness of intercellular junctions[292]. TEER is particularly sensitive to early and subtle changes in barrier function and junctional organization, including alterations that may not yet affect large molecule permeability[230]. Moreover, TEER allows for continuous monitoring over time, enabling dynamic assessment of barrier responses to stimuli such as cytokines, growth factors, or drugs. Integrating TEER measurements alongside macromolecular flux assays would therefore strengthen the interpretation of barrier function in hiPSC-ECs by capturing both ionic and molecular permeability components. Additionally, it would facilitate detection of intermediate phenotypes or compensatory mechanisms that may not be apparent through endpoint assays alone.

To explore this approach, we attempted to culture hiPSC-derived endothelial cells on electrode-compatible artificial basal membrane[293] (ABM, developed in collaboration with Pr. Yong Chen at ENS, Département de chimie). While the *APPdup* and isogenic control cells adhered and grew successfully on the ABM membranes (Fig.5-1), all attempts to apply an electric current (across a range of frequencies and acquisition parameters) resulted in rapid and complete cell death. Despite multiple optimizations, including varying current strength, exposure duration, and timing post-seeding, the cells consistently failed to tolerate electrical stimulation. We therefore concluded that these hiPSC-ECs, particularly those with the *APPdup* background and its isogenic control, were unusually sensitive to electrical currents and unable to support TEER-based analysis under the tested conditions. Due to these repeated and consistent failures, we did not pursue TEER measurements on the later-derived DS1 line and its isogenic control, as similar outcomes were anticipated. As such, we relied exclusively on the

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molecular weight-based paracellular permeability assay to functionally evaluate endothelial barrier integrity across all cell lines.

Since the initial failed attempts at performing TEER, the ICM has acquired an xCELLigence RTCA eSight system (Agilent Technologies), which may offer a promising alternative for reassessing endothelial barrier integrity in our model[294]. Unlike traditional TEER systems that rely on external electrodes and direct current application, xCELLigence uses interdigitated gold microelectrodes embedded in the bottom of specialized E-plates to continuously monitor electrical impedance in real time, under low-voltage conditions that could potentially be more tolerated by our cells. This could allow for dynamic measurements of cell adhesion, proliferation, and barrier function. It also permits parallel live-cell imaging, which could facilitate direct visualization of monolayer integrity and junctional morphology during the assay. Furthermore, the use of 96 wells plate would allow for high numbers of replicates tested in parallels.

To further advance our research and move closer to physiological relevance, we aim to develop three-dimensional cerebrovascular organoids that better recapitulate the *in vivo* human brain environment. Building on previous results from our laboratory, using StemCell Technologies kits to generate vascular organoids, we are now focusing on creating fusion organoids by combining vascular and dorsal forebrain organoids derived from different iPSC lines (Fig.5-2), in collaboration with the teams of Dr. Philippe Ravassard and Dr. Bassem Hassan at ICM and with the help of Dr. Benjamin Galet and Dr. Johnny Bou Roupheal. This approach is designed to help us investigate the role of the vascular system in the development and progression of A β deposition, a hallmark of Alzheimer's disease and related disorders. So far, we have successfully generated dorsal forebrain organoids from *APP*dup iPSCs and preliminary results suggest significant increase in A β accumulation starting at day 90, when compared to isogenic control-derived dorsal forebrain organoids (Figs.5-3B, C). In parallel, we have established vascular organoids independently and performed their fusion with the dorsal forebrain organoids. Integration of the vascular component into the neural organoid was observable under brightfield microscopy, indicating successful physical incorporation (Figs.5-3A). However, due to technical difficulties, we have not yet been able to successfully perform immunostaining on the vascular organoids. As a result, we have not been able to confirm their cellular composition, nor to determine the presence or distribution of A β within these structures.

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Figure 5-1: *hi-PSC-ECs form a confluent monolayer on artificial basement membrane in both APPdup (A) and isogenic control lines (B). Immunostaining for VE-cadherin (green) and CD31 (red) confirms the presence of endothelial junctions and appropriate cell–cell contact.*

Discussion

Figure 5-2: Formation of cerebrovascular organoids to investigate the role of the vasculature in the formation of $A\beta$ deposits. A: formation of autologous and heterologous organoids B: Protocol of the formation of fusion organoids.

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Figure 5-3: Preliminary characterization of cerebrovascular organoids. *A:* Spontaneous fusion of dorsal forebrain (blue arrowhead) and vascular (red arrowhead) organoids observed within a few days of co-culture (no clear difference observed between genotypes). *B:* Immunostaining of 90-day-old dorsal forebrain organoids derived from *APPdup* iPSCs (left) and isogenic controls (right), showing Caspase-3 (green), $A\beta$ (6E10, red), and Sox2 (white) expression. *C:* Quantification of immunostaining signals across dorsal forebrain organoids at different developmental stages. Signals are normalized to DAPI (to adjust for organoid size and acquisition variability) and to the isogenic control.

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We also intend to evaluate BBB permeability *in vivo* using the Dp(16)1Yey/+ (Dp16) mouse model of Down syndrome, compared to euploid control mice. Importantly, the Dp16 mouse model carries a segmental duplication on mouse chromosome 16 from the Lipi locus to the Zbtb21 locus (<https://www.alzforum.org/research-models/dp161yey>, UCSC Genome Browser on Mouse GRCm39/mm39 coordinate chr16:75,337,402-97,763,815), which includes orthologues of several human Chr21 genes we hypothesize drive the EC permeability differences observed in our *in vitro* model: including *App*, *Dyrk1a*, *Erg*, *Gabpa*, *Runx1*, *Il10rb*, *Rcan1* and *Bace2*. *Pofut2* being located on mouse chromosome 10, it is not included in the duplication of mouse chromosome 16. This will help elucidate whether the *in vitro* endothelial dysfunction translates into altered BBB properties *in vivo*. We plan to administer FITC-dextran (4kDa and 70 kDa) systemically and, after circulation, collect brain tissue for quantitative fluorescence analysis on brain homogenates and histology on brain sections.

Another possible future direction could be to extend our findings by examining human *post-mortem* brain tissue to determine whether the endothelial alterations observed in our hiPSC-derived EC models are also present *in vivo*. Specifically, we could perform immunohistochemistry on brain sections from individuals with DS, *APPdup* and age-matched controls from the collection set up in the team[46]. Using antibodies against key endothelial markers including CD31, VE-cadherin or claudin-5 could potentially allow us to assess morphological features of the endothelium, such as vessel density, branching, diameter, and junctional continuity. This approach may allow us to detect structural or organizational changes in endothelial cells that mirror the changes in ECs size, disrupted junctional integrity and altered permeability we observed *in vitro* in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs.

The last and perhaps most ambitious direction would be to perform a longitudinal study involving both DS and neurotypical control participants at multiple ages, from early childhood to late adulthood and AD late stages, using Dynamic Contrast-Enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI), a powerful, non-invasive method to assess BBB permeability *in vivo*[295]. Its capacity to detect subtle and region-specific changes in BBB integrity makes it particularly well-suited for tracking vascular alterations across the lifespan.

Endothelial cell dysfunction has recently gained significant attention as a key contributor to neurovascular and neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's disease and CAA[194–196,296–301]. Our findings clearly demonstrate that endothelial cell function is significantly and differentially altered in DS and *APPdup*, two distinct genetic causes of early-

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onset CAA. The combination of transcriptomic, proteomic, and functional permeability data paints a coherent and compelling picture of endothelial involvement in disease pathology. These findings not only underscore the value of hiPSC-derived ECs in modeling cerebrovascular phenotypes, but also highlight the need for broader validation across additional patient-derived lines. Moving forward, it will be essential to confirm these results in larger cohorts and delve deeper into the fundamental biology of endothelial cells, not only in the context of neurovascular disorders like CAA, but also as active players in broader brain homeostasis and degeneration. Our work opens the door for further exploration of endothelial contributions to CAA and suggests new angles for therapeutic investigation targeting the neurovascular unit

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All data and supplementary materials generated in this study have been deposited on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18259653) and can be accessed using the thesis title and author details.

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```
library(Seurat)
library(SeuratObject)

# Load your bulk RNA-seq dataset (as a matrix or data frame)
bulk_expr <- read.csv("global_expression_genes_updated_interest.csv", sep=";", row.names = 1)

# Load your singlenuclei RNA-seq dataset (as a matrix or data frame)
sn_data <- readRDS("ROSMAP.VascularCells.counts_full.rds") # Replace with your actual data file
metadata <- readRDS("ROSMAP.VascularCells.meta_full.rds")

# Find common genes and only keep them in bulk RNAseq data
bulk_genes <- rownames(bulk_expr)
sn_genes <- rownames(sn_data)
common_genes <- intersect(bulk_genes, sn_genes)
bulk_expr <- bulk_expr[common_genes,]

# Create a Seurat object for bulk RNA-seq
bulk_seurat <- CreateSeuratObject(counts = bulk_expr)

# Create a Seurat object for singlenuclei RNA-seq
sn_seurat <- CreateSeuratObject(counts = sn_data)

# Add metadata to the seurat object
all(rownames(metadata) == colnames(sn_seurat))
sn_seurat <- AddMetaData(sn_seurat, metadata)

# Normalize bulk data (match the snRNA-seq pipeline)
bulk_seurat <- NormalizeData(bulk_seurat)
bulk_seurat <- FindVariableFeatures(bulk_seurat)
bulk_seurat <- ScaleData(bulk_seurat)

# Normalize sn data
sn_seurat <- NormalizeData(sn_seurat)
sn_seurat <- FindVariableFeatures(sn_seurat)
sn_seurat <- ScaleData(sn_seurat)

# run pca and umap
sn_seurat <- RunPCA(sn_seurat, npcs=50)

# Analyse how much variance is explained by each principal component in a PCA
# to determine the "dims" parameter
stdev <- sn_seurat[["pca"]][@stdev]
variance <- stdev^2
prop_var <- variance / sum(variance) # Proportion variance explained by each PC
cum_var <- cumsum(prop_var)
plot(cum_var, xlab = "PC", ylab = "Cumulative Variance Explained", type = "b",
     pch = 19)
```

Supplementary Annex 1: R code

```
abline(h = 0.8, col = "red", lty = 2) # 80% variance line

#Run UMAP on the selected dimensions (parameter "dims")
sn_seurat<- RunUMAP(sn_seurat, dims=1:15, return.model=TRUE)

#Find anchors
anchors <- FindTransferAnchors(reference = sn_seurat, query = bulk_seurat,
                               dims = 1:15, reference.reduction = "pca",
                               k.score = 20 )

bulk_seurat_map <- MapQuery(anchorset = anchors,
                            query = bulk_seurat,
                            reference = sn_seurat,
                            reduction.model = "umap",
                            transferdata.args=list(k.weight=15))

# Plot reference UMAP
umap_sn_seurat <- DimPlot(sn_seurat, reduction = "umap", group.by = "cellsubtype")

# Plot bulk projections on the same UMAP
umap_bulk_seurat <- DimPlot(bulk_seurat_map, reduction = "ref.umap", pt.size = 5, label = TRUE)

# Combine plots
umap_sn_seurat + umap_bulk_seurat

library(ggplot2)

# Extract umap coordinates

#Extracts UMAP coordinates from the reference Seurat object umap_sn_seurat, and
#sets a new column group equal to cell subtype labels (e.g., endothelial
#subtypes, fibroblasts, etc.).
df_sn_seurat <- umap_sn_seurat$data
df_sn_seurat$group <- df_sn_seurat$cellsubtype

#Extracts UMAP coordinates from the query dataset (bulk_seurat) and labels all
#its points as "Query" (i.e., hiPSC-EC)
df_bulk_seurat <- umap_bulk_seurat$data
df_bulk_seurat$group <- "Query"

#Ensures the two data frames have matching column names so they can be combined.
colnames(df_bulk_seurat)<-colnames(df_sn_seurat)

# Combine the dataset
df_combined <- rbind(df_sn_seurat, df_bulk_seurat)

# Create the overlay UMAP plot
library(dplyr)
overlay<-ggplot(df_combined, aes(x = umap_1, y = umap_2, color = group)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.7) +
  theme_minimal() +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("Query" = "red",
                                "aEndo"="blue4",
                                "vEndo"="royalblue",
                                "capEndo"="blue",
```

Supplementary Annex 1: R code

```
"Fib1"="seagreen",  
"Fib2"="green3",  
"Fib3"="green2",  
"Per1"="orange",  
"Per2"="orange3",  
"aSMC"="purple",  
"vSMC"="purple3",  
"Ependymal"="hotpink"))  
print(overlay)  
  
ggsave("umap_overlay.png", plot = overlay)
```

Supplementary Annexes

Supplementary Annex 2: Published Review Article: Reviewing the possible connection interplay between cerebral amyloid angiopathy and blood brain barrier integrity in Down syndrome.

Review written as my thesis introduction and published the journal *Alzheimer and Dementia* in September 2025.

REVIEW ARTICLE

Reviewing the possible connection between cerebral amyloid angiopathy and blood–brain barrier integrity in Down syndrome

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Abstract

Individuals with Down syndrome (DS) have a higher risk of developing cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA), primarily because of the excessive production of amyloid beta ($A\beta$). However, the consequences of CAA on blood–brain barrier (BBB) integrity and the neurovascular unit (NVU) are still not well understood. Systematic search was conducted on PubMed using 12 targeted keywords related to CAA, BBB, and the NVU in combination with DS. Additional sources were identified and the research gap validated using Consensus and ChatGPT-assisted literature screening. Individuals with DS are vulnerable to cerebrovascular conditions across their lifespan. Despite pronounced $A\beta$ pathology, CAA appears less frequent than in cases with microduplication of the *APP* locus, suggesting distinct vascular dynamics potentially influenced by chromosome 21 genes. Limited direct evidence on BBB integrity in DS highlights the need for mechanistic and longitudinal studies. DS offers a unique lens for exploring cerebrovascular resilience and CAA pathogenesis.

KEYWORDS

Alzheimer's disease, amyloid beta, amyloid-related imaging abnormalities, blood–brain barrier, cerebral amyloid angiopathy, chromosome 21, Down syndrome, induced pluripotent stem cell models, intracerebral hemorrhage, microbleeds, neuroimaging, neurovascular unit, vascular pathology

Highlights

- Down syndrome (DS) individuals overexpressing amyloid precursor protein (APP) are at risk for cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) and lobar microbleeds.
- CAA is less severe in DS compared to APP microduplication (*APPdup*) cases.
- Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) is less common in DS than in *APPdup* cases.
- DS may have protective mechanisms against CAA and ICH involving BBB function.
- Few longitudinal studies examine BBB permeability in DS across the lifespan.

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1 | COMORBIDITIES IN DOWN SYNDROME

Down syndrome (DS), originally described in 1866 by John Langdon Down from whom its name derives,¹ is associated with a wide range of physical and cognitive characteristics. It is the most common chromosomal abnormality linked to intellectual disability resulting from a complete (95% of cases), or partial duplication of the 21st chromosome.^{2,3} It affects 3.3 to 6.7 per 10,000 individuals worldwide.³

The most common physical phenotypes include flat facial profile, almond shape eyes, epicanthal fold, small nose and flat nasal bridge, small mouth with macroglossia, small low-set ears, short neck with excess skin at the nape, hypotonia, short stature, presence of brachycephaly, single palmar crease, clinodactyly, sandal gap deformity, and atlantoaxial instability (loose neck joints).⁴⁻⁷ It is also considered the most common condition associated with intellectual disability, ranging from mild to moderate, delayed speech and language development, delayed motor milestones, increased risk of autism spectrum disorder, and general behavioral issues.⁸⁻¹⁰

Besides intellectual disability, individuals with DS have increased risk for several pathologies such as cardiac malformations,¹¹ diabetes,^{12,13} hypothyroidism,¹⁴ gastrointestinal defects,¹⁵ hematologic defect (increased risk of leukemia),¹⁶ hearing¹⁷ and vision defects,¹⁸ increased susceptibility to infections,¹⁹ obstructive sleep apnea,²⁰ and obesity.²¹ In addition, individuals with DS are at high risk for developing Alzheimer disease (AD; 77% in their 60s).²² They exhibit the same neuropathological hallmarks as those observed in individuals with AD in the general population, but at a much younger age. By their fourth decade, all individuals with DS show full-blown AD pathology, regardless of the presence of symptoms.²³

Clinical features associated with DS also occur in the general population but at different rates, severity, or age of onset. Interestingly, individuals with DS have significantly lower risk of developing solid tumors,²⁴ arteriosclerosis,²⁵ and arterial hypertension^{21,26,27} suggesting protective mechanisms associated with the overexpression of genes from chromosome 21. They are also less prone to smoking.²⁸ The risk of vascular fibrosis and calcification was found to be lower in the hippocampus,²⁹ but higher in the basal ganglia.³⁰

2 | CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES IN DS

2.1 | Moyamoya disease

Individuals with DS are at high risk for moyamoya disease (MMD, ORPHA:2573), a rare blood vessel condition affecting most commonly children, in which the carotid artery in the skull becomes blocked or narrowed. Its incidence is 0.086 to 0.94 per 100,000 individuals in the general population³¹ while 9.5% of all MMD cases under 15 are DS.³² This suggests shared developmental dysfunctions that contribute to the occlusion of the internal carotid artery and its proximal branches. Combined with the numerous case reports of vascular abnormalities in young individuals with DS,³³⁻³⁹ these findings indicate an increased

vulnerability of the neurovascular unit (NVU) in DS from a very young age.

2.2 | Cerebral amyloid angiopathy

Cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) is characterized by an accumulation of amyloid beta (A β) peptides in the walls of the cerebral blood vessels, resulting in vascular fragility, microbleeds, and impaired blood flow.⁴⁰⁻⁴² Sporadic CAA is most often present in the occipital cortex and other neocortical areas while medial temporal structures and the hippocampus are less affected.⁴³ The first description of "plaques like incrustation" in the cerebral blood vessel of an individual with DS was reported in 1948.⁴⁴ Since then, numerous *post mortem* studies have confirmed a significantly higher risk of CAA in individuals with DS, increasing their susceptibility to stroke and microbleed with aging.⁴⁵⁻⁵⁰ While individuals with DS also face a high risk of developing AD, the interplay between CAA and AD remains to be fully elucidated.

This review will focus on the NVU, which is influenced by both risk and protective factors in DS, with particular emphasis on CAA. Our aim is to explore current research and discoveries while also highlighting limitations, research gaps, and emerging topics in the field.

3 | METHODS

We conducted a comprehensive search on PubMed for publications up to December 2024, using "Down syndrome" as the primary keyword in combination with 12 additional keywords: "(brain) AND (vascular)," "(cerebral amyloid angiopathy)," "(cerebral endothelial cell)," "(cerebral smooth muscle cell)," "(perivascular macrophage)," "(pericyte)," "(blood-brain barrier)," "(blood-brain barrier permeability)," "(cerebral atherosclerosis)," "(cerebral arteriosclerosis)," "(microbleed)," and "(cerebral hemorrhage)." The number of records found for each keyword combination is detailed in the workflow (Figure 1 and Table S1 in supporting information). The selection of these keywords was the result of discussions among the authors to ensure all relevant research on CAA in DS was included. In total, 711 records were identified.

The screening process consisted of three steps. First, abstracts were reviewed to exclude irrelevant records that did not mention DS or vascular content (e.g., articles using "down" in the context of "down-regulated" in other syndromes). The second step involved removing duplicate publications from overlapping keyword searches. Finally, in the third step, we excluded articles deemed irrelevant after full-text review or those for which full-text access was unavailable. After all screening processes, 24 case reports, 86 research articles, and 46 reviews were included for a total of 156 records.

It is important to note that due to the evolving nomenclature of DS, earlier articles using outdated terms (e.g., "mongoloid") may have been missed. Additionally, some articles that were not directly related to CAA or vascular issues (such as those on A β metabolism or general DS pathology) were also included. Relevant articles were identified

FIGURE 1 Screening process flowchart. The figure details the total number of records retrieved, screened, and excluded, as well as the number of relevant records selected for final analysis.

through general reviews and PubMed search. Ongoing clinical trials were identified during congresses attended by the authors.

To confirm the research gap on BBB permeability in DS, artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, Consensus, and Perplexity were used to identify all studies on the topic, ensuring no relevant research was overlooked. These tools were also used during the writing process to help rephrase and improve the clarity of the text.

4 | AD AND CAA IN DS

4.1 | Molecular mechanisms—A β deposition and vascular dysfunction: which comes first?

AD is a progressive neurodegenerative disease characterized clinically by memory loss and cognitive decline, disorientation, and impaired praxis.^{51,52} At the pathological level, it is defined by the deposition of extracellular A β peptides in the parenchyma and intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles composed of hyperphosphorylated tau.^{53,54} AD is classified based on its pathology and underlying causes. Sporadic late onset AD (sLOAD) and sporadic early onset AD (sEOAD) are distinguished by their age of onset, clinical symptoms, pathology topography, and a greater genetic component often associated with sEOAD. They represent > 95% of all AD cases.^{47,55,56} Autosomal dominant AD (ADAD) results from point mutations in the amyloid precursor protein gene (*APP*), presenilin genes (*PSEN1* or *PSEN2*),⁵⁵ or microduplications of the *APP* locus (*APPdup*), with a total of three copies of that locus, as in DS.⁵⁷ DS, with three copies of chromosome 21, including the *APP* locus, is now considered ADAD.⁵⁸ In ADAD cases with point mutations, alteration of APP processing leads to changes in A β production and deposition.^{59,60} In contrast, DS and *APPdup* cases exhibit increased A β production due to overexpression of the *APP* gene.^{47,57} CAA is present to varying degrees in both sLOAD and sEOAD, and different forms of ADAD, highlighting its complex role in AD pathology.⁴⁷

APP is a transmembrane glycoprotein⁶¹ widely expressed in cells across various organs,⁶² including the vascular unit and the central nervous system. APP undergoes two major proteolytic processing pathways: the non-amyloidogenic pathway,^{63–65} which is the predominant route, and the amyloidogenic pathway, which leads to A β production.^{63,66} The balance between these pathways is crucial for APP metabolism and A β generation. A β is produced through the sequential cleavage of APP by two key enzymes. β -secretase (beta-site APP-cleaving enzyme 1 [BACE1]) first cleaves APP in the extracellular domain, generating membrane-bound C-terminal fragments (CTF).⁶⁷ γ -secretase then processes CTF within the membrane, producing A β peptides.⁶⁸ BACE2, a homolog of BACE1, can also cleave APP but at alternative sites, including the β' -site, resulting in shorter fragments. While BACE2 typical activity favors non-amyloidogenic processing,⁶⁹ under certain pathological conditions BACE2 can act as a conditional β -secretase.⁷⁰ A β peptides range in length up to 49 amino acids.^{49,71} A β 42 is prone to aggregation and primarily accumulates in amyloid plaques within the brain parenchyma, a hallmark of AD.⁷² In addition,

A β 40 and truncated A β peptides at both the amino and carboxy termini accumulate in blood vessels, where they are closely linked to CAA.^{49,73}

The origin of A β peptides deposited in the NVU is subject to multiple non-exclusive hypotheses. A β peptides could be: (1) produced locally by cells from the NVU, the cells proven to produce A β are the endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells,⁷⁴ and glial cells;^{75–77} (2) imported from the parenchyma for clearance through peri-vascular drainage;⁷⁸ or (3) coming from the periphery, produced in other organs^{62,79} and seeding in the NVU (Figure 2). Moreover, positive correlation between lymphatic system dysfunction and CAA severity has been found in sporadic CAA.⁸⁰ Despite extensive research, the precise mechanisms underlying A β production and aggregation in blood vessels, the specific cell types, and the distinct roles of different A β species in CAA and AD remain unclear. In fact, diagnosis of CAA in vivo remained a challenge for a long time.

4.2 | Identification of CAA in DS: *post mortem* studies

Until the late 1990s, CAA was primarily studied in *post mortem* samples from individuals with sporadic AD (sAD), including few individuals with DS.^{79,81–93} This limited number of DS samples was likely due to the challenges in obtaining them, as well as the discovery that in AD and DS, A β deposits were very similar.⁹⁴ Early studies focusing on A β considered DS similar to AD and did not differentiate them in their analyses.^{72,95–101} (Table 1). The first large comparative study was published by David M. A. Mann's group in 1989.¹⁷⁷ This study examined 44 *post mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS and highlighted the progression of A β deposition throughout the lifespan of individuals with DS, showing the vast predominance of vascular deposition after 40 years old, and paving the way for a series of influential papers with large cohorts and key discoveries.^{107,109,147,47} A few other studies also used a large number of *post mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS but did not identify any significant difference between DS and AD.^{104,105} As *post mortem* brains from individual with DS became more accessible and new research and diagnostic tools emerged, the number of studies on the molecular mechanisms and link between AD and CAA in DS increased.^{46,48}

In a paper published in 2018 by Mann's team,⁴⁷ 152 *post mortem* brain samples were used to study the pattern and severity of vascular A β in ADAD, DS, sAD, and controls. The samples were divided into six categories: 4 patients from two families with *APPdup* (three from the same family), 34 individuals with DS, 16 patients with missense mutation in the *APP* gene, 34 patients diagnosed with sEOAD, 34 diagnosed with sLOAD, and 30 elderly controls. In the paper, they separated CAA into different types including: type 1 CAA involving abundant diffuse and cored A β plaques across the cerebral cortex, with amyloid deposition restricted to leptomeningeal vessels; type 2 CAA also featuring numerous plaques, with CAA extending into both leptomeningeal and penetrating cortical arteries, particularly in the occipital cortex; and type 3, with CAA in both capillaries and arteries,

Supplementary Annexes 2: Published review

TABLE 1 Summary of articles identified through a systematic review investigating cerebrovascular risk associated with CAA in DS.

Paper	Year	Country	Type	Number of DS cases or models analyzed	Age/ age range (average or median)	Brain and surrounding tissues region
Reid and Maloney ¹⁰²	1974	UK	Case report	1	59	CCx, BG, BS, CB, WM, HC, LM, CV, CBV
Deshpande and Levine ³³	1984	USA	Case report	1	13	CB, Occ, Tmp, CP, 4V, DM, SAS, CV
Masters et al. ⁹⁴	1985	Australia	Research article	1	NS (elderly)	CCx, GM, WM, CBV
Belza and Ulrich ¹⁰³	1986	USA	Case report	1	56	NS
Coria et al. ⁹⁵	1987	USA	Research article	0*	-	CCx, WM, HC, NCx, LM, CBV, CV
Guiroy et al. ⁹⁶	1987	USA	Research article	0*	-	HC, FCx, TCx, Amg, NBM, BG, BS, CB, UCC, GM, WM, MNG, CV
Robakis et al. ⁹⁷	1987	USA	Research article	0*	-	CCx, TCx, FCx, PCx, OCx, CV
Coria et al. ⁹⁸	1988	USA	Research article	0*	-	CCx, HC, GM, CBV, Cap
Prelli et al. ⁷²	1988	USA	Research article	0*	-	CCx, LM, CV
Abraham and Potter ⁸¹	1989	USA	Review	1	NS (elderly)	GM, WM, CCx, MNG, CV, CBV, MBV
Joachim et al. ⁷⁹	1989	USA	Research article	4	25, 36, 38, 44	CCx, MNG, CV
Miyakawa and Kuramoto ⁸²	1989	Japan	Research article	1	NS	CCx, MNG, CV, Cap
Watkins et al. ¹⁰⁴	1989	UK	Research article	19	18–48 (35)	CCx, MNG, CV, Cap
Abraham et al. ⁸³	1990	USA	Research article	4	12, 35–58	GM, WM, CCx, FCx, HC, CB, BG, SN, MNG, CBV, CV
Farrar ¹⁰⁵	1990	UK	Research article	12–14	(38.4)	GM, WM, CCx, MNG, CV, Cap
Maruyama et al. ⁸⁴	1990	Japan	Research article	1	37	CCx, LM, CBV, LMV, Cap
Matsubara et al. ⁸⁵	1990	Japan	Research article	2	29, 33	Serum, CSF
Picken et al. ⁸⁶	1990	USA	Research article	1	NS	NCx, HC, Thal, BG, CB, BS, GM, WM, LM, CBV, LMV, Cap
Yoshimura et al. ¹⁰⁶	1990	Japan	Case report	1	45	CCx, HC, Amg, OB, BG, BS, CB, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Abraham et al. ⁹⁹	1991	USA	Research article	0*	-	GM, MNG, CV
Guiroy et al. ⁸⁷	1991	USA	Research article	2	59, 69	HC, Amg, CB, CCx, LM, CBV, LMV, CV
Kalaria et al. ⁸⁸	1991	USA	Research article	4	37–69 (55)	FCx, TCx, PCx, OCx, ECx, HC, PHG, BG, CB, BS, LM, Cap, CBV, CV
Mann et al. ¹⁰⁷	1992	UK	Research article	16	13–48 (36.5) 50–65 (58.4)	HC, TCx, LM, CV, CBV, LMV, Cap
Tamaoka et al. ⁸⁹	1992	USA	Research article	2	36, 38	FCx, TCx, PCx, OCx, WM, CB, BG, CBV, CV, LMV, Cap
Van Nostrand et al. ¹⁰⁰	1992	USA	Research article	0*	-	CSF
Nelson et al. ¹⁰¹	1993	USA	Research article	0*, Rat model	-	-
Ikeda et al. ¹⁰⁸	1994	Japan	Research article	7	31, 37, 38, 42, 55, 60, 62	NCx, WM, GM, LM, LMV, CBV, CV, Art, Cap
Maat-Schieman et al. ⁹¹	1994	Netherlands	Research article	1	57	GM, WM, LM, CBV, LMV, CV

(Continues)

Supplementary Annexes 2: Published review

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Paper	Year	Country	Type	Number of DS cases or models analyzed	Age/ age range (average or median)	Brain and surrounding tissues region
Maat-Schieman et al. ⁹⁰	1994	Netherlands	Research article	1	62	FCx, GM, LM, CV, CBV, Cap
Armstrong ⁹²	1995	UK	Research article	4	41–60	Tmp, Occ, PHG, PHS, HF, MNG, CV
Iwatsubo et al. ¹⁰⁹	1995	Japan	Research article	16	31–50 (39.9) >53–64 (58.5)	FCx, CCx, GM, MNG, LM, MBV, CV, CBV
Helisalimi et al. ¹¹⁰	1996	Finland	Research article	24	(35)	Blood samples
Aylett et al. ³⁴	1996	UK	Case report	1	13	CT scan and angiography
Kalaria et al. ⁹³	1996	USA	Research article	3	33, 37, 69	NCx, FCx, TCx, PCx, OCx, LM, CV
Nagasaka et al. ³⁵	1996	Japan	Case report	1	20	CV
de la Monte and Bloch ^{111]}	1997	USA	Research article	64	0–60	FCx, TCx
Kálmán et al. ¹¹²	1997	Hungary	Research article	52	(41)	Serum
Donahue et al. ¹¹³	1998	USA	Case report	2	63, 50	NCx, ECx, HC, WM, CB, BS, BG, LM, CBV, LMV, CV
Sameshima et al. ³⁶	2000	Japan	Case report	1	29	CT scan and angiography
Diab et al. ³⁷	2001	Lebanon	Case report	1	6	CT scan and angiography
Wegiel et al. ²⁹	2002	USA	Research article	23	33–72	HF, BG, CB, LM, CV, Cap, LMV
Jin et al. ¹¹⁴	2003	USA	Research article	5	45–68	TCx, NCx
Tranquilli et al. ¹¹⁵	2003	Italy	Research article	15	0 (Fetuses)	Amniotic fluids
Mazur-Kolecka et al. ¹¹⁶	2004	USA	Research article	0*	-	In vitro culture of LMV
Wegiel et al. ¹¹⁷	2004	USA	Research article	0	-	NCx, ECx, HF, BG, SN, Amg, Thal, CB, LM, CBV, LMV, CV
Frackowiak et al. ¹¹⁸	2005	USA	Research article	0*	-	FCx, LM, MNG, LMV, CBV, CV
Ichinohe et al. ¹¹⁹	2005	Japan	Research article	18	0–50	FCx, CCx, WM
Jea et al. ¹²⁰	2005	USA	Research article	16	1–29 (9.3)	FCx, PCx, OCx, WM, BG, LM, CV
Cabrejo et al. ¹²¹	2006	France	Research article	0	-	HF, ECx, FCx, CB, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap, Art
Cullen et al. ¹²²	2006	Australia	Research article	2	54,58	HC, ECx, FG, CCx, GM, WM, CBV, Cap, Art, Ven
Liu et al. ¹²³	2006	USA	Research article	10	9–53 (26.3)	FCx, TCx, OCx, CB, LM, LMV, CBV
López et al. ¹²⁴	2006	Spain	Case report	1	50	PCx, FCx, BG, Thal, ECx, HC, WM, LM, LMV, CBV, CV
Ridley et al. ¹²⁵	2006	UK	Research article	0* Primate model	-	-
Naito et al. ¹²⁶	2008	Japan	Case report	1	52	FCx, NCx, HC, GP, MNG, CBV, LMV, CV
Varga et al. ¹²⁷	2008	Hungary	Research article	31	1–25 (5)	Serum
Vorbodt et al. ¹²⁸	2008	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Eger et al. ³⁸	2009	Germany	Case report	1	4	MRI and CT scan
Minami et al. ¹²⁹	2009	Japan	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Prasad et al. ³⁹	2009	India	Case report	1	0.5	MRI and CT scan

(Continues)

Supplementary Annexes 2: Published review

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Paper	Year	Country	Type	Number of DS cases or models analyzed	Age/ age range (average or median)	Brain and surrounding tissues region
Ramakrishna et al. ¹³⁰	2009	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Van Rooden et al. ¹³¹	2009	Netherlands	Research article	2	49,62	Fr, Occ, WM, LM, CBV, LMV, Cap
Mendel et al. ¹³²	2010	Poland	Case report	1	54	Fr, Occ, HC, NCx, LM, CV, CBV, MBV
Rutgers et al. ¹³³	2011	Netherlands	Research article	Cellular model	-	-
Sabbagh ¹³⁴	2011	USA	Case report	1	55	FCx, TCx, PCx, Amg, HC, PHG, Thal, SN, BG, CB, BS, LM, CV, CBV, LMV
Bell et al. ¹³⁵	2012	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Moro et al. ¹³⁶	2012	Italy	Research article	4	31, 39, 46, 55	FCx, NCx, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Moguel-Ancheita et al. ¹³⁷	2012	Mexico	Research article	4	NS	Ocular/Orbital Structures
Frost et al. ¹³⁸	2013	USA	Research article	3	47, 55, 46	FCx, TCx, HF, CV
Granic and Potter ¹³⁹	2013	USA	Research article	Mouse and cellular model	-	-
Nabuurs et al. ¹⁴⁰	2013	Netherlands	Research article	1	31	TCx, NCx, GM, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Zhang et al. ¹⁴¹	2013	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
O'Callaghan et al. ¹⁴²	2014	Sweden	Research article	3	61, 70, 80	HF, LM, CBV, LMV, Cap, CV
Jastrzębski et al. ¹⁴³	2015	Poland	Case report	1	60	BG, Occ, WM, CCx, LM, CV
Carmona-Iragui et al. ⁴⁵	2017	Spain	Research article	117	(49.1)	CCx, Occ, Par, Fr, Tmp, HF, LM, LMV, CBV, CV
Drachman et al. ¹⁴⁴	2017	USA	Research article	5	(59.6)	NCx, HC, CB, BG, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Head et al. ⁴⁶	2017	USA	Research article	32	(55.2)	FCx, TCx, PCx, OCx, Thal, BG, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
LeVine et al. ¹⁴⁵	2017	USA	Research article	39	1–66 (44.1)	FCx, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Brandicourt et al. ¹⁴⁶	2018	France	Case report	0	-	-
Davidson et al. ¹⁴⁷	2018	UK	Research article	56	0–76 (48)	FCx, TCx, HC, OCx, CB, SN, LC, BS, BG, FG, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap, CV
Mann et al. ⁴⁷	2018	UK	Research article	28	36–69 (58.7)	FCx, TCx, OCx, CB, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Allach El Khattabi et al. ¹⁴⁸	2019	France	Research article	Mouse and cellular model	-	-
Cho et al. ¹⁴⁹	2019	South Korea	Research article	Zebrafish model	-	-
Raha-Chowdhury et al. ¹⁵⁰	2019	UK	Research article	47	(50)	FCx, TCx, HC, ECx, BG, OB, CP, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Schoeppe et al. ¹⁵¹	2019	Germany	Research article	12	(5)	Fr, Par, Tmp, Occ, BG, Thal, WM, BS, CB, LM, LMV, CBV, CV
Yanai et al. ¹⁵²	2019	Japan	Case report	1	53	Fr, Par, Tmp, WM, CCx, LM, CV, LMV
Guedj et al. ¹⁵³	2020	USA	Research article	7	0	Amniocytes from fetuses

(Continues)

Supplementary Annexes 2: Published review

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Paper	Year	Country	Type	Number of DS cases or models analyzed	Age/ age range (average or median)	Brain and surrounding tissues region
Kumar et al. ¹⁵⁴	2020	Germany	Research article	3		CCx, Fr, Par, Tmp, LM, CBV, LMV
Lao et al. ¹⁵⁵	2020	USA	Research article	138	(50)	Fr, Par, Tmp, Occ, BG, CCx, LM, LMV, CV
Byworth et al. ¹⁵⁶	2021	Canada	Case report	1	56	Fr, Par, Tmp, BG, CB, DM, CV
Pivtoraiko et al. ¹⁵⁷	2021	USA	Research article	18	43–63 (53.2)	FCx, PreC, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Raha et al. ¹⁵⁸	2021	UK	Research article	47	52–76 (60)	NCx, MTG, HC, CC, CP, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Nakamura et al. ¹⁵⁹	2021	Japan	Case report/ review	1	19	Occ, Par, BG, DM, LM, CV
Ishihara ¹⁶⁰	2021	Japan	Research article	Mouse model	-	NCx, CCx, VZ, SVZ, CBV
Aranha et al. ¹⁶¹	2022	Spain	Case report	1	59	Tmp, Occ, CB, OCx, CCx, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Ichimata et al. ¹⁶²	2022	Canada	Research article	11	38–66 (54.7)	FCx, TCx, PCx, ACC, HC, Amg, BG, Thal, CB, BS LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Huang et al. ¹⁶³	2023	China	Case report	1	19	CCx, Ventr, LMV, CV
Kreutzer et al. ¹⁶⁴	2023	USA	Research article	4	47, 57, 49, 55	FCx, CCx, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Mukamel et al. ¹⁶⁵	2023	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Seol et al. ¹⁶⁶	2023	South Korea	Research article	73	0–40 (11.3)	HC, CCx
Yamamoto et al. ¹⁶⁷	2023	Japan	Case report	1	13	Tmp, Thal, Ventr, Occ, DM, LM, CV
Aranha et al. ¹⁶⁸	2024	Spain	Research article	195	(44.4)	Par, Fr, Tmp, Occ, WM, LM, CBV, LMV, Art
Casado-Naranjo et al. ¹⁶⁹	2024	Spain	Case report	1	44	Fr, Par, CCx, CB, WM, LM, LMV, CBV, CV
Choi et al. ¹⁷⁰	2024	USA	Research article	Mouse model	-	-
Edwards et al. ¹⁷¹	2024	USA	Research article	185	(45.2)	WM, Blood samples
Kasri et al. ⁴⁹	2024	France	Research article	12	(48.7)	FCx, HC, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Lao et al. ¹⁷²	2024	USA	Research article	242	25–72 (45.1)	Fr, Par, Tmp, Occ, BG, WM, LM, LMV, CV
Liu et al. ¹⁷³	2024	USA	Research article	15	43–68 (56.6)	FCx, TCx, PCxn HC, LM, LMV, CBV, Cap
Morcillo-Nieto et al. ¹⁷⁴	2024	Spain	Research article	261	(46.96)	WM, Fr, Par, Tmp, Occ, BG, CC, Thal, CV
Rizvi et al. ¹⁷⁵	2024	USA	Research article	195	(50.6)	Fr, Par, Occ, Tmp, WM, HC, CV
Uygun et al. ¹⁷⁶	2024	Turkey	Case report	0	-	-
Zsadanyi et al. ⁵⁰	2024	Spain	Research article	276		Fr, Par, Tmp, Occ, CB, LM, LMV, CBV, CV

Note: The table includes the number of cases analyzed in each study (or, when applicable, the model studied), the age when available (age, age range, mean, or median), and the cerebrovascular region studied, with the exception of a few studies for which only CSF or blood samples were analyzed. The list of regions has been harmonized for readability and comparability across studies. In certain instances, regional names have been simplified and some detailed anatomical distinctions omitted to limit the use of abbreviations. 0*: DS was mentioned as similar to AD but no actual cases were used in the paper.

Abbreviations: 4V, fourth ventricle; ACC, anterior cingulate cortex; AD, Alzheimer's disease; Amg, amygdala; Art, arteriole; BG, basal ganglia (including the striatum, putamen, caudatoputamen, caudate nucleus, globus pallidus, and the nucleus accumbens); BS, brainstem (including the medulla oblongata, pons, and midbrain); Cap, capillaries; CB, cerebellum; CBV, cortical blood vessels; CC, corpus callosum; CCx, cerebral cortex; CP, choroid plexus; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; CV, general meningeal/cerebral vessels; DM, dura mater; DS, Down syndrome; ECx, entorhinal cortex; FCx, frontal cortex; FG, fusiform gyrus; Fr, frontal lobe; GM, gray matter; HC, hippocampus; HF, hippocampal formation (including the cornu ammonis); LC, locus coeruleus; LM, leptomeninges; LMV, leptomeningeal blood vessels; MBV, meningeal blood vessels; MNG, meninges; MO, medulla oblongata; MTG, mid-temporal gyrus; NBM, nucleus basalis of meynert; NCx, neocortex; Occ, occipital lobe; NS, not specified; OB, olfactory bulb; OCx, occipital cortex; Par, parietal lobe; PCx, parietal cortex; PHG, parahippocampal gyrus; PHS, parahippocampal sulcus; PreC, precuneus cortex; SAS, subarachnoid space; SN, substantia nigra; SVZ, subventricular zone; TCx, temporal cortex; Thal, thalamus; Tmp, temporal lobe; UCC, upper cervical cord; Ven, venules; Ventr, ventricular system; VZ, ventricular zone; WM, white matter.

FIGURE 2 Hypothesis of the origin of A β peptides in CAA. A β peptides could be (1) produced locally by cells from the vascular unit, (2) imported from the parenchyma for clearance, or (3) coming from the periphery, produced in other organs. A β , amyloid beta; CAA, cerebral amyloid angiopathy.

especially in the primary visual cortex, but accompanied by relatively few A β plaques. This major study led to numerous results. First, amyloid plaques were more abundant both in DS and missense *APP* mutations compared to sEOAD and sLOAD cases, while there was no significant difference between sEOAD and sLOAD. Second, the severity of CAA was significantly higher in *APP*dup and missense *APP* mutations, as well as in DS, compared to sAD. Third, in DS, sLOAD, and controls, type 1 CAA was significantly more predominant compared to types 2 and 3. However, in *APP*dup, type 3 was the principal CAA phenotype. In summary, their study suggested that missense *APP* mutation, *APP*dup, and DS are associated with the most severe CAA compared to sAD and controls. Additionally, the study highlighted regional differences between *APP*dup and DS, with higher frequency of type 3 CAA in *APP*dup, mainly located in the visual cortex, by opposition to DS diffuse distribution across cortical and leptomeningeal vessels throughout the brain, higher type 1, and similar proportion of type 2 and 3 CAA. Thus, despite their shared characteristic of having three copies of the *APP* gene, other genes on chromosome 21 may influence CAA pattern and A β deposition. However, one crucial limit to this study was the low number of *APP*dup cases due to the rare occurrence of this genetic disease.

In a more recent study from the team,⁴⁹ 51 *post mortem* brain samples were analyzed, with 15 samples from aged-matched controls, 11 with sAD, 6 with *APP* point mutations, 7 with *APP*dup from 6 families, 8 from individuals with DS with AD neuropathology (DSAD), and

7 from individuals with DS but no AD. By performing immunostaining of A β on cortical sections, we found that A β deposits were present in a small quantity in the parenchyma but absent from the blood vessels in the four cases with DS without AD, while deposits were present in the parenchyma and in blood vessels of DSAD cases. This suggested that a threshold of A β in the parenchyma might be required to develop CAA. However, in samples with *APP*dup, despite the massive amyloid deposits in the blood vessels, parenchymal A β levels were similar to those observed in DS without AD. Overall, these results suggest that individuals with DS are protected against CAA compared to those with *APP*dup, which could imply the presence of protective mechanisms due to the overexpression of genes from chromosome 21.

4.3 | Imaging CAA in DS in vivo

The diagnosis of CAA has evolved significantly with advancements in biomarkers and imaging techniques. Historically, CAA could only be confirmed *post mortem* through histopathological examination of amyloid deposits in cerebral vessels.¹⁷⁸ The introduction of the Boston criteria in the 1990s allowed for the diagnosis of probable CAA in living patients using brain imaging, moving the diagnostic process from *post mortem* examination to clinical settings.¹⁷⁸ Furthermore, imaging modalities such as susceptibility-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and amyloid positron emission tomography (PET) now enable

in vivo detection of characteristic hemorrhagic and amyloid deposition patterns.^{145,179,180} MRI, particularly using T2*-weighted gradient echo or susceptibility weighted imaging, reveals microbleeds which are key radiological markers supporting the Boston criteria for probable CAA.^{50,168}

A meta-analysis on case reports suggested that in individuals with DS, the occurrence of intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) may be greatly reduced compared to APPdup by nearly 10 times.¹⁸¹ However, a later study found that while a reduction is present, it is less significant than initially estimated, but remains 2-fold.⁴⁵ Interestingly two individuals with DS and ICH detected on MRI showed no clinical symptoms of ICH.⁴⁵ Furthermore, individuals with DS appeared to have significantly more lobar microbleeds than EOAD patients, as in other forms of ADAD. In a later study, individuals with DS were also found to have significantly more microbleeds than controls, without impacting cognitive performance.⁵⁰

5 | BIOMARKERS OF CAA

CAA exhibits a unique cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarker profile compared to healthy control (HC) and AD patients.^{182,183} Specifically, CSF A β_{40} levels are reduced in CAA relative to both HCs and AD patients, whereas tau and phosphorylated tau (p-tau) levels are elevated in CAA compared to HCs but remain lower than those observed in those with AD.^{182,183} These biomarkers offer potential non-invasive diagnostic alternatives, especially in at-risk populations such as individuals with DS.¹⁸⁴⁻¹⁸⁶ In a recent study investigating the A β peptides signature associated with CAA in *post mortem* brain samples,⁴⁹ we observed that in the insoluble fraction derived from the cortex and hippocampus of patients, N-terminally truncated peptides terminating at positions 37, 38, 39, and 40 exhibited the strongest positive correlations with CAA. Conversely, peptides ending at amino acids 42 and 43, along with their pyroglutamylated forms, were found to exhibit significant negative correlations with CAA severity. A recent study involving patients with sporadic and hereditary CAA indicated that the level of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) in the CSF might serve as an early marker for CAA.¹⁸⁷ However, another study found similar GFAP levels between patients with sporadic CAA and controls subjects¹⁸⁶ indicating that additional investigation is needed to establish GFAP as reliable biomarker for CAA.

Another direction to find plasma biomarkers was tested in a recent study using machine learning algorithms to develop and assess the performance of plasma biomarkers identified using proteomic analyses.¹⁸⁸ A panel of 146 individuals with probable CAA and 128 controls were prospectively enrolled and a total of 166 differentially expressed proteins were identified in patients with CAA. Six hub proteins were selected to construct a circulating panel, which demonstrated strong performance in distinguishing patients from controls across all cohorts: Pro-CTSH, the inactive precursor of cathepsin H, emerged as the most influential across three independent cohorts; USP15, a deubiquitinating enzyme implicated in the regulation of type I interferon signaling and neuroinflammation; ApoA-IV plays a key role in lipopro-

tein metabolism and plasma lipid transport; PREP, serine peptidase that hydrolyzes proline-containing peptides; Fibulin-5, an extracellular matrix protein essential for elastic fiber assembly and cell adhesion; and RNase 4, a member of the RNase A superfamily, with undefined biological role. Although no direct protein-protein interactions have been identified among these candidates, they are suggested to converge on shared pathogenic pathways including A β production and clearance, vascular remodeling, neuroinflammation, and oxidative stress, all central to CAA pathophysiology. Furthermore, the risk stratification system based on the hub protein panel effectively identified individuals at high risk for new-onset lobar ICH. Altogether, the study uncovered distinct circulating protein profiles associated with CAA and developed a validated hub protein panel to support CAA screening and risk stratification. The integration of these tools should improve early detection, risk stratification, and potential therapeutic monitoring of CAA.¹⁸⁹

6 | ROLE OF THE BLOOD-BRAIN BARRIER IN CAA

The blood-brain barrier (BBB) is known to play a crucial role in the clearance of A β in AD, and emerging evidence suggests that BBB dysfunction may occur early in the disease, impairing A β clearance and promoting its accumulation.¹⁹⁰ This may create a vicious cycle contributing to both AD and CAA.¹⁹¹ However, the precise relationship between BBB dysfunction and CAA remains poorly understood, particularly in DSAD, in which ICH and microbleeds appear to be less frequent than expected compared to APPdup, despite the common genetic factor of an additional APP copy (see section 3.3, Figure 3). Similarly, CAA in DS is below the expected level due to APP overexpression (see section 3.2), further challenging our understanding of the role of the BBB in DSAD and CAA. It suggests that there may be protective mechanisms, potentially linked to genes or regulatory elements on chromosome 21, that influence A β deposition in the NVU. Our current knowledge is that under normal conditions, A β is cleared through enzymatic degradation, perivascular drainage, and transport across the BBB via low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 1 (LRP1).^{192,193}

Research on CAA and the BBB dysfunction in DS still faces several limitations. *Post mortem* studies provide valuable insights into vascular pathology but fail to capture dynamic changes in BBB integrity over time, limiting their applicability to disease progression. In addition, intense lipofuscin and rapid RNA degradation in *post mortem* samples limit their use for immunofluorescence staining and RNAseq analysis, respectively. In vivo imaging techniques, such as dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI and PET, offer real-time assessment of BBB permeability but often lack the resolution to detect subtle molecular alterations.^{194,195} Nevertheless, intra-arterial injection and the long acquisition time could be difficult to apply to individuals with DS. Additionally, CSF biomarker studies are constrained by the invasive nature of lumbar punctures, reducing their feasibility for large-scale studies,¹⁹⁶ especially in individuals with DS. Blood biomarkers could represent a more feasible alternative to CSF biomarkers in DS.

FIGURE 3 Comparative overview of CAA-related features across different conditions. The schematic summarizes key vascular pathologies in elderly control individuals (Ctrl) and individuals with DS, sAD, DSAD, and APPdup. CAA frequency progressively increases from Ctrl and DS to sAD, DSAD, and APPdup,^{46-49,248} with severity following a similar trend, from controls exhibiting milder CAA, to APPdup presenting severe CAA. Frequencies of ICH^{28,45,181,249} and microbleeds^{45,50,248,249} parallel CAA patterns. BBB integrity is poorly characterized, but available data suggest a general decline in sAD relative to controls, with substantial interindividual variability likely influenced by age, genetic background, and other factors¹⁹⁰ and with very limited information on DS individuals.¹⁹⁷ Detailed references are provided in Table S2 in supporting information. These comparisons should be interpreted with caution, as there are few studies including all groups—particularly young individuals with DS without AD, and those with APPdup—and due to age variability, especially in control groups. APPdup, amyloid precursor protein gene microduplication; BBB, blood-brain barrier; CAA, cerebral amyloid angiopathy; DS, Down syndrome; DSAD, Down syndrome with Alzheimer's disease; ICH, intracerebral hemorrhage; sAD, sporadic Alzheimer's disease.

7 | BBB INTEGRITY IN DS

To the best of our knowledge, the sole cross-sectional peer-reviewed study investigating BBB integrity in DS is the one conducted by Mann's team in 1992, in which they used lectin histochemistry to investigate brain microvessels in *post mortem* samples from the hippocampus of individuals with DS. The study included control brains from individuals aged 20 ($n = 4$), 40 ($n = 5$), 60 ($n = 6$), and 80 ($n = 5$) years, as well as brains from patients with AD ($n = 23$), and individuals with DS < 50 years of age ($n = 8$) and > 50 years old ($n = 9$).¹⁰⁷ They found that in AD and in individuals with DS > 50 years, the binding of lectins e-PHA, L-PHA, and PAA was elevated beyond what would be expected due to normal aging. Additionally, binding of lectins *Ulex europaeus* agglutinin 1 (UEA-1) and *Bandeiraea simplicifolia* lectin (BSA-I_{B4}) was increased in AD but not in DS. Individuals with DS < 50 years old showed no binding changes beyond those associated with normal aging. These specific increases observed in AD and DS may reflect disease-related alterations in the basement membrane (BM) and could suggest impaired BBB function or integrity. If so, it would suggest that young individuals with DS have no BBB integrity issues but develop them with aging probably due the deposition of A β . Furthermore, the lack of increase of UEA-1 and BSA-I_{B4} in DS compared to AD may indicate relatively fewer integrity issues in DS compared to AD. Most of the current understanding of BBB integrity in DS is based on indirect evidence, including signs of vascular abnormalities and an increased vulnerability to neurodegenerative conditions such as CAA and AD. By assuming a direct link among CAA, ICH, and BBB integrity, one could hypothesize that the observed lower incidence of ICH^{45,181} and reduced CAA^{49,147} burden in DS compared to individuals with APPdup could suggest that the BBB in DS may be relatively more resilient than in APPdup cases.

A recent cross-sectional proteomic analysis of CSF from individuals with DS revealed an increase in plasma proteins more than a decade before estimated year of onset (EYO), suggesting potential BBB leakage.¹⁹⁷ Interestingly, lactadherin, known as the precursor of medin which co-aggregates with vascular A β ¹⁹⁸ and is a marker associated with CAA in the CSF,¹⁹⁹ was found to be decreased > 20 years before EYO.¹⁹⁷ This suggests that BBB leakage could potentially be a secondary effect of CAA.

While some *post mortem* analyses and *in vivo* imaging studies suggest BBB dysfunction in DS, there is a significant gap in research, particularly regarding in-depth mechanistic studies and longitudinal analyses in living individuals. More studies using advanced imaging techniques, CSF biomarker analysis, and *in vitro* BBB models derived from cells of individuals with DS are needed to fully characterize the extent and consequences of BBB alterations in DS.

8 | NEW RESEARCH TOOLS FOR STUDYING CAA AND THE BBB

Cellular models, such as those developed from induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), offer valuable mechanistic insights. However, they might not completely mimic the intricate relationship between the various cell types within the NVU. Despite this limitation, they remain essential to the investigation of brain cell types that are typically inaccessible. Mono- and co-cultures of iPSC-derived cells can serve as *in vitro* BBB models. Besides evaluating the functionality of the BBB under specific conditions, through methods such as Transwell assays²⁰⁰ or transepithelial/transendothelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements,²⁰¹ these techniques can also play a crucial role investigating drug delivery mechanism to the brain.²⁰² The

TABLE 2 Overview of commonly used mouse model of CAA, with associated mutations and CAA onset.

Model	Mutations/design	CAA onset
APPDutch ²²²	APP mutation Dutch (E693Q)	22–25 months
Tg-SwDI ²²³	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), Dutch (E693Q), Iowa (D694N)	3 months
5xFAD ²²⁴	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), Florida (I716V), London (V717I) and PSEN1 mutations M146L and L286V	3 months
APP23 ^{225,226}	APP mutations Swedish (K670N/M671L), London (V717I)	8–10 months
APP/Ld ²²⁷	APP mutation London (V717I)	15–24 months

Note: This is not an exhaustive list.

Abbreviations: APP, amyloid precursor protein; CAA, cerebral amyloid angiopathy.

Transwell model serves as an *in vitro* method to study the permeability and transport of molecules through biological membranes. It typically comprises two compartments separated by a semi-permeable membrane that supports cell culture. TEER is a quantitative measure of the resistance to current flow across a cell monolayer, providing insights into tight junctions' integrity.

Developing organoids from individuals with DS-derived cells can resolve some of the 2D culture limitations by integrating cell type interactions and 3D configuration. Cerebral organoids are now widely studied and protocols to generate specific brain regions have been developed²⁰³ which can even recapitulate AD phenotype.^{204,205} In addition, the recent development of vascular organoids²⁰⁶ allowed the generation of cerebrovascular organoids that potentially re-create the interaction between specific brain regions and the NVU.^{207–212}

Mouse models have been developed to better reflect *in vivo* pathophysiology for investigating the mechanisms of DS,²¹³ but with several limitations. Human chromosome 21q genes are orthologous to segments from three mouse chromosomes, the 16th, 17th, and 10th. Most mouse models have only a portion of the orthologous chromosome 21 duplicated genes, potentially not representing all complex genetic interactions. In addition, mice modeling DS do not produce A β plaques even with a humanized APP gene,²¹⁴ unless the APP gene carries specific mutations present in ADAD.^{215,216} Nevertheless, as every model has its own strengths and limitations, mouse models remain crucial in DS research due to their ability to mimic key genetic features, provide controlled environments for studying disease progression, and facilitate long-term, longitudinal studies. In the context of CAA, mouse models can be used to study BBB permeability and A β clearance.^{217–221} Table 2 provides a list of mouse models with CAA. While mice remain the most common model for DS research, a variety of animal models including rats,²¹³ zebrafish,¹⁴⁹ and primates¹²⁵ offer complementary insights into the genetic, developmental, and cognitive aspects of DS.

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) is now an established technique for investigating biological mechanisms at both the cellular

and molecular levels. When combined with vessel enrichment protocols, it has enabled the creation of a detailed atlas of the human NVU.^{228–230} While this approach has not yet been applied to individuals with DS, it has already been used in sAD to identify genes positively and negatively associated with CAA.²³¹ Moreover, advances in spatial transcriptomic technologies have allowed for even higher resolution analyses, enabling researchers to assess how proximity to A β deposits affects the transcriptomes of different cell types.²³² These emerging techniques will be essential for investigating CAA in individuals with DS and for understanding its impact on the various cell types that make up the BBB.

9 | CURRENT THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES FOR CAA

Individuals with DS represent the largest population group with EOAD but they have been largely under-studied and were initially excluded from clinical trials. This exclusion can be attributed to various factors including enrollment challenges, broad exclusion criteria, regulation concerning informed consent for individuals with intellectual disabilities, and overly cautious institutional review boards.²³³ In the last decades, the inclusion of individuals with DS in trials has greatly improved. The review of Alldred *et al.*²³³ summed up many trials with DS persons to prevent or reduce cognitive impairment and decline.²³⁴ Several trials are now focusing on AD in DS²³⁵ such as the Amyloid Lowering for Alzheimer's in Down's with Donanemab Investigation (ALADDIN NCT06911944) presented during the Alzheimer's Association International Conference in 2024; the A β ATE study (NCT05462106), a recent phase 1 clinical trial for a vaccine against A β ; and the HERO study (NCT06673069), to evaluate the safety and tolerability of ION269, an antisense oligonucleotide designed to reduce the expression of the APP gene. In the A β ATE study, the vaccine effectively induced an immune response, promoting the production of A β antibodies without any adverse effect, which is promising for its potential therapeutic applications. Further optimization and trials will be necessary to fully explore the therapeutic potential to treat neurological disorders associated with A β .²³⁶

There is currently no effective treatment for CAA in the general population, as well as in the context of DS. Current potential treatments are focused on targeting the formation and deposition of A β at various stages.^{237–239} A study conducted by Head's team revealed that lecanemab, a monoclonal antibody targeting soluble A β protofibrils, binds to vascular A β in *post mortem* brain samples from individuals with DS. This finding suggests that lecanemab may have potential therapeutic effect on both parenchymal and vascular A β deposits.¹⁷³ However, removing A β from already deteriorating vessels could lead to complications such as amyloid related imaging abnormalities-hemorrhages (ARIA-H) and ARIA-edema (ARIA-E)^{196,240} and in some cases are fatal.²⁴¹

Alternative stroke recovery therapies can be implemented, with participation in a physical exercise program, a safe and effective approach to regain pre-stroke levels of cardiorespiratory fitness and

functional mobility.²⁴² Botulinum toxin (BoNT) may help visual rehabilitation for patients with cerebral damages due to cerebrovascular stroke in DS.¹³⁷ By temporarily inhibiting acetylcholine release at the neuromuscular junction, BoNT can reduce overactivity in extraocular muscles, thereby correcting strabismus and improving ocular alignment. This can enhance binocular vision, support visual relearning, and facilitate engagement with rehabilitation strategies that rely on intact visual processing. Additionally, by alleviating abnormal muscle tone or facial dystonia, BoNT can improve visual field use and facial symmetry, both of which are relevant in post-stroke recovery. Given that individuals with DS are predisposed to both cerebrovascular events and pre-existing visual impairments, BoNT could be a valuable therapy in neurorehabilitation strategies.

A recent study found a link between pulse pressure and dementia in DS.¹⁷⁵ Higher pulse pressure was found to be associated with increased white matter hyperintensity (WMH) volumes, particularly in the global, parietal, and occipital regions. However, no significant association was observed between pulse pressure and enlarged perivascular spaces, cerebral microbleeds, or infarcts. However, a larger volume of WMH is linked to increased neurodegeneration and dementia. Therefore, a potential preventive therapy could focus on reducing pulse pressure in individuals with elevated levels.

A novel therapeutic approach involves the transient opening of the BBB to improve drug delivery to the brain.²⁴³ The BBB serves as a selective filter, protecting the brain from harmful substances while permitting essential nutrients to pass through. This selectivity, however, complicates the delivery of drugs intended to treat neurological disorders. In a review from 2023, Niazi²⁴³ discusses emerging non-invasive strategies to enhance drug delivery to the brain, such as focused ultrasound with microbubbles, transcranial magnetic stimulation, nanoparticles, and intranasal methods. These techniques aim to overcome the challenges posed by the BBB and improve the treatment of AD, Parkinson's disease, and DS.

10 | RESEARCH GAPS AND EMERGING TOPICS

This review underscores a significant gap in our understanding of BBB integrity in DS, both in the context of CAA and AD, and in younger individuals. While evidence suggests a potential link between CAA and BBB dysfunction with potential protective factors limiting this dysfunction in DS, the exact mechanisms remain elusive. Historically, this research gap may have stemmed from limited access to appropriate tools for mechanistic and *in vivo* investigations of the BBB. However, recent advancements in neuroimaging techniques, such as high-resolution MRI, and molecular approaches like scRNA-seq, have brought us closer to answering these critical questions.

To bridge this gap, future research should leverage longitudinal, multimodal imaging combined with advanced CSF and blood-based biomarkers to monitor BBB alterations over time. The development of non-invasive BBB permeability assays, including blood-based markers of endothelial dysfunction and novel MRI contrast agents, holds promise for earlier detection of BBB impairment. Additionally,

emerging models and techniques now enable the study of previously underexplored aspects, such as the distinct roles of endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells, pericytes, and perivascular macrophages, among others, in BBB regulation. Furthermore, key molecular pathways, including inflammation,^{244,245} oxidative stress,^{116,246} vascular remodeling,²⁴⁷ and amyloid clearance, warrant deeper investigation to understand their contributions to BBB dysfunction in DS. Addressing these research gaps will be essential for developing targeted therapeutic strategies aimed at preserving BBB integrity and mitigating cerebrovascular pathology in DS while potentially finding protective factors against CAA on chromosome 21.

11 | CONCLUSION

Individuals with DS exhibit a heightened vulnerability to cerebrovascular pathologies across their lifespan, from early-life MMD to late-onset CAA and AD. The overlap between these conditions underscores a complex interplay of genetic, molecular, and vascular factors, many of which remain poorly understood. While significant progress has been made in understanding A β metabolism and deposition in DS, questions persist regarding the role of the BBB in CAA pathogenesis, particularly in DSAD, in which ICH and microbleeds appear less frequently than expected, especially compared to APPdup (Figure 3). Emerging research suggests that additional genetic factors on chromosome 21 may confer a degree of protection, necessitating further investigation.

The current understanding of BBB integrity in DS remains incomplete, with limited direct studies and much of the evidence being inferred from related vascular and neurodegenerative processes. While *post mortem* and *in vivo* studies suggest that BBB dysfunction emerges with aging and amyloid pathology, there is still a need for more longitudinal and mechanistic research. The lower incidence of ICH and potentially greater BBB resilience in DS compared to APP duplication cases raises intriguing questions about protective mechanisms that require further exploration. Advancements in neuroimaging, biomarker analysis, and patient-derived cellular models offer promising avenues to fill these gaps. Future research should prioritize integrating these approaches to better characterize BBB alterations in DS, particularly in younger individuals, and to identify factors that contribute to both vulnerability and resilience. A deeper understanding of these mechanisms could not only improve our knowledge of DS-related neurodegeneration but also inform therapeutic strategies aimed at preserving BBB function and mitigating cerebrovascular pathology.

The development of advanced imaging modalities, biomarkers, and experimental models, ranging from transgenic mice to iPSC-derived vascular models, has provided unprecedented opportunities to study the mechanisms of CAA in DS and AD. However, despite these advancements, therapeutic options remain limited. Current efforts to target amyloid accumulation have shown promise but also raise concerns regarding treatment-associated complications such as ARIAs. Future research should focus on improving early detection through non-invasive BBB permeability assays, identifying protective factors

unique to DS, and exploring novel therapeutic strategies such as transient BBB opening to enhance drug delivery. With the increasing inclusion of individuals with DS in clinical trials, their unique perspectives on AD and CAA could ultimately provide benefits to the wider population at risk for these devastating neurovascular conditions.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. Author disclosures are available in the [supporting information](#).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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Supplementary Annexes

Supplementary Annex 3: Manuscript in Preparation (Not yet submitted)

Cerebral amyloid angiopathy-related functional properties of iPSC-derived endothelial cells with Trisomy 21.

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Abstract

Down syndrome (DS) is the most prevalent chromosomal abnormality linked to intellectual disability and is characterized by an extra copy of chromosome 21. This genetic condition leads to a variety of clinical features, including a heightened risk of Alzheimer's disease (AD) in their 40s, a condition referred to as DSAD. DSAD exhibits distinct clinical and biological differences compared to sporadic AD and autosomal dominant AD (ADAD).

This study investigates the integrity of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) in DS and its potential role in cerebrovascular amyloid angiopathy (CAA). Using human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) derived from individuals with DS and with *APP* duplication (*APPdup*), we differentiated endothelial cells (ECs) to model the BBB. Our analysis included morphological comparisons, secretion of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) peptides, gene expression profiling, and permeability assays.

Key findings indicate that ECs from individuals with DS exhibited increased secretion of $A\beta_{40}$ and $A\beta_{42}$ peptides, altered cell morphology with increased cell size, and enhanced barrier integrity compared to controls. In contrast, *APPdup* ECs showed compromised barrier function and distinct gene expression profiles. Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) and weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) revealed significant differences in biological pathways between DS and *APPdup* ECs, highlighting the unique transcriptional landscape in DS that may contribute to its relative protection against CAA.

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Introduction

Down syndrome (DS) is the most common chromosomal abnormality associated with intellectual disability¹. The presence of an extra copy of chromosome 21 (Chr21) genes leads to a complex set of characteristics, including an increased risk of cardiac malformations, obesity, diabetes, gastrointestinal issues, thyroid dysfunction, vision and hearing impairments, hematologic defects, obstructive sleep apnea, and recurrent infections². Additionally, individuals with DS face a high risk of developing Alzheimer's disease (AD) in their 40's³. It was recently proposed that AD in individuals with DS (DSAD) could be considered an autosomal dominant AD (ADAD)⁴. However, DSAD exhibits differences from sporadic AD and ADAD, both clinically and biologically. Notably, the level of tau pathology, a key neuropathological feature of AD, is more pronounced in DSAD compared to AD and ADAD^{5,6}.

The composition of amyloid- β (A β) plaques, another key neuropathological feature of AD, varies in individuals with DSAD compared to ADAD or AD⁷. In addition to A β accumulation in the brain parenchyma, pathological A β deposits can also be found in the walls of cerebral vessels, including arteries and arterioles, and less frequently in capillaries and veins, leading to cerebrovascular amyloid angiopathy (CAA)⁸⁻¹⁰. Recently, we conducted a comparative analysis of CAA across sporadic AD, DS, DSAD, and ADAD with three genomic copies of the *APP* locus (*APPdup*). Our findings indicate that i) CAA is almost absent in DS; ii) CAA is less frequent in sporadic AD compared to DSAD and *APPdup*; iii) CAA is more severe in *APPdup* compared to DSAD, despite both conditions involving similar APP overexpression⁶. These results suggest that individuals with DS may possess genetic factors that protect them from CAA.

Additionally, we observed differences in the composition of A β peptides in DSAD and *APPdup* compared to sporadic AD. We found higher levels of truncated A β peptides at both the N-terminus (A β_{2N-X} and A β_{4N-X}) and the C-terminus (A β_{34} to A β_{40}), which were found to be enriched in blood vessel deposits. We also detected elevated levels of A β_{17} to A β_{19} ⁶.

It remains unclear whether these specific peptides are produced or degraded locally within the neurovascular unit (NVU). However, it is established that endothelial cells¹¹, smooth muscle cells¹², and glial cells¹³⁻¹⁵ can generate A $\beta_{40/42}$ peptides, and that A β_{42} has harmful effects on these cells. Additionally, it is well-documented that CAA can compromise the integrity of the blood-brain barrier (BBB), leading to microbleeds and intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH)¹⁶.

In this context, individuals with DSAD exhibit more microbleeds than controls but fewer instances of ICH compared to those with *APPdup*¹⁷. This suggests that ICH is less frequent than expected in DSAD relative to other forms of AD, despite a similar prevalence of microbleeds¹⁸. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no direct studies of the BBB in DS published to date.

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Alterations in basal membrane proteins have been observed in DSAD but not in DS, indicating that younger individuals with DS may not have BBB integrity issues but develop them with aging, likely due to A β deposition¹⁹. Recent proteomic analyses of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from individuals with DS have identified dysregulation in extracellular matrix pathways and plasma proteins related to BBB dysfunction²⁰.

Overall, individuals with DS appear to be somehow protected from CAA. Whether this protection is due to inherent differences in the BBB within this population remains unknown.

To investigate the integrity of the BBB in DS, its potential role in CAA, and to compare these findings with those in *APPdup*, we analysed endothelial cells (ECs), which form the first monolayer of cells of the BBB, derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs). We utilized commercial hiPSC clones with trisomy 21 and its isogenic control, as well as *APPdup* hiPSCs and generated its isogenic control.

We compared the morphology of hiPSC-ECs and secretion of A β peptides using ELISA and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LCMS). We also examined gene expression profiles through differential expression analysis, gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) and weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA). Additionally, we compared our findings to single-nucleus RNA sequencing (snRNAseq) data from the literature, obtained from *postmortem* human brains with AD, with or without CAA^{21,22}.

Finally, we assessed the permeability of endothelial cell monolayers cultivated on Transwell inserts to simulate a simplified BBB model.

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Materials and Methods

Cell lines

Human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC) lines carrying the amyloid precursor protein (*APP*) duplication (hereafter *APPdup*, **Supplementary Fig.1A**) were purchased from the Coriell Institute (GM24675, 60 years old Finnish woman). hiPSC lines exhibiting trisomy 21 and their corresponding isogenic euploid controls (designated DS1 and DS1 isogenic, respectively) were obtained from the WiCell Research Institute (UWWC1-DS1 and UWWC1-DS2U, 1 year old male). Furthermore, an independent control hiPSC line (referred to as WTS60) was obtained from Wellcome Sanger Institute, HipSci (HPSI0114i-zapk_3, 60 years old male, no known pathology).

*Generation of *APPdup* isogenic hiPSCs*

The *APPdup* isogenic control hiPSC line was created using CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing by the iPS facility (ICV-iPS) of the Paris Brain Institut. A total of 10^6 iPSCs from the *APPdup* hiPSC clone were nucleofected (Lonza, 4D nucleofector System) with a ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex, which included 225pmol each of crRNA and tracrRNA-ATTO, along with 120pmol of Cas9 protein (IDT, Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 crRNA, Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 tracrRNA, ATTO 550, and Alt-R® S.p. HiFi Cas9 Nuclease 3NLS). The crRNA was designed using CRISPOR tool (<https://crispor.gi.ucsc.edu/crispor.py>) to target the sequence 5'-GCGGAATTGACAAGTTCCGA-3', situated immediately upstream of the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequence 5'-GGG-3' in exon 5 of *APP* gene.

Twenty-four hours after nucleofection, ATTO-positive cells were isolated using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) and plated at a low density (10–50 cells/cm²) on Laminin-521-coated plates supplemented with CloneR2 for clonal selection (StemCell, 77003 and 100-0691 respectively). After one-week, 192 individual iPSC clones were manually selected under a stereomicroscope and expanded in 96-well plates coated with Laminin-521. Upon reaching confluency, the clones were further expanded for cryopreservation and genomic DNA extraction.

Genomic DNA from each clone was analysed through PCR amplification followed by Sanger sequencing (primer Fwd = ACCAAAGTGTAACCCATGCT, primer Rev = GCAGACTCTGATGGGAGTGG). Sanger sequence files were then analysed using ICE CRISPR Analysis Tool (<https://ice.editco.bio/#/>). Three knockout (3KO) clones were identified. One clone, initially named CE2 but later referred to as *APPdup* isogenic, containing a 1 bp deletion at codon 180 in exon 5 220C on one of the three alleles generating a stop codon 3 amino acids downstream of the frameshift, was selected for all subsequent analyses (Supplementary Fig.1B).

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Differentiation of hiPSC into Endothelial Cells (hiPSC-ECs)

Differentiation of hiPSC clones into endothelial cells was carried out similarly as previously described²³ (**Fig. 1A**). In summary, hiPSCs were dissociated with 0.5 mM EDTA and plated on hESC-grade Matrigel (Corning #354277) at a density of 37,000 to 47,000 cells per cm² (depending on the cell line) in mTeSR1 (STEMCELL Technologies, Catalog #85850) medium supplemented with 10 μ M Y-27632 (Biotechne #1254). Upon reaching 90% confluency, the medium was replaced with a priming mesoderm medium. This medium consisted of N2B27, a 1:1 mixture of DMEM:F12 with Glutamax (Gibco #31331028) and Neurobasal media, supplemented with N2 and B27 (Life Technologies # 17502048 and #17504044), 6 μ M CHIR99021 (Stemcell #72054), and 25 ng/mL BMP4 (R&D Systems # 314-BP). After three days, the priming medium was switched to EC Induction Medium, which comprised StemPro-34 SFM medium (Life Technologies #10639011) supplemented with 200 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ (PeproTech #100-20-50UG) and 2 μ M forskolin (Sigma-Aldrich #50-165-7104). This induction medium was refreshed after one day. On the sixth day of differentiation, EC were dissociated using Accutase and separated via Magnetic-Activated Cell Sorting using CD144 (also called CDH5 or VE-cadherin) MicroBeads (Miltenyi Biotec # 130-097-857). The CD144-positive sorted cells were then replated on hESC-grade Matrigel-coated dishes at a density of 35,000 cells per cm² in StemPro-34 SFM supplemented with 100 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ for one day. On day seven, the medium was replaced with EGM2 medium (Lonza #CC-3162) supplemented with 50 ng/mL VEGF₁₆₅ (endothelial cell expansion medium). This expansion medium was replaced every other day. Confluent cells were cryopreserved at 1 million cells per vial in a freezing medium consisting of 50% EGM2, 40% FCS, and 10% DMSO before being used for assays. Quality controls, using VE-cadherin and CD31 immunostaining, were performed on hiPSC-derived endothelial cells at passage 3, and these cells maintained their endothelial phenotype at least up to passage 4.

Endothelial Cells culture

hiPSC-EC were cultured on 60mm petri dishes (TPP™ #93060) coated with Matrigel (Corning #354277). The culture medium used was Endothelial Cell Growth Medium-2 BulletKit (EGM2, Lonza #CC-3162), supplemented with 50 μ g/mL of VEGF₁₆₅ Recombinant Protein (PeproTech #100-20). Medium was replaced every 2-3 days, and cells were utilized for experiments once they reached at least 80% confluency.

MSD assay for A β measurements

A β peptides quantification was performed using the Meso Scale Discovery (MSD) electrochemiluminescence immunoassay platform with the A β Peptide Panel 1 (6E10) Kit

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(K15200E-2), following the manufacturer's instructions. Cell culture supernatants were collected, centrifuged to remove debris, and stored at -80°C until analysis. MSD 96-well multi-spot plates pre-coated with capture antibodies against $\text{A}\beta_{38}$, $\text{A}\beta_{40}$ and $\text{A}\beta_{42}$ were blocked with MSD Blocker A, followed by incubation with standards and samples in duplicate for 2 hours at room temperature. After washing, SULFO-TAG-labeled detection antibodies were added and incubated for 1h. Plates were washed again, and MSD Read Buffer T was added immediately before reading on a MESO QuickPlex SQ 120 instrument. Electrochemiluminescence signals were quantified using MSD Discovery Workbench software, and analyte concentrations were calculated based on a standard curve. Data below the lower limit of detection were excluded, and statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism on the average between the sample duplicates.

Mass spectrometry

Amyloid- β peptides profile was investigated in cell media using mass spectrometry (MS). Prior to MS analysis, $\text{A}\beta$ peptides were immunoprecipitated from 2 mL of supernatant using magnetic beads (Dynabeads M-280 Sheep anti-mouse, Thermo Fisher Scientific) coupled to anti- $\text{A}\beta$ antibodies, 6E10 and 4G8 (both, BioLegend), as previously described⁶. Eluates from the immunoprecipitation were dried down in a vacuum centrifuge and stored at -80°C . Prior to MS analysis, samples were reconstituted in 7 μl 8% formic acid/8% acetonitrile in water (v/v/v). Samples were run using a nanoflow liquid chromatography (LC) coupled to electrospray ionization (ESI) hybrid quadrupole-orbitrap tandem MS using a Dionex Ultimate 3000 system and a Q Exactive (both Thermo Fisher Scientific), as previously described²⁴. Database search was performed with PEAKS Studio v8.5 (Bioinformatics Solutions Inc.) against a custom-made APP database. All suggested fragment mass spectra were then evaluated manually. Details of the $\text{A}\beta$ peptides identified can be found in Supplementary Table 'Elena'.

RNAseq

RNA extraction and sequencing were conducted in two batches, with alignment and analysis performed uniformly across batches. Detailed information on each batch's samples is provided in **Supplementary Table 1**.

For the first batch, total RNA was isolated using the RNeasy Mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), which included a Trizol treatment step. The quality of the RNA was evaluated using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer, and only RNA samples with a RIN greater than 7 were used for RNAseq. Sequencing was carried out at the Helmholtz Zentrum Munich core facility on an Illumina NovaSeq sequencer. Illumina library kits, specifically TruSeq Stranded mRNA or Stranded mRNA Prep, Ligation, were used along with a PE150 stranded protocol to generate paired-end data. This data was then processed through an RNA-seq pipeline that included

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quality control checks using FastQC and MultiQC, followed by read trimming with trim_galore version 0.6.6 and cutadapt version 3.4.

For the second batch, total RNA isolation was performed using the RNeasy Plus Mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), which included a DTT treatment. The mRNA library preparation followed the manufacturer's recommendations using the Illumina Stranded mRNA Prep, Ligation kit from Illumina. Pooled library preparations were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus platform at iGENSEQ platform of the Paris Brain Institute, yielding 2 x 50 million 100-base reads per sample after demultiplexing.

Dragen

The initial bioinformatics analyses were conducted by the Data Analysis Core facility at ICM (RRID:SCR_026138). FastQC was used to assess the quality of the raw sequencing data. Poor-quality sequences were filtered out, and adapters were trimmed using fastp with default parameters. The Illumina DRAGEN bio-IT Platform (version 4.2.9, project PB25_LVA_RSQ) was employed to map the reads to the reference genome hg38 and to quantify the reads based on GENCODE version 47. Picard tools were utilized to evaluate library orientation, library composition, and coverage along transcripts. Normalized counts per million (CPM) were calculated using EdgeR (version 3.38.0)²⁵. **Supplementary Table 2** gives the level of expression for all sequenced samples.

Projection of Bulk RNA-seq Data onto a Single-Nuclei Reference Using Seurat

Bulk RNA-seq data were projected onto a vascular single-nuclei RNA-seq reference²¹ using Seurat (v4) in R. Bulk and single-nuclei expression matrices were imported and subset to genes that were commonly mapped in both datasets, regardless of expression levels. Both datasets were converted into Seurat objects, normalized, and scaled. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) were performed on the single-nuclei data using the top 15 principal components (number explaining more than 80% of the variance). Anchors between the datasets were identified with FindTransferAnchors(), and bulk samples were mapped onto the UMAP space using MapQuery(). Cell subtype annotations from the single-nuclei reference were used for visualization, and bulk samples were overlaid using ggplot2 to assess transcriptional similarity and alignment within the vascular cell landscape.

Differential Gene Expression (DGE) analysis - Quby

Downstream analyses and data visualizations were performed using Quby, an R Shiny software developed by the Data Analysis Core of the Paris Brain Institute (<https://dac.institutducerveau.org/>). Raw data were filtered using a CPM threshold greater than

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1 in at least half of the samples. Differential expression analysis was carried out using the GLM framework likelihood ratio test from DESeq2 (version 1.34) with the design formula \sim Batch + SampleGroup for the DS1 and isogenic samples, and \sim Passage + SampleGroup for the APPdup and isogenic samples. The resulting p-values were adjusted using the Benjamini and Hochberg procedure to control the False Discovery Rate (FDR). Genes with an FDR less than 0.05 were considered significantly differentially expressed, either upregulated or downregulated. **Supplementary Table 3** provides the list of DEGs.

Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA)

Enrichment analysis was performed using clusterProfiler (version 3.14.3) with Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) utilizing the Gene Ontology database C5: GO gene sets (April 2025). To compile a comprehensive list of protein-coding genes on human chromosome 21, we queried the Ensembl genome database using the BioMart data mining tool (Ensembl Genes 114, Human genes, GRCh38.p14). The dataset was filtered to retain only genes located on chromosome 21 with the gene type annotated as "protein_coding." For each gene, the Ensembl stable gene ID and the corresponding gene name were extracted. This curated gene list was subsequently used for downstream analyses focused on chromosome 21-specific gene expression.

Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA)

The Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) was conducted using a custom R program within the RStudio environment, specifically utilizing R version 4.4.3 (released on 2025-02-28 ucrt) and RStudio 2024.12.1 Build 563. Gene expression count data (in CPM) samples were imported and batch-corrected using the ComBat function to remove batch effects. Negative values resulting from correction were set to zero. Genes expressed above 1 CPM in at least half of the samples were retained and log₂-transformed ($\log_2(\text{CPM} + 1)$).

Samples and genes with excessive missing data were excluded using the goodSamplesGenes function. The top 3000 most variable genes were selected for further analysis. A soft-thresholding power was determined using the pickSoftThreshold function to approximate scale-free topology, and a power of 15 was chosen for both DS1 and APPdup analysis (**Supplementary Fig. 2A and 3A**).

Weighted gene co-expression networks were constructed using the WGCNA package. Adjacency and topological overlap matrices (TOM) were computed, followed by hierarchical clustering of genes based on TOM dissimilarity. Modules were identified using dynamic tree cutting with a minimum module size of 30 genes, then merged based on eigengene similarity at a cut height of 0.25.

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Module eigengenes were correlated with clinical traits (trisomy 21 and *APP*dup status). Module membership (MM) and gene significance (GS) measures were calculated to identify key genes within modules associated with traits. Module networks with an absolute module trait relationship superior to 0.5 and a MM GS correlation superior to 0.4 were exported for visualization in Cytoscape (V3.10.3) where gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) was performed on all modules. Representative networks reflecting result diversity were selected. Fold change values from differential gene expression analysis were used as border color coding for gene nodes, while edge weights were displayed inside gene names.

Permeability assay

Cells were washed once with sterile PBS, detached using 1 mL pre-warmed TrypLE Express (Thermo Fisher Scientific #12604013) at 37°C for 6 minutes, and collected in EGM 2 medium. Cell concentration was determined using a hemocytometer, centrifuged at 200 × g for 5 minutes, and resuspended to 5 × 10⁵ cells/mL. Cells (5 × 10⁴ in 100 µL) were seeded onto fibronectin-coated (5 µg/cm², Merck F1141) Corning 6.5 mm Transwell inserts (Corning #3413) and cultured at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Medium was refreshed after 24 hours and then every 2–3 days.

For permeability assays, 70 kDa FITC-Dextran in EGM2 (0.07 mg/mL, Sigma-Aldrich #FD250S) was applied to the apical side, with thrombin (10 U/mL, Sigma-Aldrich #T6884) only in positive controls Transwells. Samples from the well compartment were collected every 30 minutes over 2 hours, and fluorescence was measured using a SpectraMax® i3X microplate reader (Molecular Devices) with excitation and emission wavelengths set at 485 nm and 535 nm, respectively.

ImmunoCyto Chemistry (ICC)

Cells were seeded between 7.5 to 10 × 10⁴ cells per well onto glass coverslips placed in 24-well plates (Costar 3527), pre-coated with fibronectin (Merck #F1141) at 5 µg/cm² in PBS for 1 hour at room temperature (RT). Cells were cultured in EGM2 medium at 37 °C with 5% CO₂, with medium changes every 2–3 days. After 7 days, cells were rinsed with PBS and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA, Electron Microscopy Science #15714) diluted in PBS for 20 minutes at RT, followed by three PBS washes. Samples were stored at 4 °C in PBS until immunofluorescence staining.

For staining, cells were permeabilized for 20 minutes at RT with PBS containing 2% BSA and 0.05% saponin, then incubated with primary antibodies (Abcam antibodies VE-cadherin #ab33168, CD31 #ab24590, Occludin #ab242202, Claudin-5 #ab131259, KDR # ab2349, VWF #ab11713, Invitrogen antibody ZO1 #40-2200 and Biologend antibody 6E10 #803001) for 1 hour at RT, followed by secondary antibodies for 1 hour, both diluted in PBS-BSA-saponin.

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Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI (1 µg/mL) for 10 minutes at RT. Coverslips were mounted with Vectashield Antifade Mounting Medium (Vectashield #H-1700-10) and stored at 4 °C until imaging.

All images were captured in a single session with identical settings. Z-stacks were acquired for each field of view to capture the full thickness of the endothelial monolayer, ensuring complete coverage of cellular signal throughout the apical–basal axis. For each image, a summed Z-projection (sum of slices) was generated in Fiji (ImageJ, version 1.54f) to integrate total signal intensity across the entire cell volume for quantification.

Each immunostaining batch consisted of parallel seeding, fixation, staining, and imaging performed under identical conditions to ensure reproducibility and allow accurate comparison across cell lines.

To estimate average cell size, the total surface area of the field of view (acquired using identical confocal parameters across all samples) was divided by the number of DAPI-positive nuclei in that image. For consistency across experiments, each value was normalized to the average cell area of the corresponding isogenic control within the same immunostaining batch.

Protein expression was quantified by measuring the mean fluorescence intensity on summed Z-projection of the entire area of acquisition (not limited to the membrane) to include both junctional and cytoplasmic pools of each protein. Expression values were then normalized both on a per-cell basis and to the corresponding isogenic control average within each staining batch to account for differences in cell size and inter-batch variability.

Statistical Analyses

All statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.2. Details regarding the specific statistical tests used and the number of replicates are provided in the corresponding figure legends.

Figure and writing

Figure layouts and illustrations were created using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.2. and BioRender. Assistance from ChatGPT (OpenAI) was used for support with writing by reformulating sections of this article for clarity.

Results

Differentiation and characterization of hiPSC-derived Endothelial Cells (hiPSC-ECs)

Human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) were differentiated into endothelial cells (ECs) using a stepwise protocol (**Fig. 1A**). Cells were initially primed with CHIR99021, a GSK-3 inhibitor that activates Wnt/ β -catenin signaling, and Bone Morphogenetic Protein 4 (BMP4), a morphogen from the TGF- β superfamily, to induce mesoderm differentiation. Subsequent induction with Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) and forskolin, an adenylyl cyclase activator that increases intracellular cAMP levels to modulate cell signaling, promoted endothelial differentiation, followed by CD144-based magnetic sorting to isolate endothelial populations.

Immunofluorescence staining of the hiPSC-ECs demonstrated expression of key tight and adherent junction proteins (VE-cadherin and ZO-1 respectively) (**Fig. 1B**). Additional endothelial markers such as adherent junction protein CD31, tight junction protein Claudin-5 (CLDN5), von Willebrand factor (VWF) and the VEGF receptor type 2 also known as Kinase insert Domain Receptor (KDR), were robustly expressed thus confirming endothelial identity and BBB-relevant protein expression (**Fig. 6A and Supplementary Fig. 5**). Quantitative analysis of cell size based on immunostaining revealed that DS1 derived ECs were significantly larger than their isogenic control (1.7fold) and additional independent control (1.2fold). *APP*dup ECs exhibited a moderate increase in cell size (1.25fold larger compared to isogenic controls). (**Fig. 1C**)

We then measured A β peptides secreted by ECs using Meso Scale Discovery (MSD) assay. Secretion of A β ₄₀ (**Fig. 1D**) and A β ₄₂ (**Fig. 1E**) peptides by DS1 and *APP*dup ECs were increased relative to their respective isogenic controls. DS1 ECs secreted 1.9fold more A β ₄₀ and 2.5fold more A β ₄₂, whereas *APP*dup ECs secreted 1.5fold more A β ₄₀ and 1.25fold more A β ₄₂ compared to their respective isogenic ECs. The ratio of A β ₄₂ to A β ₄₀ revealed that ECs predominantly secreted A β ₄₀, with levels approximately 10 to 14 times higher than A β ₄₂ (**Fig. 1F**). While the A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio tended to decrease in *APP*dup ECs compared to isogenic ECs, it appeared significantly elevated in DS1-derived ECs compared to isogenic ECs, indicating altered processing or secretion dynamics in DS1 ECs.

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We further characterized the full spectrum of secreted A β peptides using immunoprecipitation followed by mass spectrometry analyses (IP-MS). A total of 16 distinct A β peptides were identified, originating from cleavage sites at positions 1, 5, and 17, and terminating at various downstream positions (**Fig. 1G**). The most abundant peptides detected were A β ₁₉ and A β ₁₅. Notably, DS1 ECs exhibited a unique peptide signature characterized by a high abundance of A β ₁₇, distinct from all other samples. Furthermore, only DS1 and *APP*dup ECs secreted detectable amounts of the longer peptides A β ₄₀ and A β ₃₄. DS1 isogenic control ECs also showed a distinct profile, with several peptides absent compared to other conditions. Overall, the total A β peptide content was highest in DS1 and *APP*dup cells relative to their respective isogenic controls, consistent with the quantitative measurements obtained via MSD assay (**Fig. 1H**).

hiPSC-ECs exhibit gene expression profiles like those of brain ECs

To further confirm the identity of the hiPSC-ECs, we conducted RNAseq on ECs differentiated from the different hiPSC lines. In 2023, a study published in *Nature Neuroscience*²¹ generated single-nuclei RNAseq (snRNAseq) profiles from human brain vascular cells isolated from various brain regions and defined cell-type-specific gene signatures. We compared these published cell-type gene lists (including arterial, venous, and capillary ECs, pericytes, smooth muscle cells, and fibroblasts) with the gene expression profiles from hiPSC-ECs RNAseq data (**Fig. 2A**). This comparison revealed that hiPSC-ECs shared over 95% of expressed genes with brain ECs while the overlap was lower with other vascular cell types such as smooth muscle cells (around 89.1% on average), fibroblasts (87.4% on average), pericytes (86.3% on average) and ependymal cells (80.1% on average). Among the vascular endothelial subtypes, hiPSC-ECs showed slightly greater transcriptional similarity to arterial ECs signatures than to capillary and venous ECs but still expressed genes specific to each of the three subtypes gene list.

To incorporate gene expression levels and more precisely position hiPSC-ECs gene expression profile within the single-nuclei vascular landscape, we projected our hiPSC-ECs RNA-seq data onto the published single vascular cell low-dimensional UMAP space. This was done using the Seurat package integration workflow (see Methods), aligning shared genes between datasets and transferring the hiPSC-ECs samples onto the single vascular cell UMAP. Our analysis showed that all hiPSC-ECs samples

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mapped predominantly onto the arterial endothelial cluster (**Fig. 2B**). This approach allowed a high-resolution comparison and validation of the endothelial identity of our hiPSC-ECs.

Gene expression changes in hiPSC-ECs from the individual with DS and the patient carrying *APPdup*

Differential gene expression (DGE) analysis was performed on the hiPSC-ECs RNA-seq data to assess transcriptional alterations in DS1 and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs compared to their respective isogenic controls (**Supplementary Fig. 4**). For the DS1 comparison, batch was included as a covariate to account for variability introduced by independent differentiation experiments (**Supplementary Fig. 4A,D**). The analysis revealed extensive transcriptomic dysregulation in DS1 ECs, with a total of 6,566 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (adjusted $p < 0.05$), comprising 3,175 upregulated and 3,381 downregulated genes (**Fig. 3A, Supplementary Fig. 4B**). Heatmap of the top DEGs demonstrated clear segregation between DS1 and isogenic samples, confirming robust and consistent transcriptional differences (**Fig. 3B**). For the *APPdup* comparison, only one batch was performed; therefore, cell passage number was included as a covariate to control for technical variability. We identified 2,952 DEGs (adjusted $p < 0.05$), among which 1,569 were upregulated and 1,383 were downregulated, suggesting a relatively moderate transcriptomic impact when compared to DS1 (**Fig. 3C, Supplementary Fig. 4E**). Despite the reduced number of DEGs, the heatmap still demonstrated a complete separation between *APPdup* and isogenic samples (**Fig. 3D**).

Identification of chromosome 21 genes involved in hiPSC-ECs phenotypes in DS and *APPdup*

To further investigate the transcriptional impact of trisomy 21 and *APP* microduplication, we specifically examined protein encoding genes mapping to human chromosome 21 (Chr21). We extracted the fold change (FC) values for all dysregulated Chr21 genes and analyzed their distribution (**Fig. 3E**) in DS and *APPdup* ECs. In DS, the distribution displayed a prominent peak around a 1.5-fold change, consistent with the expected gene dosage effect of trisomy 21. In contrast, *APPdup* cells showed only a modest symmetrical peak around -1.5 and 1.5 FC, reflecting the duplication of the *APP* locus only. We then assessed the overlap between the Chr21 genes and the

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DEGs in DS and *APPdup* (**Fig. 3F**). In DS, of the 122 Chr21 genes expressed, 80 were upregulated and 10 were downregulated compared to the isogenic control. In *APPdup*, among the 119 expressed Chr21 genes, 13 were upregulated and 10 were downregulated.

To study in greater depth the shared dysregulation pattern, we performed an intersection analysis of Chr21 DEGs between DS and *APPdup* (**Fig. 3G, Table 1 and Supplementary Table 4**). Of the 13 upregulated Chr21 genes in *APPdup*, 9 were also upregulated in DS, including key genes such as *APP*, the Dual-specificity Tyrosine Phosphorylation-Regulated Kinase 1A *DYRK1A*²⁶, the GA-Binding Protein Alpha *GABPA*²⁷, and the Ets-Related Gene *ERG*^{28–31}, all of which could be implicated in EC function and vascular biology. Interestingly, among the 10 downregulated Chr21 genes in *APPdup*, 7 were found to be upregulated in DS, including Beta-Site Amyloid Precursor Protein Cleaving Enzyme 2 *BACE2* encoding a protein involved in A β peptide processing^{32,33}.

Altogether, these results suggest both shared and distinct mechanisms involving Chr21 genes in DS and *APPdup* ECs, with potential implication for their respective cellular phenotypes.

Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) reveals distinct pathway alteration in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs

To gain further insight into the biological pathways affected in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs, we performed Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) using the DEGs and Gene Ontology (GO) gene sets. In the DS condition, a total of 327 gene sets reached significance with a false discovery rate (FDR) below 0.05. The most prominent positively enriched pathways were related to apoptosis, immune response and inflammation, endosomal and lysosomal compartments, and in a lesser way, cellular metabolism with fructose metabolism. Conversely, negatively enriched pathways were predominantly associated with cell cycle regulation and chromosome organization, suggesting impaired proliferative capacity and altered cellular architecture (**Supplementary Table 5**).

In contrast, in *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs, no gene sets met FDR < 0.05 threshold. However, when considering gene sets with an FDR below 0.1 to explore potential trends, we observed negatively enriched pathways related to ribosomal function and translation, immune system regulation, and protein processing (**Supplementary Table 6**).

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Interestingly, in both DS and *APPdup* ECs, the gene set "GOBP_protein_targeting_to_membrane" displayed a notable downregulation (**Fig. 4A,B**). Although this gene set did not meet the FDR significance threshold, the low nominal p-values suggest a biological trend worth considering, particularly given its potential relevance to the brain ECs tight and adherent junction proteins location at the plasma membrane. Additionally, in DS, the "GOBP_maintenance_of_blood_brain_barrier" gene set showed upregulation of numerous tight and adherent junction-related genes (**Fig. 4C**). While this enrichment did not reach FDR significance, the individual upregulation of the genes in that geneset may be sufficient to impact endothelial barrier properties. This pattern was not observed in *APPdup* cells (**Fig. 4D**), suggesting that distinct mechanisms may underlie endothelial dysfunction in DS and *APPdup*. **Table 2** highlights the differences of expression of key endothelial genes encoding tight and adherent junctions between DS and *APPdup*.

Collectively, these results suggest widespread transcriptional alterations in DS ECs, with specific enrichment of pathways related to BBB integrity, inflammation, and cellular metabolism, while *APPdup* ECs showed more subtle trends.

In a recent study published in *The Journal of Neuroscience*²², the authors performed snRNA-seq on endothelial cells isolated from various human brain regions, including samples with sporadic CAA (determined from histological assessment on the 32 human brain from donor diagnosed with sAD). Their analysis revealed 684 genes associated with CAA, comprising 350 genes negatively correlated, and 334 genes positively correlated with the presence of CAA.

To investigate potential changes of CAA-related ECs changes in DS and *APPdup*, we performed GSEA using the positively and negatively correlated CAA-associated gene sets alongside the list of endothelial genes from **Fig.2** deduced from the published snRNA-seq study²¹. We found that DEGs in DS were significantly enriched among genes negatively associated with CAA, while DEGs in *APPdup* were significantly enriched among genes positively associated with CAA (**Table 3**). Additionally, both the DS and *APPdup* DEGs showed significant enrichment within the broader set of endothelial genes, suggesting that both DS and *APPdup* alter the global ECs function. **Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) identifies transcriptional modules similar to the GSEA**

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We performed a weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) on hiPSC-ECs RNA-seq data to identify transcriptional modules associated with DS and *APPdup*. After merging highly similar modules, the analysis identified 13 modules for DS and 15 for *APPdup* (**Fig. 5A,B**). To focus on modules most strongly associated with the respective genetic alterations, we applied stringent selection criteria based on the module–trait correlation and the correlation between gene significance (GS) and module membership (MM). Specifically, we retained modules showing an absolute module–trait correlation greater than 0.5 and a GS–MM correlation greater than 0.4. Applying these thresholds, five modules remained for DS and four for *APPdup* (**Fig. 5C,D**). These modules were exported to Cytoscape for network visualization, and GSEA was performed on each of them.

In DS, the grey60 module exhibited an exceptionally strong positive correlation with DS (0.96) and a high GS–MM correlation (0.87). This module was significantly enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery, cell adhesion, and blood vessel morphogenesis, with most genes within these sets being upregulated. (**Fig. 5E, Supplementary Table 7**). Similarly, the white module, which was also positively correlated with DS, was enriched for gene sets associated with immune response. The salmon and darkorange modules, both positively correlated with DS, were enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery and cell surface, consistent with the biological functions identified in the grey60 module. In contrast, the blue module, which was the only module negatively correlated with DS (-0.86), was enriched for gene sets linked to cell cycle regulation, cell division, and chromosome organization, with most genes either downregulated or not differentially expressed (**Fig. 5E Supplementary Table 7**).

A similar WGCNA approach in *APPdup* samples revealed the brown module as the strongest positive correlation with *APPdup* (0.94). This module was enriched for gene sets related to cell periphery and in a lesser proportion, cell adhesion, although to a lesser extent than in DS, as reflected by a smaller number of genes per gene set and a lower proportion of upregulated genes (**Fig. 5F Supplementary Table 8**). The darkgrey module showed minimal enrichment for any gene sets, and none of the enriched sets were relevant to endothelial cell biology (Supplementary Table6). Among the negatively correlated modules, the blue module displayed the strongest negative correlation with *APPdup* and was enriched for gene sets associated with cell periphery, cell adhesion, cell junctions, and blood vessel morphogenesis, with most genes either

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downregulated or not differentially expressed. The midnightblue module, which was also negatively correlated with *APPdup* but to a lesser extent, showed similar enrichment for gene sets involved in cell junction organization, cell periphery, motility, and differentiation (**Fig. 5F Supplementary Table 8**).

Overall, WGCNA results were consistent with GSEA analysis both for DS and *APPdup*.

Quantification of junction proteins in DS and *APPdup* using immunolabelling of hiPSC-ECs

To examine whether the transcriptional changes observed in junctional proteins at the transcriptomic level were reflected at the protein level, we performed immunostaining on monolayers of hiPSC-ECs grown on a fibronectin coating and focusing on tight and adherens junction proteins, as well as the endothelial markers VWF, KDR, and APP/A β (**Fig. 1B, Fig. 6A, Supplementary Fig. 5**). Quantification of the immunostaining signal was performed across the entire cell area, rather than being restricted to the cell membrane, to account for both membrane-associated and cytoplasmic protein expression. In DS, ECs showed a significant increase in the expression of tight junction proteins CLDN5 and ZO-1, as well as adherens junction proteins VE-cadherin and CD31, consistent with transcriptomic evidence of upregulated genes involved in cell adhesion and endothelial structure (**Fig. 6B-E**). In contrast, *APPdup* ECs did not show significant changes in tight junction protein levels relative to their isogenic control but did exhibit a modest yet significant increase in adherens junction proteins. Both KDR (VEGFR2) and APP/A β (detected with the 6E10 antibody) were significantly increased in DS and *APPdup* ECs compared to their respective controls (**Fig. 6F,G**), consistent with the presence of an additional *APP* copy in both lines. VWF was notably and significantly elevated in DS1, though with high variability (**Fig. 6H**).

Overall, these results support our earlier findings: DS ECs exhibit broadly increased expression of both tight and adherens junction proteins compared to their isogenic controls, while *APPdup* ECs display milder changes, limited to adherens junction proteins, and no significant alterations in tight junctions. However, since measurements were performed on whole cells, the data may not fully reflect the functional status of these proteins.

Measure of permeability of monolayers of hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APPdup*

To assess whether the transcriptional and protein-level alterations observed in tight and adherent junction proteins translated into functional changes in endothelial barrier integrity, we established a quantitative permeability assay for hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APPdup* and their corresponding isogenic controls as well as one independent control.

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The hiPSC-ECs were grown as a confluent monolayer on Transwell microporous membranes (0.4 μm pore size) for one week, allowing sufficient time for the formation of mature intercellular junctions (**Fig. 7A**). To measure paracellular permeability, a solution of FITC-labeled dextran (70 kDa) was introduced into the upper chamber of the Transwell system, and fluorescence levels in the lower chamber were quantified over time (**Fig.7B,C**). We confirmed that thrombin treatment transiently disrupted endothelial junctions^{34,35} (**Fig.7D,E**).

For comparative analysis across multiple independent experiments, permeability values for each cell line were normalized to the average permeability of the corresponding independent control. Using this approach, we found that *APP*dup ECs exhibited a 1.3-fold increase in permeability relative to their isogenic control (**Fig.7G**), consistent with compromised BBB function. In contrast, DS ECs displayed a 2.8-fold reduction in permeability compared to both their isogenic control and the independent control, indicating enhanced barrier integrity (**Fig.7F**).

Discussion

The characterization of hiPSC-ECs from individuals with DS and a patient carrying *APP*dup has unveiled notable differences in cell morphology, gene expression profile but also tight and adherent junction protein levels. These differences are consistent with the results of functionality assays using ECs monolayers modelling the BBB permeability. In DS, genes involved in protein targeting to the membrane and cell cycle regulation appeared downregulated, potentially compromising junction integrity and cell viability. However, this was accompanied by an upregulation of several tight and adherens junction proteins, along with genes related to blood vessel morphogenesis and cell adhesion, probably linked to the overexpression of Chr21 genes. In contrast, *APP*dup ECs function were impaired more subtly, affecting membrane localization of junctional proteins similarly to DS, but with minimal positive and stronger negative effects on adhesion, and no global overexpression of junctional components to compensate, resulting in a stronger net negative impact on barrier function.

Role of A β and *APP* on hiPSC-ECs phenotypes in DS and *APP*dup

Our findings also indicate a significant increase in the secretion of both A β ₄₀ and A β ₄₂ by ECs derived from iPSC from individuals with DS or *APP*dup compared to their respective isogenic controls. This elevated secretion was associated with alterations in the A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio, showing a marked increase in DS and a trend to decrease in *APP*dup. Several studies have reported that the A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio in individuals with DS decreases with age due to the deposition of A β ₄₂^{36,37} and plasma from individuals with DS generally exhibits a lower A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio compared to controls^{38–40}. Conversely, studies using cultured neurons have documented an increased A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio in DS relative to isogenic controls and DS cells with one *APP* copy KO^{41,42}. Despite these variations, all the aforementioned studies indicate that both A β ₄₀ and A β ₄₂ levels are elevated in DS compared to controls. This aligns with our findings and is consistent with the overexpression of the *APP* gene due to the presence of an extra Chr21.

To the best of our knowledge, no prior study had examined A β secretion specifically from hiPSC-ECs from individuals with DS and *APP*dup. Our findings indicate that ECs secrete A β with levels of A β ₄₀ approximately 10–15 times higher than those of A β ₄₂. This observation aligns with previous reports suggesting that vascular amyloid is predominantly composed of A β ₄₀⁴³. Interestingly, the relatively higher proportion of A β ₄₀ in plasma compared to culture media may indicate increased deposition of A β ₄₂ in the brain or reduced transport of A β ₄₂ across the BBB in individuals with DS.

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Furthermore, mass spectrometry analysis revealed distinct A β peptide profiles between *APPdup* and DS. The most abundant secreted peptides were A β ₁₇ and A β ₁₉, both products of APP processing via the amyloidogenic pathway. A β ₁₉ has been observed in cells expressing APP with the Iowa and Swedish mutations, while A β ₁₇ was found to be increased only with the Swedish mutation⁴⁴. Notably, A β ₁₇ is the second most abundant peptide in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), elevated in Alzheimer's disease, whereas A β ₁₉ is also present but at lower concentrations⁴⁵. Both A β ₁₇ and A β ₁₉ levels decreased following γ -secretase inhibition^{46,47}, which is known to regulate vascular permeability and angiogenesis in endothelial cells through its role in the Notch signalling pathway, affecting cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival⁴⁸. Indeed, γ -secretase inhibitors have been shown to induce the formation of immature vessel networks⁴⁸.

Additionally, A β ₁₉ can be produced following BACE2 cleavage⁴⁹, which is increased in DS. While BACE2 favours non-amyloidogenic processing³³, in AD, it can act as a β -secretase³². Other studies using DS organoids have suggested that BACE2 acts as an AD-suppressor gene⁵⁰. Here, DS ECs carrying three genomic copies of BACE2 produced very high levels of A β ₁₉ compared to DS isogenic ECs with only two copies of BACE2. Levels of BACE2 transcripts in DS ECs were 7.7 fold higher compared to isogenic ECs (**Table 1**). *APPdup* ECs and their isogenic counterparts produced similar levels of A β ₁₉, albeit lower than those observed in DS. Of note, this study did not include *APPdup* isogenic organoids. Our recent work on *postmortem* brains showed that A β ₁₇ was absent in control and DS brains but high in DS with AD (DSAD) and *APPdup*. A β ₁₉ levels were high across all cases. Collectively, these findings suggest differential APP processing in DS and *APPdup*.

It is widely accepted that A β disrupts endothelial junctional integrity and impairs BBB function by modulating VE-cadherin phosphorylation⁵¹, reducing the expression and altering the distribution of tight junction proteins^{52–54}, and promoting cytoskeletal rearrangements such as stress fiber formation and actin filament disorganization⁵⁵. These changes create intercellular gaps and ultimately increase endothelial permeability. However, the intrinsic role of APP in ECs, independent of its cleavage into A β , remains less well characterized.

Emerging evidence suggests that APP expression in the vascular endothelium is important for maintaining endothelial homeostasis. APP has been implicated in the regulation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) expression and the maintenance

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of nitric oxide (NO)-mediated endothelial function⁵⁶. Given that eNOS-derived NO contributes to the structural and functional integrity of endothelial junctions⁵⁷, preserving barrier properties and coordinating intercellular signaling, APP overexpression may enhance endothelial cell junctional stability to some extent by increasing NO production and promoting the formation of adherent junctions.

Conversely, APP has also been shown to mediate tyrosine kinase-dependent signalling cascades in endothelial cells⁵⁸. Kinases such as Src and Yes are known to regulate the dynamic remodelling of adherent junctions through the phosphorylation of VE-cadherin, a key adhesion molecule^{59,60}. Dysregulation of this pathway by APP overexpression could impair junctional plasticity, leading to increased vascular permeability or impaired endothelial repair^{59,60}. In light of this, APP overexpression may exert a dual effect: while promoting some aspects of endothelial stability, it may also destabilize junctions through aberrant kinase signalling.

This duality could potentially explain our WGCNA results in APPdup, which revealed a balance between a modest pro-cell adherens and a stronger anti-angiogenic, and negative effect on both cell adhesion and junction. These findings highlight the complex, context-dependent role of APP in endothelial biology, suggesting that both its expression level and processing may critically shape vascular function.

Differences in gene expression between DS and APPdup hiPSC-ECs and their effects on CAA

First, gene expression changes were found to be more than twice as extensive in DS compared to APPdup, with 6,566 and 2,952 differentially expressed genes (DEGs), respectively. This broader impact in DS is due to the overexpression of the entire Chr21, compared to only the APP locus in APPdup.

Second, GSEA showed that upregulated genes in DS were involved in apoptosis, immune response and inflammation, the endo-lysosomal compartment and fructose metabolism while in APPdup downregulated genes belonged to categories such as the immune system and protein synthesis. Only in DS downregulated genes belonged to the cell cycle and proliferation categories. Interestingly “protein targeting to the membrane” gene category was decreased both in DS and APPdup while genes involved in maintenance of the BBB were increased in DS but not in APPdup. A published study in hiPSC-ECs from DS found similar increase of apoptosis but also mitochondrial reactive oxygen species, angiogenesis and oxygen consumption rate as well as a decrease in EGR1⁶¹. Consistent with the GSEA findings, our WGCNA also

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revealed a positive link with angiogenesis (module grey60, Fig.5E and Supplementary Table 5) in DS. Furthermore, we observed reduced EGR1 expression in our samples with foldchange of -2.75 (Supplementary Table 8). Overall, our results support and partially replicate the previously reported DS endothelial phenotype.

DEGs in DS ECs were enriched in genes negatively correlated with CAA while in *APPdup* DEGs positively correlated with CAA, a difference that could explain the higher CAA severity in *APPdup* compared to DS, suggesting gene expression profile in ECs that could protect against CAA. These findings also support the hypothesis that ECs are intrinsically involved in CAA pathology and supports the use of ECs as a relevant model to study early CAA mechanisms. Nevertheless, whether the observed ECs functional alterations (junction organization and permeability changes) are directly driven by genes identified in the CAA correlation analysis remains uncertain. The link is biologically plausible but requires further validation through perturbation studies.

Finally the WGCNA showed that In DS, gene modules positively correlated with the condition were enriched for processes related to cell adhesion, blood vessel morphogenesis, and the immune response, with most genes being upregulated. In contrast, negatively correlated modules were associated with cell cycle regulation and chromosome organization, with genes largely downregulated. In *APPdup*, similar but weaker enrichment for cell adhesion and cell periphery was observed among positively correlated modules, while negatively correlated modules were enriched for cell junction organization, morphogenesis, and motility, with most genes either downregulated or unchanged. Overall GSEA and WGNA analyses pointed to negative changes in cell cycle only in DS, and opposite effects on immune response and membrane proteins involved in cell adhesion and junction. In *postmortem* brains from individuals with DS, co-expression modules related to ECs, microglia and astrocytes were positively correlated with immune response and vascular development⁶². The largest number of hub genes were involved in extracellular signalling and cell-cell interaction, consistent with our WGCNA results.

Overexpression of Chr21 genes in DS on ECs phenotypes

Our data show upregulation of *APP*, *DYRK1A*, *ERG*, and *GABPA* transcripts in both *APPdup* and DS, with Runt-related transcription factor 1 (*RUNX1*) a transcription factor essential for hematopoiesis, downregulated in both conditions. Conversely, Interleukin 10 Receptor Beta (*IL10RB*), *BACE2*, and Protein O-Fucosyltransferase 2 (*POFUT2*),

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an enzyme that adds O-fucose sugars to proteins, aiding their proper folding and function, were upregulated in DS but downregulated in *APPdup* (**Table 1**).

ERG is known to directly regulate the expression of *CLDN5* gene by binding to its promoter region; knockdown or loss of *ERG* leads to reduced *CLDN5* levels and increased endothelial permeability^{28,29}. In addition, ERG also positively regulates adherent junctions through Wnt/ β -Catenin but also affects VE-cadherin^{30,31}. Overall, the overexpression of ERG is expected to stabilize not only tight junctions but also adherent junctions and therefore decrease ECs permeability.

Although less studied in EC, DYRK1A loss-of-function disrupts tight junctions, increases vascular permeability, and causes cerebral haemorrhage, indicating its role in maintaining junctional stability²⁶. Mechanistically, DYRK1A regulates calcium homeostasis, essential for assembling and maintaining tight and adherens junctions. Disruption leads to altered calcium-binding protein and adhesion molecule expression, compromising junction integrity²⁶. Thus, DYRK1A upregulation could enhance junction stability and barrier function, consistent with its positive regulation of angiogenesis and ECs proliferation⁶³. It was also demonstrated that DYRK1A increases EGFR1 via PPARG suppression and that the involvement of EGFR1 on ECs phenotypes in DS (apoptosis, mitochondrial reactive oxygen species production, angiogenesis, and oxygen consumption rate) can be restored either by EGFR1 suppression by treatment with pioglitazone or inhibition of DYRK1A⁶¹. It will be interesting to know whether DYRK1A inhibition can modify the decrease of permeability of a monolayer of ECs from individuals with DS.

Downregulation of *IL10RB* in *APPdup* may impair endothelial junction integrity, as IL10RB mediates IL-10 signaling that reduces endothelial inflammation, apoptosis, and permeability, while preserving VE-cadherin expression⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. Similarly, POFUT2, an enzyme responsible for O-fucosylation of thrombospondin type 1 repeat (TSR)-containing proteins, is critical for post-translational modification of extracellular matrix (ECM) and adhesion proteins, which are vital for ECs junctions⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹. Its downregulation in *APPdup* could impair ECM protein maturation and junction function.

RUNX1 induces VE-cadherin expression and promotes angiogenesis in embryonic endothelial precursors. Loss of *RUNX1* results in defective vascular formation, increased permeability, and hemorrhage, underscoring its role in maintaining barrier integrity⁷⁰. Its unexpected downregulation in both *APPdup* and DS likely contributes to junctional defects, particularly in adherent junctions. Overexpression of *RUNX1* in DS

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modulates the extracellular matrix (ECM) in various cell types and tissues such as heart and fibroblasts, increasing cell migration while those effects are reduced by silencing RUNX1⁷¹.

GABPA is involved in the regulation of genes important for endothelial cell morphogenesis. Genome-wide studies show that GABPA directly or indirectly regulates genes crucial for endothelial and epithelial cell development, including processes related to cell structure and function²⁷. A study identified a conserved GABP-binding motif within the *Robo4* promoter that is essential for endothelial expression, confirmed via promoter mutagenesis and *in vivo* reporter assays⁷². *Robo4* have been found in multiple studies to have a critical role in endothelial cells function including barrier stabilization and angiogenesis.^{73–75}

GABPA regulates genes essential for endothelial morphogenesis and cell structure²⁷. A conserved GABP-binding motif was found in *Robo4* promoter, validated by mutagenesis and *in vivo* reporter assays, and critical for *Robo4* endothelial expression⁷². *Robo4* itself plays a key role in barrier stabilization and angiogenesis^{73–75}. Moreover, GABP α/γ complexes repress *VEGF* transcription. In cerebral ischemia models, reduced BAI2 lowers GABP levels, resulting in *VEGF* upregulation⁷⁶. Therefore, *GABPA* upregulation may slow the cell cycle by repressing *VEGF*⁷⁷, consistent with our WGCNA results. Collectively, *GABPA* overexpression in DS and *APPdup* likely impacts endothelial function at multiple levels.

It was also found that DS ECs exhibit decreased proliferation, reduced migration, were less responsive to *VEGF* with an increase in *VEGF* receptors (FLT1, KDR and FLT4) and a weak TNF- α inflammatory response⁷⁸. The decrease of response to *VEGF* could be due to the increase of formation of A β -*VEGF*-derived peptides complexes in DS and *APPdup*. Indeed it was shown that those *VEGF*-derived peptides can prevent A β aggregation and toxicity⁷⁹. In our study FLT4 and KDR were increased with FC of 1.9 and 1.8 respectively (**Supplementary Table 3**), suggesting reproducibility across various DS lines.

Although several of these genes are upregulated in both *APPdup* and DS, the greater fold changes observed in DS, combined with differences in gene dysregulation patterns, may underline the compensatory effects seen exclusively in DS (**Table 1, Table 2**).

BBB Functionality and Aging in DS and *APPdup*

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While the opposing effect on ECs permeability in DS and *APPdup* are in accordance with molecular analysis, the decrease in ECs permeability observed in DS ECs does not necessarily equate to preserved or improved BBB function during aging. Interestingly, ECs from DS exhibit a slower cell cycle and increased size, features that may limit regenerative capacity during aging and thereby contribute to BBB dysfunction later in life. The initially enhanced junctional organization could confer early-stage resilience, especially when compared to *APPdup* ECs. This might suggest a window of relative vascular stability in DS, followed by a decline associated with reduced renewal capacity and cumulative stress.

Limitations

While our hiPSC-EC model provides valuable insights into cell-intrinsic changes, it cannot fully recapitulate the complexity of the NVU and the brain microenvironment. Factors such as aging, multicellular interactions, and systemic inflammation likely play crucial roles in modulating the BBB integrity and CAA progression. The interplay between endothelial, glial, pericytes, smooth muscle cells and immune cells at the NVU suggests that the transcriptomic and functional changes observed in hiPSC-ECs represent only a subset of the broader *in vivo* effects. Importantly, chronic disturbances in homeostasis, particularly those related to A β accumulation and impaired clearance, are expected to further compromise BBB function over time.

Although endothelial cells can produce A β locally, our DS model showing decreased BBB permeability, and probably less clearance despite less CAA, suggests that CAA in DS may not arise from local A β production alone. Instead, the vasculature may act mainly as a clearance pathway for parenchymal A β , which could explain also the higher parenchymal A β burden observed in DSAD compared to *APPdup* individuals^{6,9}. This is consistent with the relatively higher plasma levels of A β_{40} compared to cell culture media, as mentioned earlier in the discussion. Given that A β_{42} is less soluble, its clearance from brain tissue to blood may be hindered by the less permeable BBB in DS, contributing to the lower plasma A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio seen in DS despite endothelial cells producing a higher A β_{42} /A β_{40} ratio compared to controls.

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Acknowledgments

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Figure legends

Figure 1: Differentiation and characterization of hiPSC-derived Endothelial Cells (hiPSC-ECs) from an individual with DS and a patient carrying *APPdup* and their isogenic controls. **A:** Schematic overview of the differentiation protocol based on Patsch et al. (2015)²³. **B:** Representative immunostaining of hiPSC-ECs showing expression of adherent junction VE-cadherin (top) and tight junction ZO-1 (bottom), with nuclei counterstained using DAPI. **C:** hiPSC-EC cell size normalized to the corresponding isogenic control cultured and stained in parallel for each condition, showing significant increased size in both DS1 (1.7fold) and *APPdup* (1.25fold) compared to their respective isogenic controls. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with multiple comparisons. **D:** $A\beta_{40}$ levels secreted by ECs derived from hiPSC DS1 (left) and *APPdup* (right). **E:** $A\beta_{42}$ levels secreted by ECs derived from hiPSC DS1 (left) and *APPdup* (right). **F:** $A\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio in DS1 compared to DS1 isogenic whereas there is a more modest tendency to its decrease in *APPdup* compared to *APPdup* isogenic. **G:** Different $A\beta$ peptides detected in hiPSC-EC supernatants by mass spectrometry. Both bar height and color scale indicate signal intensity for each peptide. **H:** Total abundance (sum) of all $A\beta$ peptides identified in G confirming the MSD results. Numbers above bars indicate the number of distinct $A\beta$ peptides detected per group. Statistical significance: Unpaired t-tests * $p \leq 0.05$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 2: hiPSC-EC exhibit gene expression profiles similar to those of brain ECs. **A:** Table showing the number of expressed genes shared between hiPSC-ECs and transcriptomic signatures of various human brain vascular cell types, as defined by snRNA-seq from Sun et al. (2023)²¹ Values in parentheses indicate the total number of genes in each reference signature (column headers) and the number of shared genes (table entries). **B:** UMAP projection of bulk hiPSC-EC RNA-seq data onto a reference single-nuclei vascular cell atlas²¹ using Seurat. hiPSC-EC samples are shown in red and superpose with brain endothelial cells.

Figure 3: Gene expression changes in hiPSC-ECs from an individual with DS and a patient carrying *APPdup* compared to their isogenic controls. **A:** Volcano plot from DGE analysis of DS1 vs DS1 isogenic showing massive dysregulations. **B:**

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Heatmap associated with DS1 DGE analysis. **C:** Volcano plot from DGE analysis of *APPdup* vs *APPdup* isogenic showing less drastic dysregulation compared to DS1. **D:** Heatmap associated with *APPdup* DGE analysis. **E:** Histogram showing the number of differentially expressed genes (y-axis) on chromosome 21 across fold change intervals (x-axis, bin width = 0.5) from the differential gene expression analysis on DS1 and *APPdup* and their respective isogenic controls. **F:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes expressed in DS1 (up) and *APPdup* (down) and the differentially expressed genes from their respective DGE analysis. **G:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes dysregulated in DS1 and *APPdup* respective DGE analysis showing similarities but also distinct expressions changes. The list of the 64 Chr21 genes upregulated in DS1 only can be found in **Supplementary Table 4**.

Figure 4: Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) reveals distinct pathway alteration in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs. **A, B:** Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "protein targeting to the membrane." in DS1 (A) and *APPdup* (B). **C, D:** Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "Maintenance of blood-brain barrier" in DS1 (C) and in *APPdup* (D).

Figure 5: Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) identifies transcriptional modules similar to the GSEA. **A, B:** Gene dendrograms and corresponding module color assignments before and after module merging for the DS1 (A), *APPdup* (B) and their respective controls. **C, D:** Summary tables showing the selected merged modules in DS1 (C) and *APPdup* (D), based on module–trait correlation and correlation between gene significance (GS) and module membership (MM), with associated *p*-values. **E, F:** Examples of gene sets representative of the diversity of pathways identified by GSEA for selected modules in DS1 (E) and *APPdup* (F). Border color indicates the regulation status in the DGE analysis (up red, down blue, non-regulated white), and fill color represents the relative weight (importance) of each gene within the module. **E:** In DS1, the grey60 and white modules, both positively correlated with the DS trait, were enriched for genes involved in cell periphery, cell–cell adhesion, blood vessel morphogenesis, and immune response, primarily composed of upregulated genes. The blue module, negatively correlated with DS, was enriched for cell cycle–related genes, mostly downregulated. **F:** In *APPdup*, the brown module, positively correlated with the *APPdup* trait, contained a small number of genes

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linked to cell periphery and cell–cell adhesion. The blue module, negatively correlated with *APPdup*, was enriched for genes associated with cell junctions, adhesion, cell periphery, and blood vessel morphogenesis, largely composed of downregulated or non-regulated genes.

Figure 6: Quantification of junction proteins in DS and *APPdup* using immunolabelling of hiPSC-ECs. **A:** Representative immunostaining of hiPSC-ECs showing expression of adherent junction CD31 (yellow) and tight junction claudin-5 (green), APP/A β labelling (6E10, red), with nuclei counterstained using DAPI. **B-H:** Quantification of adherens junctions VE-cadherin (**B**) and CD31 (**C**), tight junctions ZO1 (**D**), Claudin-5 (**E**), endothelial markers VWF (**F**) and KDR (**G**) and APP/A β (6E10, **H**). All measurements represent relative signal per cell, normalized to the respective isogenic control line. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA for each comparison. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 7: Measure of permeability of monolayers of hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APPdup*. **A:** Schematic of the experimental setup used to measure permeability: a 70KDa FITC-dextran passage through a hiPSC-EC monolayer cultured on Transwell inserts was monitored over time, and permeability was calculated using the formula adapted from Czupalla et al. (2014)⁸⁰. **B, C:** Time-course of FITC fluorescence accumulation in the lower well compartment, showing reduced tracer passage in the presence of hiPSC-EC monolayers from DS1 (**B**) and *APPdup* (**C**) compared to cell-free controls. **D, E:** Permeability values over time for DS1 (**D**) and *APPdup* (**E**) hiPSC-EC, including controls. Thrombin treatment was used as a positive control disrupting adherent junctions and increasing permeability. **F:** Normalized permeability at 120min in DS1, its isogenic control, and the independent control WTS60, showing a significantly reduced permeability in DS1 compared to both controls. **G:** Normalized permeability at 120min in *APPdup*, its isogenic control, and WTS60, showing a significantly increased permeability in *APPdup* relative to both controls. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with multiple comparisons. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Supplementary Figure 1: Characterization of the *APPdup* microduplication and its isogenic control deletion. **A:** Genomic localization of the microduplication on

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chromosome 21 identified in the *APPdup* patient. The microduplication is 763 134 bp long and includes the genes *GABPA*, *ATP5J*, *JAM2* and *APP*. **B:** Location of the CRISPR/Cas9 mediated deletion introduced in one of the three *APP* copies of the *APPdup* hiPSCs to generate an isogenic hiPSC control line.

Supplementary Figure 2: Weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) in DS1, its isogenic control, and independent controls after module merging. **A:** The scale independence plot shows that a scale-free topology fit ($R^2 > 0.8$) is achieved at soft-thresholding power $\beta = 15$. **B:** Heatmap of eigengene adjacency showing correlations between merged modules. Warmer colors indicate higher correlation between module eigengenes, suggesting co-expression similarity. **C:** Merged module–trait relationship heatmap. Cells show Pearson correlations (with p-values) between module eigengenes and DS traits; color indicates correlation strength and direction. **D to H:** Scatter plots showing the relationship between gene significance (GS) for the trait and module membership (MM) in selected merged module with an absolute module–trait correlation > 0.5 and exhibiting genes with a significant positive correlation ($r > 0.4$, $p < 0.05$) between GS and MM, indicating key genes associated with both the trait and the module.

Supplementary Figure 3: WGCNA in *APPdup* and its isogenic control after module merging. **A:** The scale independence plot shows that a scale-free topology fit ($R^2 > 0.8$) is achieved at soft-thresholding power $\beta = 15$. **B:** Heatmap of eigengene adjacency showing correlations between merged modules. Warmer colors indicate higher correlation between module eigengenes, suggesting co-expression similarity. **C:** Merged module–trait relationship heatmap. Cells show Pearson correlations (with p-values) between module eigengenes and *APPdup* traits; color indicates correlation strength and direction. **D to G:** Scatter plots showing the relationship between gene significance (GS) for the trait and module membership (MM) in selected merged module with an absolute module–trait correlation > 0.5 and exhibiting genes with a significant positive correlation ($r > 0.4$, $p < 0.05$) between GS and MM, indicating key genes associated with both the trait and the module.

Supplementary Figure 4: Differential gene expression (DGE) analysis in DS1 and *APPdup* lines compared to their respective isogenic controls. **A:** Principal component analysis (PCA) of DS1 and its isogenic control, corrected for batch effects, reveals clear segregation by genotype and differentiation. **B:** Bar plot showing the

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number of significantly dysregulated genes in the DS1 hiPSC-ECs. **C:** MA plot of DS1, showing no abnormal global trends. **D:** PCA of *APPdup* and its isogenic control, corrected for passage number, reveals segregation by genotype and differentiation. **E:** Bar plot summarizing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs. **F:** MA plot of *APPdup*, with no abnormal global trends.

Supplementary Figure 5: Immunolabelling of endothelial proteins in DS and *APPdup* hiPSC-ECs. Representative immunostaining of hiPSC-ECs showing expression of VWF (red) and VEGF receptor KDR (green), with nuclei counterstained using DAPI.

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Table legends

Table 1: Expression changes of key Chr21 genes in hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APP*dup and their isogenic controls.

Table 2: Expression changes of keys endothelial tight and adherent junctions genes in hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APP*dup and their isogenic controls.

Table 3: GSEA in hiPSC-ECs from DS and *APP*dup for endothelial genes from *Bryant et al. 2023*²² and genes positively or negatively correlated with CAA from *Sun et al. 2023*²¹.

Supplementary Table 1: List of RNAseq samples with associated information on differentiation, passage numbers and RNAseq batch.

Supplementary Table 2: Gene expression matrix for all RNA-seq samples, expressed in counts per million (CPM).

Supplementary Table 3: List of DEGs un hiPSC-ECs from an individual with DS (sheet 1) and a patient carrying *APP*dup (sheet 2) and their isogenic controls.

Supplementary Table 4: List of Chr21 genes up regulated in DS1 and not dysregulated in *APP*dup in **Fig.3G**.

Supplementary Table 5: GSEA of DEGs between hiPSC-ECs from DS vs isogenic control. All tested gene sets are included.

Supplementary Table 6: GSEA of DEGs between hiPSC-ECs from *APP*dup vs isogenic control. All tested gene sets are included.

Supplementary Table 7: GSEA for each module identified by WGCNA on the DS1 vs DS1 isogenic and independent control samples.

Supplementary Table 8: GSEA for each module identified by WGCNA on the *APP*dup vs *APP*dup isogenic samples.

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Figure 1

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A

	Endothelial (935)	Fibroblast (806)	Pericyte (666)	SMC (578)	Ependymal (1546)	Capillaries (857)	Veins (887)	Arteries (650)
<i>APPdup</i>	95.2% (890)	87.6% (706)	86.8% (578)	89.4% (517)	80.4% (1243)	94.5% (810)	93.3% (828)	95.8% (623)
<i>APPdup isogenic</i>	96.5% (902)	89.7% (723)	88.4% (589)	90.7% (524)	82.1% (1270)	95.7% (820)	94.9% (842)	97.4% (633)
<i>DS1</i>	94.8% (886)	86.0% (693)	84.8% (565)	88.2% (510)	79.7% (1232)	94.3% (808)	92.7% (822)	95.8% (623)
<i>DS1 isogenic</i>	95.5% (893)	90.3% (728)	88.7% (591)	91.7% (530)	81.7% (1263)	95.0% (814)	93.8% (832)	96.6% (628)
<i>WTS60</i>	94.4% (883)	83.4% (672)	82.7% (551)	85.6% (495)	76.8% (1188)	93.6% (802)	92.1% (817)	95.1% (618)

B

Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

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A

B

Clone E2: 1bp deletion (C) on one *APP* copy

Supplementary Figure 1

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Supplementary Figure 2

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Supplementary Figure 3

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Supplementary Figure 4

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Supplementary Figure 5

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FeatureID	Line	FC	FDR	Status	Average expression (cpm)
APP	DS1	1.87	4.25E-16	Up in DS1	1658.91
	<i>APPdup</i>	1.47	7.95E-05	Up in <i>APPdup</i>	1920.15
DYRK1A	DS1	1.67	6.04E-10	Up in DS1	33.50
	<i>APPdup</i>	1.37	2.56E-03	Up in <i>APPdup</i>	25.30
ERG	DS1	1.94	6.44E-06	Up in DS1	213.90
	<i>APPdup</i>	1.29	2.12E-03	Up in <i>APPdup</i>	213.28
GABPA	DS1	1.42	6.83E-04	Up in DS1	16.64
	<i>APPdup</i>	1.30	1.27E-02	Up in <i>APPdup</i>	19.38
RUNX1	DS1	-10.18	4.39E-77	Down in DS1	4.60
	<i>APPdup</i>	-2.26	1.32E-02	Down in <i>APPdup</i>	2.65
IL10RB	DS1	2.41	3.15E-19	Up in DS1	43.91
	<i>APPdup</i>	-1.38	6.03E-04	Down in <i>APPdup</i>	32.74
BACE2	DS1	7.70	1.34E-70	Up in DS1	240.19
	<i>APPdup</i>	-1.54	2.51E-02	Down in <i>APPdup</i>	84.58
POFUT2	DS1	1.57	1.19E-22	Up in DS1	60.85
	<i>APPdup</i>	-1.35	9.86E-05	Down in <i>APPdup</i>	51.18

Table 1

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Junction type	FeatureID	Line	FC	FDR	Status	average expression (cpm)
Adherens junctions	PECAM1 (CD31)	DS1	2.74	1.94E-18	Up in DS1	1558
		APPdup	-1.16	0.39	Not regulated	2239
	CDH5 (VE-cadherin)	DS1	1.75	1.10E-08	Up in DS1	971
		APPdup	-1.01	0.96	Not regulated	1007
Tight junctions	CLDN5 (Claudin 5)	DS1	2.35	7.52E-04	Up in DS1	481
		APPdup	1.23	0.62	Not regulated	453
	OCLN (Occludin)	DS1	1.90	8.31E-06	Up in DS1	13
		APPdup	-1.02	0.97	Not regulated	5.94
	TJP1 (ZO1)	DS1	1.09	0.61	Not regulated	103
		APPdup	1.31	3.19E-03	Up in APPdup	102
	TJP2 (ZO2)	DS1	1.80	1.28E-20	Up in DS1	83
		APPdup	1.01	0.97	Not regulated	90
	TJP3 (ZO3)	DS1	not expressed			
		APPdup				
	F11R (JAM1)	DS1	1.84	2.40E-13	Up in DS1	142
		APPdup	1.01	0.96	Not regulated	126
	JAM2	DS1	1.45	0.45	Not regulated	1.67
		APPdup	-1.63	0.29	Not regulated	0.93
JAM3	DS1	2.12	1.20E-15	Up in DS1	239	
	APPdup	1.33	0.02	Up in APPdup	219	
ESAM	DS1	1.82	1.03E-07	Up in DS1	581	
	APPdup	1.07	0.58	Not regulated	650	

Table 2

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Description	setSize	Condition	setSize expressed	Enrichment Score	NES	pvalue	p.adjust	qvalues
Endothelial gene list	935	DS1	899	0.48	1.67	1.68E-4	8.38E-4	5.29E-4
		<i>APPdup</i>	908	0.39	1.41	5.98E-4	1.77E-3	1.12E-3
Positive correlation with CAA	334	DS1	308	0.26	0.83	0.92	0.92	0.58
		<i>APPdup</i>	310	0.49	1.67	7.09E-4	1.77E-3	1.12E-3
Negative correlation with CAA	350	DS1	326	0.48	1.55	1.27E-3	3.18E-3	2.01E-3
		<i>APPdup</i>	325	0.33	1.13	0.19	0.31	0.20

Table 3

Supplementary Annexes

Supplementary Annex 4: Congress participation and presentations

- Doctoral School Days, May 19–20, 2022, Paris, France – *Poster presentation*
- FENS Forum of Neuroscience, July 9–13, 2022, Paris, France – *Poster presentation*
- GO-DS21 Consortium Meeting, September 18–20, 2022, Barcelona, Spain – *Oral presentation*
- NeuroFrance, May 24–26, 2023, Lyon, France – *Poster presentation*
- Doctoral School Days, June 19–20, 2023, Paris, France – *Poster presentation*
- GO-DS21 Consortium Meeting, September 7–9, 2023, Paris, France – *Oral presentation*
- AD/PD 2024 (Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s Diseases Conference), March 5–9, 2024, Lisbon, Portugal – *Poster presentation*
- T21RS International Conference, June 5–8, 2024, Rome, Italy – *Co-chair and oral presentation*

Comprendre le rôle des cellules endothéliales dans le développement de l'angiopathie amyloïde cérébrale dans la maladie d'Alzheimer et la trisomie 21

Résumé :

La trisomie 21 (DS) est caractérisée par une déficience intellectuelle et un risque élevé de développer la maladie d'Alzheimer (MA) à un âge précoce. La MA chez les personnes porteuses de trisomie 21 (MA-DS) partage des caractéristiques clés avec ses autres formes autosomiques dominantes (MAAD), notamment chez les individus présentant une microduplication du gène *APP* (*APPdup*), les deux conditions étant associées à une triple copie du gène *APP* et à une surproduction de peptides amyloïde- β ($A\beta$). Pourtant, malgré ce point commun génétique, les personnes atteintes de MA-DS présentent une moindre incidence d'angiopathie amyloïde cérébrale (AAC) et d'hémorragies intracérébrales que les patients *APPdup*, suggérant l'existence de mécanismes protecteurs liés à la trisomie 21. La barrière hémato-encéphalique (BHE), en grande partie assurée par les cellules endothéliales (CEs), joue un rôle central dans la clairance de l' $A\beta$ et constitue une cible principale de l'AAC.

Nous avons développé un modèle de CE humaines *in vitro* à partir de cellules souches pluripotentes induites différenciées, de lignées DS, *APPdup*, de leurs témoins isogéniques, ainsi que d'un donneur sain. Ces cellules expriment les marqueurs typiques de la BHE, notamment les protéines de jonction serrée et d'adhérence. Les dosages d' $A\beta$ par ELISA et spectrométrie de masse ont révélé une sécrétion accrue d' $A\beta_{40}$ et $A\beta_{42}$ dans les CEs DS et *APPdup*, avec des profils peptidiques distincts. Les analyses d'expression génique ont montré une dérégulation plus marquée dans les CEs DS, incluant des signatures positivement associées à l'adhésion cellulaire, l'angiogenèse, l'immunité et la voie endo-lysosomale, mais une réduction des voies liées à la prolifération. À l'inverse, les CEs *APPdup* présentaient des altérations moindres, incluant une baisse de la traduction et un profil ambigu plutôt négatif concernant les gènes de jonctions et d'adhérence. Certaines de ces différences pourraient s'expliquer par la surexpression de gènes du chromosome 21. En outre, les gènes associés à une moindre sévérité de l'AAC sont enrichis dans les profils DS, tandis que ceux favorisant l'AAC sont enrichis chez *APPdup*. Des immunofluorescences ont confirmé une expression plus importante des protéines de jonction dans les CEs DS, et les tests de perméabilité ont mis en évidence une perméabilité réduite chez DS, mais augmentée chez *APPdup*.

Ces résultats suggèrent une meilleure intégrité de la BHE chez les individus trisomiques, ce qui pourrait contribuer à leur relative protection contre l'AAC. Toutefois, la faible prolifération combinée à une angiogenèse altérée pourraient affecter négativement la BHE avec l'âge.

Mots clés : [Trisomie 21, Maladie d'Alzheimer, Angiopathie amyloïde cérébrale, Duplication de l'*APP*, Barrière hémato-encéphalique, Cellules endothéliales, hiPSC, Jonctions endothéliales, $A\beta$, Dysfonctionnement vasculaire]

Understanding the role of endothelial cells in cerebral amyloid angiopathy development in Alzheimer disease and Down syndrome

Abstract :

Down syndrome (DS), caused by trisomy 21, is associated with intellectual disability and a high risk of developing Alzheimer's disease (AD) in midlife. AD in DS (DSAD) shares major features with other autosomal dominant AD (ADAD), particularly in individuals with *APP* microduplication (*APPdup*), as both conditions involve three copies of the *APP* gene and overproduction of amyloid- β ($A\beta$). Despite this shared genetic driver, DSAD shows reduced cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) and fewer intracerebral hemorrhages than *APPdup*, suggesting the presence of protective factors in DS. The blood-brain barrier (BBB), largely maintained by endothelial cells (ECs), plays a key role in $A\beta$ clearance and is a primary site of damage in CAA.

To investigate EC-specific contributions to the protection against CAA in DS, we developed a human *in vitro* model using hiPSC-derived ECs from DS and *APPdup* lines, their isogenic controls, and a healthy donor line. These ECs expressed canonical BBB markers, including tight and adherens junction proteins. $A\beta$ quantification by ELISA and mass spectrometry revealed hiPSC-ECs secrete $A\beta$ peptides with increased $A\beta_{40}$ and $A\beta_{42}$ in both DS and *APPdup* ECs, with distinct peptide profiles. Transcriptomic analyses (DGE, GSEA, WGCNA) showed broader dysregulation in DS ECs, including positive correlation to cell adhesion, angiogenesis, immune response, and lysosomal function, but negative correlation to cell cycle and proliferation. *APPdup* ECs showed subtler changes, with decreased translation and targeting to the membrane but also mixed negative regulation of adhesion genes. Some of these changes could be linked to specific chromosome 21 genes. Moreover, CAA-associated genes negatively linked to pathology were enriched in DS dysregulation, while *APPdup* showed enrichment in CAA-promoting genes. Immunostaining confirmed higher junction protein expression in DS ECs. Permeability assays showed reduced permeability in DS ECs, and an increase in *APPdup* ECs, consistent with transcriptional findings.

Overall, our results suggest that despite similar *APP* dosage, DS ECs maintain stronger junctional integrity and reduced permeability, which may underlie their reduced CAA vulnerability. However, impaired proliferation and altered angiogenesis in DS may negatively impact long-term BBB function with aging.

Keywords : [Down syndrome, Alzheimer's disease, Cerebral amyloid angiopathy, *APP* microduplication, Blood-brain barrier, Endothelial cells, hiPSCs, Endothelial junctions, $A\beta$ peptides, Vascular dysfunction]